

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Progress in Energy and Combustion Science

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/pecs

Temperature measurement techniques for gas and liquid flows using thermographic phosphor tracer particles

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 16 December 2016
Accepted 11 September 2017
Available online xxx

Keywords:

Thermometry
Thermographic phosphors
Laser diagnostics
Turbulent flows
Temperature
Velocimetry

ABSTRACT

Optical diagnostics for fluid temperature measurements continue to further our understanding of flows involving heat transfer and/or chemical reactions, which are intrinsic to key areas including energy production, the process industries, transportation, heating/cooling systems and naturally-occurring thermal convection. Besides temperature, all flows must also be described by their velocity. As these flows are often turbulent, an important capability is to measure both velocity and temperature at the same time to capture, for example, the turbulent heat flux term appearing in the energy conservation equation.

This paper reviews temperature measurement techniques for fluid flows that are based on thermographic phosphors, which are materials that possess temperature-dependent luminescence properties. Phosphor particles are seeded into the fluid flow of interest. Following laser excitation, the luminescence of the particles is detected, and the temperature measurement is derived using either the spectral intensity ratio or the lifetime. The same particles can also be used for velocity measurements using well-established particle-based approaches, such as laser Doppler velocimetry (LDV) or particle image velocimetry (PIV), producing instantaneously correlated vector-scalar data. First introduced over a decade ago, this concept has since evolved and is currently capable of two-dimensional measurements in the temperature range 200–900 K. At lower temperatures a single-shot spatial precision better than 4 K is possible, as is imaging at sampling rates in the multi-kHz range. The approach is flexible, allowing, for example, techniques which probe single particles for point measurements with a 200 μm spatial resolution. Besides many validation experiments, the method has been applied in internal combustion engines, a falling film absorber, a high-pressure reaction vessel and in enclosed wind tunnels to study various turbulent heat transfer and reactive flow phenomena.

The objective of this article is to provide the first review of this emerging field. The focus is on 1) the method: how has the principle of phosphor thermometry been used for flow measurements, and what instrumentation and processing steps were implemented; 2) how phosphor particles were characterised, and which phosphors are best-suited to temperature measurements in flows; and 3) the applications of the technique. Throughout, and with a detailed analysis of various sources of error, the review endeavours to compare the work and identify common aspects, advantages and limitations of the studies that led to successful flow measurements, and therefore should serve as a guide for researchers using the method. The article also briefly summarises the various challenges which the authors consider are key to the future development of these diagnostics.

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2017.09.001>

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1. Introduction

The universal role of temperature in heat and mass transport processes and chemical reactions makes it a variable of fundamental thermodynamic importance, and much effort is directed toward the measurement of gas and liquid temperatures. Methods that do not disturb delicate yet sometimes hostile flow systems are preferable and so a rich variety of optical diagnostic approaches have been developed, especially since the advent of the laser, and used to remotely probe the temperature of fluid flows both in-situ and in laboratory scale experiments. We highlight the areas of convective heat transfer, which underlies the exchange of thermal energy in a huge range of engineering components and process industries, such as the

cooling of power generation engines and electronic microchips, oil and gas extraction, transportation, material processing, refrigeration, and the ventilation of buildings and transport vehicles; turbulent natural convection, which occurs in systems of geophysical interest like the Earth's oceans, atmosphere and mantle; and turbulent combustion, where the influence of the turbulent flow field on the reaction chemistry variously alters flame ignition, propagation, stabilisation and extinction and may lead to dangerous flow instabilities/feedback e.g. thermoacoustic oscillations in gas turbines, in turn affecting their safe operation as well as the efficiency and emission of harmful pollutants. Given the importance of such fluid flows in energy and combustion science, and in many scientific fields beyond these, detailed and comprehensive knowledge about them is needed. The inherent

complexity of the systems being studied means that the development of optical measurement techniques for multiple flow variables, e.g. pressure, chemical species, quantity representing state of mixing, e.g. mixture fraction, specific pollutants and most especially the fluid temperature, continues to be a crucial area of research.

In addition, to capture the transport processes in a flow of liquid or gas it is necessary to measure the velocity. In many practical situations, the flow field is not the same everywhere and is turbulent, that is, it fluctuates rapidly in space and time. Measurements that are averaged in a temporal sense or across a volume are usually far insufficient to capture the required physical detail. Therefore laser-based point measurements of velocity and scalar quantities, which are quasi-instantaneous (that is, a short measurement duration with regard to the time scales of the fluid flow) were developed, including laser Doppler velocimetry (LDV), laser Rayleigh scattering and coherent anti-Stokes Raman scattering (CARS). Laser diagnostics have since advanced to two-dimensional flowfield imaging and now even into three-dimensions, affording unprecedented insight into turbulent flows. Thousands of measurements, each with a high spatial resolution, are contained in every image. Instantaneous snapshots of flow structures covering a range of spatial scales are accessible by laser imaging methods, permitting resolution of the gradients that drive the transport of momentum, chemical species, and thermal energy. High sampling rates of kHz-MHz are able to reveal transient turbulent flow phenomena and rare events. In these ways, there are three main uses of laser-based measurement techniques (for each we name just a few examples from hundreds): to investigate specific fundamental phenomena (e.g. differential diffusion of H_2 in free turbulent jets [1]); to provide well-documented experimental data for comparison with numerical simulations (such as the Turbulent Non-premixed Flame [2] and Engine Combustion Network [3] databases); and to probe generic or specific configurations to understand particular engineering systems (e.g. combustion in Diesel engines [4]). This last point betrays the curious fact that much vital technology such as boilers, combustors, furnaces, heating and cooling devices, are much older than our ability to measure or model them, and therefore fully understand their operation.

Though measurements of temperature and velocity are of great value, in turbulent flows an additional and demanding capability is to measure both variables at the same time. With this information, it is possible to measure the turbulent transport of heat - the turbulent diffusion terms; and also gain a deep understanding of the coupling between the turbulent flow and various phenomena intimately linked to the fluid temperature, for example buoyancy forces and/or rate of chemical reactions. Joint measurements are also necessary to achieve statistically significant measurements for nonstationary processes or in transient flows which are not easily reproduced experimentally. Many previous review articles of laser-based diagnostics have stressed the value of simultaneous measurements of scalar quantities and flow velocity [5–8]. However, as well as combined measurements being something of a longstanding challenge in flow diagnostics, temperature is a notoriously difficult parameter to measure.

The aim of this paper is to review a class of laser-based fluid temperature diagnostics based on thermographic phosphors, which are solid materials with temperature-dependent luminescence properties. Phosphor particles are seeded into the gas or liquid as a flow “tracer”, taken to mean that they effectively match the temperature (and velocity) of the surrounding fluid. The particles are probed using lasers and the luminescence emission is detected using appropriate sensors to determine the flow temperature. By various, usually well-established velocimetry techniques, the same phosphor particles can readily be used as a tracer to measure the flow velocity.

There are innumerable types of thermographic phosphors and different ways in which the luminescence properties are influenced by temperature. Therefore various implementations of this general concept have emerged which provide point and two-dimensional field

measurements, at sampling rates up to several kHz and covering different temperature ranges. Especially in the last ten years, the method has evolved into a versatile diagnostic that is finding increasing use for fundamental and applied research. This paper is to the knowledge of the authors the first review of these techniques. In this introduction, we provide a brief overview of the measurement principle (Section 1.1), and a short technical summary (Section 1.2) aimed only at those interested in the main findings of this comparative exercise. A short historical review of studies that used thermographic phosphors for fluid temperature measurements is then presented in Section 1.3. To frame the emergence of this method, Section 1.4 considers existing (state-of-the-art) techniques for temperature and velocity measurements. Section 1.5 guides the reader through the contents of the review paper.

1.1. Measurement concept

Inorganic phosphors are solid crystalline materials, generally consisting of particles with a size in the nm to μm range i.e. in fine powder form, which exhibit the phenomenon of luminescence. They are used in a large variety of applications including fluorescent lamps, night vision devices (image intensifier phosphor screens), light-emitting diode (LED) bulbs, plasma display panels, security labelling, optical fibers, lasers, solar cells, medical treatment (photodynamic therapy) and imaging, and glow-in-the-dark materials. In the most general sense they are used to convert incoming radiation, e.g. X-rays, γ -rays, electron beam and ultraviolet (UV) light, into light in the visible region of the spectrum. As an example, in a fluorescent lamp, a low-pressure mercury vapour produces a narrow UV line at 254 nm under excitation by an electric arc. This harmful and invisible radiation is absorbed by a layer of phosphor powder to produce visible luminescence.

This is the basic principle. Upon absorption of electromagnetic radiation, the electrons in the phosphor material are promoted from a ground state to a higher energy state which may then be followed by a radiative decay (luminescence). Note that due to internal relaxation processes, the emission is almost always spectrally shifted away from the excitation. Depending on both radiative and non-radiative transition rates, light emission can persist for an extended time after the excitation source is removed, ranging from sub-nanosecond to minutes or even hours. The energy states between which radiative transitions occur are determined by the electronic structure of the solid material. The presence of impurities usually deliberately introduced into the “host” material (for example aluminium oxide Al_2O_3 or barium magnesium aluminate $BaMgAl_{10}O_{17}$) serve to change or introduce completely new energy levels, leading to luminescence properties very different to that of the original insulating compound. These “dopant” impurities are normally lanthanide (rare-earths, for example europium (Eu), holmium (Ho) etc) or transition metal (for example manganese (Mn), chromium (Cr) etc) ions. One can immediately see that the variety of materials which may be termed a phosphor is enormous. In its own right, the production of phosphors and characterisation of their luminescence properties is, to quote Dorenbos, an “unimaginably large” (and growing) field of materials research [9].

Temperature has a strong influence on the luminescence properties. There are two main types of temperature dependence: the change in the duration of the persistence of the luminescence after excitation, that is, the emission lifetime; and the relative change of the emission spectrum. Additional quantities such as the absolute emission intensity, the luminescence risetime or the excitation spectrum may also be temperature-dependent [10], but those are usually found to be of limited use in practical applications. For decades, both the emission lifetime and spectral responses have been exploited for remote thermometry, forming two broad classes of methods: the time-resolved methods and the spectrally-resolved methods. Thermographic phosphors have been extensively used for the

temperature measurement of surfaces, even preceding the advent of the laser in 1960 [10]. A thin layer of phosphor (thickness 0.5–50 μm) is coated onto the surface of interest and typically illuminated with a pulsed light source. The luminescence emission following the excitation pulse is then detected and either the spectral or temporal content are recorded and analysed to derive the surface temperature. We recommend extensive review articles on the topic [10–12].

For many phosphors, there is little evidence that the luminescence, which originates from centers in the solid phase, is influenced by the pressure and composition of the surrounding fluid. Additional benefits conferred by the materials are that they are chemically inert and normally have a high melting point. Therefore they are very well suited to measurements in harsh, reactive environments, and were used as such, e.g. in internal combustion engines, afterburners, gas turbine combustor walls (see aforementioned reviews). Furthermore, phosphors tend to possess broad excitation spectra, facilitating excitation via a range of possible light sources, including lasers common to many laboratories, for example Nd:YAG and harmonics. The luminescence emission of many phosphors is in the visible spectral region, simplifying the signal collection and detection using ordinary scientific cameras and detectors. The vast range of phosphors provides broad scope in selecting a phosphor with the right luminescence properties for a specific application.

For all these reasons, thermographic phosphor particles are clearly an attractive tracer material for temperature measurements in fluid flows. To illustrate the basic concept early on in this article, an example is shown in the photograph in Fig. 1. In this experiment, the phosphor zinc oxide (ZnO) was seeded into a liquid nitrogen-cooled jet of air. A UV laser light sheet was directed downwards through the jet. The luminescence emission of the ZnO particles peaks at ~ 390 nm in the near-visible UV spectral region. Using a cheap mobile phone camera, this luminescence was recorded as the bright blue-coloured light emanating from the jet, clearly visible in this photograph. If the luminescence were detected in an appropriate fashion, it is this same signal that yields the particle temperature.

As solid μm -size particles, phosphor particles also naturally serve as a tracer material for conventional particle-based velocimetry measurements, such as LDV or particle image velocimetry (PIV, see Section 1.4), or even velocimetry methods also based on capturing the luminescence emission of the particles. Fig. 2 shows a typical

Fig. 2. A typical imaging setup for simultaneous temperature and velocity measurements using thermographic phosphor particles.

setup for simultaneous temperature and velocity imaging. Overlapping laser light sheets define the measurement plane in the flow of interest, here a turbulent jet or flame, which is seeded with appropriate thermographic phosphor particles. One (ultraviolet) laser excites the particles, which emit luminescence. Here, this signal is detected by two cameras equipped with suitable spectral filters and these two images are used to derive the instantaneous temperature field. In this example ordinary particle image velocimetry is used to simultaneously measure the velocity field, consisting of another double-pulse (visible) laser to illuminate the same particles, and an additional camera to detect the Mie scattering signal.

This method, named “thermographic PIV”, is only the most common realisation of the method. The following section summarises only the main aspects and current capabilities of the general concept.

1.2. Technical summary

There are four important and linked considerations for those interested in these diagnostics. These basically follow the structure of the review article from Sections 3–6. First is the approach: there are many implementations using either temporal or spectral methods, and each provides different capabilities (see Section 3). For two-dimensional measurements a two-camera system with beamsplitter to obtain a two colour intensity ratio, effectively that shown in Fig. 2 above, is the most widely-used and versatile approach for instantaneous measurements. On short time scales, imaging methods using the strong sensitivity of the lifetime are currently difficult to implement, primarily due to hardware limitations. However, there are strategies for lifetime-based point measurements. Velocity measurements can be performed simultaneously with the same tracer, usually using separate PIV system (for planar measurements) and LDV (for point measurements) for greater flexibility, but there are other ways to perform the measurements using fewer cameras and lasers, for example using the particle luminescence for PIV.

Second is the choice of phosphor from a vast number of possible materials, each with very different luminescence properties. A suitable phosphor should be bright, have a short luminescence lifetime (< 10 's of μs is preferable for measurements in turbulent gas flows), a suitable sensitivity to temperature over the range of interest and ideally no additional sensitivities (e.g. on the excitation laser fluence or fluid composition/pressure). A dozen phosphors (and co-doped variants) have been used for fluid thermometry (for a concise summary, see Table 1 in Section 4 of this review), but only BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO have been characterised and compared for a known particle concentration [13–17]. The main findings are that the luminescence signal is high enough so that a moderate seeding density (10^{11} particles/ m^3) is generally sufficient for precise measurements. ZnO is more sensitive to temperature (3–5 times) but the drop of luminescence signal with temperature is also more pronounced, and the laser fluence has a stronger influence on the measured temperature (a 10% variation in fluence results in a 6 K temperature change), requiring a corrective procedure. The luminescence emission of

Fig. 1. Photograph of a liquid nitrogen-cooled jet of air seeded with zinc oxide phosphor particles, taken with a cheap CMOS sensor. The jet flows from the pipe in the right-left direction. A laser light sheet propagates downwards through the jet and excites the particles, generating the luminescence which is recorded as the bright blue colour. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

BAM:Eu²⁺ was also shown to be independent of the oxygen concentration in the range 0–200 mbar between 300 and 920 K, and to be unaffected by short (~1 s) high temperature (> 2000 K) exposures. Similar studies of other phosphors used for fluid thermometry as well as many others are necessary to improve the capabilities of the technique. This may be done using methods to probe dispersed particles, described in Section 4 of this review.

Third is sources of uncertainty (Section 5). From a theoretical standpoint, the proof of concept stems from the ability of a solid μm-size particle to trace the fluid temperature. Heat transfer models show that a particle of a given size responds equally fast to changes in flow velocity or fluid temperature, and that radiation has little effect. The response time is on the order of 10's μs for 1 μm spherical phosphor particles, appropriate for measurements in a range of turbulent flows. Also, for the moderate seeding densities mentioned above, the particles do not affect the bulk properties of the fluid. As it stands, the most prominent sources of uncertainty are surface luminescence from particles deposited on surfaces and multiple scattering by dispersed particles in the fluid phase. Surface luminescence puts restrictions on near wall measurements, while multiple scattering was shown to be a serious issue when using BAM:Eu²⁺ in large-volume seeded flows [16]. Further investigations are needed to estimate its impact in specific flow configurations as well as for other phosphors. The potential of structured laser illumination to address both issues has been investigated [18].

The final consideration is the required measurement capabilities for the intended application. In terms of temperature range, the upper temperature limit is linked to the phosphor quenching behaviour and its temperature sensitivity. ZnO and BAM:Eu²⁺ phosphors have been used between 300–500 K and 230–950 K respectively (see Section 6). Other phosphors such as Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Pr³⁺, which was used in the range 300–900 K, Y₂O₂S:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺, in the range 300–423 K, and others need further characterisation of the absolute signal level to assess their thermometric performance. In terms of spatial resolution, 200 μm can be achieved for point measurements, while for imaging the typical reported resolution is generally lower (200–500 μm) with domains around several 10's–100 mm. The temporal resolution is typically 1–10 Hz, but sampling rates up to 6 kHz have been achieved for imaging [19,20] as well as for point measurement approaches using cw lasers [21,22]. Finally concerning the temperature resolution, or precision, approximate guidelines are provided for planar imaging configurations: a few K over the range 300–500 K with ZnO (which was not tested at higher temperature) and 10–50 K for BAM:Eu²⁺ over the range 200–920 K. For applications where precise point temperature measurements are needed, higher precision (better than 1%) is possible using lifetime-based approaches.

1.3. Historical review

To our knowledge, the first implementation of phosphor particles for fluid measurements were in the 70's, to image streaks using the long luminescence emission of the particles [23]. However the first known example of thermometry in fluids using thermographic phosphors was by Miller and Keyhani, who in 2001 performed liquid-phase point temperature measurement in a free falling LiBr film using the highly temperature-sensitive lifetime of the phosphor La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺, as part of a heat and mass transfer study of absorption chillers [24]. This temperature diagnostic was developed jointly with Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Tennessee, USA. It was there in 2004 that Allison et al., pioneers in phosphor thermometry on surfaces, first laid out the advantages of using phosphor particles as flow tracers [25]. On top of their list was that phosphor particles “may yield temperature information as well as function in the usual way as light scatterers for laser Doppler velocimetry” and that, since phosphors usually consist of ceramic material, they are therefore “quite robust in surviving and functioning in harsh high temperature

environments”. Actually it was not until 2015 that phosphor particles were used in conjunction with LDV to yield simultaneous temperature and velocity point measurements [21], but in 2004 researchers in Lund University in Sweden explored several concepts for fluid temperature measurements using phosphors. They used La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ and Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ phosphor particles, dispersed into water or isoctane to measure volume-averaged temperatures of falling and levitating droplets, with the time-resolved and spectrally-resolved methods respectively [26,27]. Using a fast framing camera, they extended phosphor lifetime thermometry to 2D measurements inside droplets and sprays [28]. In the aforementioned studies, the UV harmonics (355 and 266 nm) of pulsed (10 ns) Nd:YAG lasers were used for excitation. The 2006 study of Brübach et al. (at Technische Universität Darmstadt, Germany) was similar in this respect, but used a two-colour intensity ratio approach to image average temperature distributions in n-dodecane fuel sprays [29]. This basic principle, that is, pulsed laser (typically Nd:YAG) excitation and two-colour imaging of different bands of the luminescence emission, has since been used for the majority of fluid thermometry studies. This is because it permits a short integration time (~μs), which is usually required for adequate temporal resolution in turbulent flows. These studies were in liquid flows, where the temperature range is inherently limited.

In 2007, the Lund research group started work in gas flows with the main aim of operating in a reactive high-temperature environments such as internal combustion (IC) engines. At this stage, the field of high temperature surface phosphor thermometry was focused on phosphors with slow luminescence transitions such as Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Dy³⁺ (the yttrium aluminium garnet host is commonly abbreviated to YAG) or Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺, since the decay time (in the ms to μs range) could be accurately measured. Due to thermal quenching processes the luminescence signal and lifetime decreases with temperature; the lifetime of YAG:Dy³⁺ is sensitive at temperatures as high as 2000 K [30]. YAG:Dy³⁺ also shows pronounced changes of the emission spectrum over that temperature range and so seemed a particularly attractive option for 2D measurements using the two-colour ratio-based approach. For this reason, this phosphor was the initial choice of many research groups, including ours. In 2007, Hasegawa et al. reported 2D single-shot measurements of gas temperature [31]. They seeded 4 μm YAG:Dy³⁺ particles in both a heated jet and an internal combustion engine running in homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) mode with the aim of investigating the development of ignition kernels [32,33]. However, YAG:Dy³⁺ has poor absorption characteristics, and the lifetime is 1 ms at room temperature. Usually the luminescence signal from dispersed particles in a fluid is a limiting factor, especially at high temperatures. Furthermore, in turbulent flows using an appropriate exposure time on the μs-scale with a long lifetime phosphor suffers from the rejection of the majority of the signal. These principles were stated at the end of a 2010 paper aimed at determining the survivability of YAG:Dy³⁺ particles passing through a flame; these principles have not changed since: “For future development... the challenge is to search for a thermographic phosphor type that has both a short lifetime and a strong signal at high temperature” [34]. A later study from Brunel University, London, UK showed that even for a long exposure of 100 μs and YAG:Dy³⁺ particles as large as 10 μm, the signal was too weak for single-shot measurements, even at room temperature [35]. Other studies from different research groups experienced similar difficulties with low signal levels [36–38].

Phosphor particles can be used as a tracer for LDV or PIV, and indeed one of the key aspects of this measurement concept is to measure both temperature and velocity simultaneously. Also at Lund, in 2008, the first simultaneous measurements were reported in a heated air jet and recirculating flows with the phosphor Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ [39]. Though this phosphor is much brighter than

YAG:Dy³⁺ (it is used in fluorescent lamps), it also has a long lifetime of 3 ms at room temperature [40]. Only time-average measurements were reported since signal levels were reportedly too low.

Around the same time, the Lund group also investigated the luminescence properties of a range of commercial phosphor powders with fast luminescence transitions [41]. Among them were two phosphors with the desired short lifetime ZnO:Zn (< 1 ns), and BaMgAl₁₀O₁₇:Eu²⁺ (1 μs), also referred to as BAM:Eu²⁺. The emission of ZnO containing gallium and excess zinc was used for temperature measurements in burning methanol droplets [42]. BAM:Eu²⁺ was mentioned at this time as a tracer to study Diesel combustion [43]. However it was not until 2012 that our research group, then at Imperial College in London, UK, presented the first examples of single shot temperature and velocity imaging using 2.4 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles [44]. A theoretical conduction-based heat transfer analysis showed that the ability of the particles to follow changes in fluid temperature degrades with the square of the particle diameter [44], the same as for the particle velocity (see Section 5.2). The same study also showed that the phosphor spectral signature can be used to visualise the mixing between two gas streams. Other groups used BAM:Eu²⁺ for gas-phase temperature imaging, in a high pressure reaction vessel [37] and in a heated jet [35]. The research group of David Rothamer at University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA used different phosphors, the upconversion phosphor Y₂O₂S:Er³⁺, Yb³⁺ [45] and YAG:Pr³⁺ [46]. The latter was applied to image instantaneous temperature and velocity fields in a motored IC engine [47] and in the shear layer between air and a vitiated stream of combustion gases [48].

Our research group then demonstrated that precise single shot temperature and velocity measurements at kHz sampling rates were possible using the phosphor BAM:Eu²⁺ and high speed DPSS lasers and non-intensified high-speed CMOS cameras [19]. Such diagnostics offer comprehensive time-resolved datasets of fluid mechanical instabilities, as demonstrated in a Von Kármán vortex stream, and later in a gas turbine film cooling flow [20].

In the following years (2014–2015), building on earlier studies [49,50], our research efforts were directed towards quantitative characterisation of the luminescence properties of phosphor particles dispersed in the fluid, to determine how much light a single particle emits and evaluate potential sources of error e.g. fluid composition, O₂ partial pressure, laser fluence [13]. Recognising that the luminescence and thermal properties of immobile packed powders are different from that of moving individual particles, in-situ characterisation studies were performed, which in gases requires a measure of the number density of particles [51]. This permits comparison of different phosphors and assessment of possible intrusive effects of the particles. Using these tools, it was possible to identify a more than three-fold improvement in the temperature measurement precision when using the phosphor ZnO in place of BAM:Eu²⁺ at an equivalent particle number density [14]. ZnO was since applied again in liquids [15], extending the portfolio of existing liquid thermometry techniques.

The majority of the studies cited so far used the two-colour ratio-based imaging technique. Instead, a concept for 2D measurements of temperature and velocity based on the luminescence lifetime and a single high-speed camera was proposed and used in a motored IC engine [52], to resolve both the luminescence decay of the phosphor and the displacement of the particles for PIV. A hybrid method was explored for simultaneous temperature and velocity imaging using Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺, a phosphor with a long lifetime at room temperature (> 100 μs) [53]. With an interline transfer CCD camera and an image intensifier, the luminescence of the particles can be recorded twice within a short time delay, which yields the particle velocity field, the temperature being simultaneously derived from the two-colour ratio approach. In 2015 our research group extended the LDV technique to high-resolution simultaneous point measurement of temperature and velocity by probing the luminescence and scattering of individual

BAM:Eu²⁺ phosphor particles crossing continuous wave laser beams [21,22].

The strength of simultaneous single-shot 2D temperature and velocity measurements was exploited in 2016 in Refs. [16,20] to calculate the turbulent heat flux terms $u_i T'$ in gas turbine film cooling flows and a turbulent heated jet. Such measurements are essential to understand turbulent mixing and heat transfer phenomena. The technique was also applied in non-premixed hydrogen flames [17].

It is clear that the concept of measuring fluid temperatures using thermographic phosphor particles has seen considerable developments. The primary motivation was to seek temperature (and simultaneous velocity) measurement capability, as a complement to other existing and emerging diagnostics. These are described in the following section.

1.4. Existing techniques for temperature and velocity measurements in fluids

The following outlines the state-of-the-art in temperature and velocity flow measurements. The aims are twofold: 1) to lay out the advantages and limitations of current diagnostics, for comparison against methods based on thermographic phosphor particles, and 2) to briefly discuss velocimetry techniques, which owing to their prevalence and long history, are given little technical attention in this review. The review is by no means exhaustive and we only cite examples to direct the reader towards the relevant literature. This review will not consider thermometry in systems at the nanoscale, i.e. submicron spatial resolution, even if they use nanophosphor particles (see reviews [54,55]). Though an important and growing field in nanotechnology, microfluidics and biomedicine, this is beyond the scope of this review, which is focused on fluid flows at larger scales.

Velocimetry techniques

Laser Doppler velocimetry (LDV) and particle image velocimetry (PIV) are two standard techniques to measure flow velocities. For both methods tracer particles must be added to the flow, typically in the form of liquid droplets or for reactive flows, solid particles such as aluminium oxide Al₂O₃. These particles should be chosen with a size that is small enough, for example of the order of 1 μm for gases [56], so that they follow the flow motion (for example, response times are in the range 10's of μs for a 1 μm diameter Al₂O₃ particles in air, see Section 5.2). In a typical LDV experiment, two coherent laser beams cross at a point and interfere, thereby generating a set of fringes that defines the probe volume (typically a few hundred μm in size). As particles traverse these fringes they scatter the laser light, which is detected using e.g. a photomultiplier tube (PMT). The frequency of the signal peaks contained in the "Doppler burst" is a function of the (known) fringe spacing and velocity of the particle, and thereby the velocity of the flow in which the particle is entrained. LDV is able to provide high spatial and temporal-resolution measurements of one, two, or all three components of the velocity, at a point [57,58]. Thus normally the flow field must be slowly "mapped" by traversing the LDV probe.

On the other hand, PIV is a well-established technique for measuring the flow velocity in a plane or throughout a volume, thereby furnishing the insights of instantaneous field measurements described in the introduction. To obtain a single velocity field, the seeded particles are illuminated twice in short succession, typically using a pulsed laser (e.g. frequency-doubled Nd:YAG laser at 532 nm, as shown in Fig. 2). A CCD or CMOS camera is normally used to image the particle Mie scattering in a dual-frame approach. An appropriate time delay between the laser pulses is fixed for the experiment so that the particle displacement caused by the flow motion can be identified for each image pair. For this, images are divided into interrogation windows and a cross-correlation algorithm is then used to determine the displacement of groups of

particles in each window. This yields two velocity components in the plane of the light sheet.

From an experimental point of view, PIV is a robust and comparatively simple technique that is very widely used for flow measurements (for further details see Refs. [59,60]). It can be applied to both very small (100's of μm) measurement domains using microscope objectives (micro-PIV [61]) and much larger (metre-scale) facilities (e.g. Ref. [62]). Its versatility is further evidenced by the extensions of the method. Using two cameras that observe the measurement plane at different angles, the displacement of particles in the out-of-plane direction can also be determined to measure all three velocity components (stereo PIV [63]). Using volumetric illumination and multiple cameras, all three velocity components throughout the volume can be determined (tomographic PIV [64]). High repetition rate lasers and high-speed cameras can also be used for time-resolved measurements (high-speed PIV, see for example the review of Böhm et al. for applications in turbulent combustion [65]). Here, high repetition/sampling rates refers to the multi-kHz range, especially important for turbulent gas flows where 1–10 Hz sampling rates cannot track the flow in time. Advances in kHz-rate flow imaging diagnostics have been in part facilitated by developments in off-the-shelf Q-switched (i.e. pulsed) diode-pumped solid state (DPSS) lasers and also high-speed cameras based on CMOS sensor technology. DPSS lasers operate continuously and produce the order of 10's of mJ/pulse at repetition rates in the range 1–10 kHz at 532 nm. Despite the two orders of magnitude lower pulse energy compared to low repetition rate Nd:YAG lasers, PIV can be realised at kHz rates because of the large Mie scattering cross-section of the particles.

We briefly highlight particle tracking velocimetry (PTV) which, unlike PIV, tracks the motion of individual particles. The spatial resolution is no longer limited to the size of the interrogation area. PTV is particularly suitable for measurements very near walls, where PIV is unreliable due to decreasing particle concentration and strong velocity gradients [66].

Velocimetry techniques that do not require solid particle seeding are suitable for specialised applications e.g. flow tagging methods (see for example Refs. [67–69]) for high-velocity or large volume flows that are impossible to seed; or magnetic resonance velocimetry [70] for enclosed flows in complex geometries. However, due to their advantages, especially versatility and experimental simplicity, particle-based techniques like PIV and LDV can be considered the methods of choice for velocity measurements in a very wide range of fluid flows. Then, the main point is that the temperature measurement approach must be compatible with such velocimetry techniques, which inherently means accommodating the presence of Mie scatterers (particles or droplets). This consideration will guide the following overview of flow temperature measurement techniques.

Rayleigh/Raman scattering diagnostics

Rayleigh scattering thermometry is commonly used for gas temperature measurements in combustion research [71,72]. For planar measurements, a laser sheet is formed and elastically-scattered light is imaged perpendicular to the measurement plane. The light scattered by the gas molecules depends on the gas density and can be related directly to temperature if the pressure and the gas composition are constant. A primary constraint is that the Rayleigh scattering cross-section is small ($\sim 10^{-27}$ cm^2/sr) and so the signal is orders of magnitude weaker than the interfering scattering from surfaces around the measurement plane or in the background. This is true also in sooting or particle-laden multiphase flows (e.g. sprays) and of course if particles are deliberately added as an LDV or PIV tracer. However, the spectral overlap of the scattering signals means they cannot be easily separated. A filtered Rayleigh scattering approach [72,73] combines an injection-seeded Nd:YAG laser (with a very high spectral purity, see Refs. [74,75]) and a spectrally sharp atomic or molecular filter, e.g. iodine, to block the unbroadened narrowband

particle/surface Mie scattering but transmit the broadened Rayleigh–Brillouin scattering of the gas molecules. This has been used to perform simultaneous Rayleigh temperature measurements with PIV in premixed flames [76,77]. A second restriction is that the Rayleigh signal is also a function of the average scattering cross-section, which depends on the local gas composition. In combustion this co-dependence limits the method to situations where the scattering cross-section is deemed to vary negligibly throughout the measurement region, or the product of gas density and scattering cross section has a known and monotonic relationship with the temperature. Note that one-dimensional measurements of gas composition may be performed simultaneously by Raman scattering [78–80]. Raman scattering is an inelastic process and occurs at shifted wavelengths characteristic of the energy levels of the scattering molecules. Raman scattering is a powerful technique to measure different species. However it is an even weaker process than Rayleigh scattering (by a factor $\sim 10^{-3}$), and so despite the fact that the Raman signal is spectrally-shifted from the probe laser the method is normally still sensitive to interference and low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [81].

In the context of signal levels, for Rayleigh thermometry generally only low repetition-rate (e.g. 1–10 Hz) frequency-doubled Nd:YAG lasers offer a sufficient pulse energies for adequate SNR, i.e. around 100's of mJ/pulse. At kHz rates, the significantly lower pulse energy of the aforementioned high-speed DPSS lasers has restricted Rayleigh thermometry to point or line (1D) measurements [82]. Instead, specialised, usually custom-built 'pulse-burst' laser systems can be used [83]. Pulse-burst lasers are limited by heat load in the number of consecutive pulses produced (burst duration 1–10 ms) but can deliver pulse energies of the order 1 J at 532 nm and 10 kHz, and can operate at even higher (MHz) rates. These have been applied for high-speed planar Rayleigh imaging in round jets [84] and jet flames [85], and more recently in fuel jets surrounded by a coflow to measure temperature and mixture fraction fields simultaneously [86].

Coherent anti-Stokes Raman scattering spectroscopy

CARS spectroscopy is a powerful technique to measure temperature, species concentrations and pressure, especially in hostile combustion environments [87]. In a typical CARS experiment, the frequencies of the pump and Stokes laser beams are chosen so they resonate with the Raman frequencies of the molecule(s) of interest, e.g. N_2 in air-fed reacting flows, thereby generating a Raman coherence. When a third probe beam crosses the interaction volume, the CARS signal is produced as coherently-scattered radiation along the geometric direction obeying the phase-matching condition. The main advantages are that this signal, from which the gas temperature can be derived, is both directional (laser-like), and spectrally-shifted, allowing one to avoid scattering from particles, surfaces etc. Thus CARS has a reputation for delivering high-precision measurements in very challenging situations, such as industrial coal furnaces [88], fuel sprays [89], IC engines [90,91], gas turbine combustor exhaust streams [92], porous burners [93] and pool fires [94], to name but a few.

Major recent developments involving the use of femtosecond and picosecond lasers for CARS spectroscopy are summarised in the 2010 review of Roy et al. [95]. Depending on the exact CARS approach these developments are overcoming some limitations of ns CARS, variously enabling kHz sampling rates [96], suppression of the nonresonant background signal [97], and, in some circumstances, measurements nearly independent of the collisional environment. However, these advantages do depend upon accurate and detailed modelling to interpret the often complex CARS signals. Remarkable temperature precision (and species sensitivity) has been demonstrated using, for example, advanced hybrid ps/fs-CARS schemes (see e.g. Ref. [98]). There are also exciting prospects for

CARS measurements using a single fs laser beam and pulse shaping techniques [99].

CARS spectroscopy provides instantaneous temperature measurements, usually at a point, with the spatial resolution in one direction limited to ~ 1 mm. It has been extended to line imaging [100] and used to study flame wall interactions [101]. With an alternative two-laser beam method and a 2D imaging spectrometer, CARS has been extended to two-dimensions [102–105], with the field of view currently limited by the laser beam dimensions in the interaction volume and the CCD format to ~ 10 mm \times a few mm. Combined LDV/CARS point measurements have been performed e.g. [106], with a temporal separation between temperature and velocity samples.

When measurements with a still higher precision are needed ($< 1\%$), for example to investigate charge cooling in internal combustion engines, other non-linear techniques such as laser-induced grating spectroscopy may be considered [107,108].

Laser-induced fluorescence thermometry

Laser-induced fluorescence (LIF) techniques involve the electronic excitation of an atom or molecule by the absorption of laser light. The subsequent fast (ns) radiative decay to the ground state is called fluorescence. The signal depends on the species concentration, and possibly the temperature, pressure, and gas composition, permitting simple detection or quantitative measurement of one or several of these quantities. Often the fluorescence emission is spectrally separated from the excitation wavelength, and so LIF methods are in principle compatible with particle-based velocimetry and subject to sufficient laser energy, can be used for planar measurements by forming a light sheet and imaging the fluorescence at 90° . Many different gas-phase tracers can be used for LIF thermometry. Indium atoms, nitric oxide (NO), organic gaseous molecules such as aromatic hydrocarbons or ketones (e.g. toluene, acetone) are examples of tracers that can be added to gas flows, while fluorescent dyes such as rhodamine are typically used in liquids. Also, the temperature of flame radicals e.g. hydroxyl (OH) can be probed in specific regions of the flame. Then, according to the spectroscopic characteristics (absorption/emission, collisional quenching, temperature sensitivity etc) of these tracers there are many different excitation and detection schemes that can be employed for single shot temperature imaging. In the simplest circumstances where laser fluence and tracer concentration can be held constant, single-wavelength excitation and single-colour detection can be used for thermometry by the combined temperature-dependence of the fluorescence signal and gas density i.e. tracer concentration. However in most practical cases this is not so due to flow mixing, chemical reactions and additional functional experimental considerations e.g. tracer condensation. Therefore usually varying levels of sophistication must be introduced by ratio-based measurements.

First we consider atomic fluorescence methods [109] using a two-line excitation technique based on indium. Metal salt e.g. indium chloride or indium particles using laser ablation of an indium rod [110] are seeded into the flow which then produce indium atoms in the flame. Generally, two tunable dye lasers drive transitions from two different ground states to a common excited state. For each pulse, separated by a short (100's of ns) time delay, fluorescence from this upper level to the opposite ground state is monitored to achieve the desired spectral separation [111]. The ground state populations are temperature-dependent, so the ratio of the two signals, imaged using for example two intensified cameras, is a function of temperature. The strong transitions of the atoms saturate fast and the technique has been extended into the nonlinear excitation regime to improve SNR sufficiently for single-shot measurements [112]. The technique is limited to above ~ 800 K where there is a sufficient population of the upper ground state of indium, and for stoichiometric to fuel-rich conditions where indium has not been oxidised [113,114]. Such an

approach has been used for temperature imaging up to 2800 K in non-premixed flames [114] and a fired spark ignition engine [115].

In a similar fashion, molecular tracers added to the flow e.g. NO [116] or naturally present such as OH produced in flames or shock-heated mixtures [117] can be used for single shot thermometry too. Two dye lasers are tuned to probe transitions involving closely-spaced rotational states, to cancel the tracer concentration and quenching effects. Spectrally-shifted UV fluorescence signals are detected using intensified cameras. For OH LIF thermometry, temperature information is only available in post-flame regions > 1200 K, and bias due to the intermittent presence of OH in limited product regions must be considered when obtaining average temperature fields [118]. More detailed discussion in the context of temporally-averaged temperature measurements based on these species is given in Refs. [119–121].

Organic tracers are introduced into gases in various ways (e.g. using a bubbler) so as to produce a gas mixture with some fraction of the vapour in the flow. Organic tracers may be used for mixing studies by directly measuring the concentration by the LIF intensity, see the review [122]. Sufficient seeding concentrations are required, which especially at room temperature and below may be limited by the vapour pressure. LIF thermometry using single-wavelength excitation in the UV and single-colour detection strategies may suffer from tracer concentration inhomogeneities, as discussed for engine applications [123,124]. In the case of toluene, to make the measurement independent of tracer concentration, a dual-colour detection of the temperature-dependent redshift of the UV fluorescence emission can be used for ratio-based temperature imaging. Two-colour toluene LIF has been used to obtain phase-locked measurements of the temperature distribution in a motored SI engine [125]. More recently this technique was applied at a 10 kHz repetition rate in a heated jet of nitrogen impinging on a plate [126], where measurements up to 773 K were presented. Furthermore, it was used in combination with PIV at 6 kHz to investigate the evolution of temperature stratification due to wall heat transfer [127] and fuel injection [128] in a motored spark ignition engine. Unfortunately toluene is strongly quenched by oxygen. Using 266 nm excitation, at room temperature in air the emission intensity is reduced by a factor of 60 compared to an inert bath gas environment [129]. Therefore at high repetition rates where DPSS laser energies are very low (1 mJ/pulse), the method cannot be used for temperature measurements in air. The cited heated jet impingement and IC engine studies were run entirely with nitrogen.

Ketones e.g. acetone, 3-pentanone may be used instead. The quantum yield of acetone, for example, is 0.2% [122], but it is not significantly quenched by oxygen, the signal drop with temperature is less pronounced than for aromatics, and it has a high vapour pressure (300 mbar at room temperature) permitting high seeding concentrations. Acetone thermometry is necessarily more complicated because the fluorescence emission is not temperature-dependent but the absorption spectrum is. In this case, thermometry is performed with sequential excitation (in time, similar to two-line atomic fluorescence methods above) using two wavelengths (e.g. 248 nm and 308 nm) that exploit the temperature-dependence of the UV absorption spectrum of acetone or 3-pentanone [130–132] while imaging the fluorescence that follows each laser pulse [132,133]. Acetone and 3-pentanone thermometry has been used for simultaneous measurements of temperature and end gas distribution in optically-accessible engines [132,133]. Regarding the temperature range of organic tracer LIF, temperature calibration measurements up to 1000 K have been performed with acetone [130], but tracer decomposition and eventual consumption in flames around this temperature range are a natural limitation.

Turning our attention to thermometry of the liquid phase, a commonly applied planar LIF thermometry technique uses soluble dyes e.g. rhodamine or fluorescein. To remove any dependence of the signal not originating from temperature, for example laser fluctuations

or dye concentration, a common approach is to use a temperature insensitive reference dye and a temperature-sensitive dye in combination, and use two-colour detection of the red-shifted fluorescence emissions to determine the temperature by a ratio method [134]. The technique has been used to study convection [135,136] and a blast furnace water model [137] and may be applied simultaneously with PIV using additional tracer particles, even in 3D throughout a whole liquid volume using a rapid scanning technique [138]. This approach affords measurements across the limited temperature ranges encountered in liquid flows. For instantaneous measurements using pulsed lasers, to prevent errors stemming from the saturation of the fluorescence, care must be taken to choose a suitable dye combination [139]. Dye self-absorption, photodegradation and sensitivity to chemical environment are also necessary considerations [140].

Temperature-sensitive particles

Lastly we address a rather different temperature sensing strategy, where the sensor is not a species in the fluid phase but rather seeded to the flow in the form of encapsulated particles. Thermochromic liquid crystals (TLCs) are small particles in a typical size range 10–100 μm that reflect light with a colour that depends, among other parameters, on the TLC particle temperature. White light sources are used to illuminate the particles in such a way to achieve spatial (i.e. forming a “sheet”) and temporal (pulsing the light source) resolution, and images of the particles are recorded using a colour camera [141]. Well-established methods can achieve an extraordinary temperature precision of 0.01–0.1 K, however only over a range of a few K. The same particles can be used as a tracer to simultaneously obtain the velocity field [142]. The temporal resolution is restricted by the long response times of TLCs, which include the time required for heat transfer (conduction) from the surrounding fluid and within the particle, but also that of the colour change, which depends on the crystal itself [143]. Estimated response times vary: ~ 10 ms for 10 μm crystals is reported in Ref. [144], making their application in gas flows questionable. The spatial resolution in the out-of-plane dimension is limited to several mm by the white light illumination sources employed [142]. Additionally, the accuracy of (global or local) calibration strategies, the dependence of the reflection spectrum on particle size, and hysteresis or damage due to shear forces within the fluid flow need to be addressed to achieve the optimum precision and accuracy.

Temperature-sensitive particles can also be synthesised by incorporating a temperature-dependent luminophore (e.g. EuTTA dye) into ion-exchange particles. These have been used as a tracer for temperature and velocity measurements in liquids [145,146], by using planar UV excitation of the particles and measuring the temperature-dependent luminescence lifetime in 2D. Similar to TLCs, the relatively large diameter (10 μm) of these particles restricts the application to liquid flows.

Summary

This overview illustrates some of the remarkable developments in fluid temperature measurement techniques made in the last decades. In particular, advanced laser sources have led to new measurement capabilities. DPSS lasers have extended the use of PIV and also some LIF techniques from \sim Hz to kHz repetition rates. Burst-mode lasers may broaden the application of existing techniques still further by virtue of their pulse energy being comparable with low repetition rate lasers. Also, the research using fs/ps laser sources for CARS spectroscopy has led to fascinating developments, improving the temperature measurement accuracy and precision, and likewise the sampling rate [95]. While no attention was given here to absorption-based techniques, their capabilities have tremendously improved, as described in recent PECS reviews [147,148].

There are, however, some circumstances where current diagnostic capabilities may be advanced. The presence of tracer particles for

velocimetry complicates the use of Rayleigh/Raman scattering for simultaneous temperature measurements. Instead, if the signal containing the temperature information is easily separated from the particle Mie scattering (as is the case for the shifted emission of most LIF tracers or the coherent signal beam of the CARS thermometer), simultaneous application of PIV or LDV is in principle a possibility. On the other hand, from a practical viewpoint a significant disadvantage is experimental complexity. LIF tracers tend to have optical properties, e.g. specific/narrow absorption bands, ultraviolet fluorescence emission, and cross sensitivity to the bath gas environment, that complicates excitation and detection thereby needing high laser pulse energies, specific wavelengths or well-controlled laser spectral profiles, and often multiple laser systems and intensified detectors. Likewise, advanced CARS techniques require specialised laser sources. Therefore in some measurement situations, it is evident that the versatility of temperature measurement techniques based on thermographic phosphor particles is advantageous.

1.5. Directions through the paper

For several reasons a review article is timely. First, from the foregoing it is evident that there are many different approaches to the execution of the basic concept, therefore Section 3 is devoted to the method: how has phosphor thermometry been used for flow measurements, what instrumentation, image processing and calibration methods were implemented, and what are the sources of error (Section 5). The aim is to identify common advantages and drawbacks, and should serve as a useful guide for researchers using the diagnostics. Second, we point out that only a tiny fraction of the vast range of phosphors have been used for flow thermometry. Therefore an introduction to thermographic phosphors is provided in the next Section 2, with particular attention to classes of phosphor material (semiconductors, and divalent rare-earth-doped oxides), which were given less attention in previous phosphor thermometry reviews but are very suitable for fluid measurements. Section 4 considers which phosphors are best-suited to temperature measurements in flows, as well as how phosphor particles were characterised and the results of these studies. Third, it is useful to summarise the applications of the method, contained in Section 6. Section 7 also points out the various challenges which the authors consider are key to the future development of the technique.

2. Thermographic phosphors

Inorganic phosphors consist of crystalline compounds which are in most cases doped with specific ions, usually lanthanides (rare-earths) or transition metals. These substitute a small fraction of the atoms making up the (now “host”) crystal, which act as luminescent centres to form a single activated material e.g. $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Cr}^{3+}$, normally known as the gemstone ruby. However, this is not always the case. Zinc oxide ZnO or calcium tungstate CaWO_4 are examples of undoped luminescent materials, i.e. just the semiconductor or insulator compounds themselves. While there is a near-endless variety of inorganic phosphors, they generally share some common features. Their density generally ranges from 3 to 6 g/cm^3 , and their volumetric heat capacity from 2 to 3.5 $\text{J}/\text{cm}^3\text{K}$ which are large with respect to gases so that only small particles (μm -size) are capable of following the fluid motion and fluid temperature accurately. These aspects are discussed in Section 5.2. The presence of a small fraction of dopant ions, which normally replaces a few percent of the population of one of the constituting atoms of the crystal, generally has little effect on mechanical and thermal properties. Klein and Croft measured the density, thermal conductivity, diffusivity and expansion of Y_2O_3 , $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG) and La_3F_3 , for undoped crystals and crystals with 1% mole Nd^{3+} doping [149]. Heat capacity and density were largely unchanged, but a large difference in the thermal conductivity was

observed for Y_2O_3 . The melting point of most phosphors is above 2000 K (e.g. Y_2O_3 : 2698 K, $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$: 2238 K), which in principle makes them useful for the study of combustion systems. Phosphor particles are often relatively inert, i.e. broadly speaking they do not chemically react with other materials including fluids they are immersed in, at least over short time scales (ms-s). However, transformation of the material in some environments over long time scale (min-hours) may occur, as discussed in Section 4.4.3.

To summarise, given these properties, one can see why these materials have attracted such interest as remote temperature sensors. However, though the thermal and mechanical properties are generally similar, their luminescence properties are extremely variable and offer a very wide range of possibilities as sensor materials. In the following section, a brief overview of the various mechanisms involved in the light emission process is provided, focusing on how the luminescence can be used for temperature measurements in fluids.

2.1. Luminescence of thermographic phosphors

The luminescence processes of phosphors are complex and involve a variety of mechanisms. Dorenbos offers a useful overview of the electronic transitions found in phosphors by means of the diagram of Fig. 3 [9]. Phosphor crystals have a wide (3–10 eV) forbidden gap between the valence and conduction band. This electronic band structure is modified by the addition of dopant ions or impurities, leading to new or changed energy levels. Electronic transitions which result in the absorption and emission of light variously take place between the band states of the host compound and/or energy levels within the gap.

For general conceptual understanding, consider a phosphor particle that contains many luminescent centres. A very short laser pulse, for example, provides excitation light that, upon absorption, drives many luminescent centres to an upper excited state. The system then returns to the stable ground state, either by emission of luminescence, or non-radiative relaxation. The depopulation of the excited state $N_1(t)$ can be described by:

$$\frac{dN_1}{dt} = -(W_R + W_{NR})N_1 \quad (1)$$

where W_R and W_{NR} are the respective radiative and non radiative transition rates. The electronic structure of the material determines the rates (transition probability) of these de-excitation processes. Following the short laser pulse excitation, the time it takes for the luminescence intensity to decay to 36.8% (1/e) of its initial value is $\tau = 1/(W_R + W_{NR})$, the aforementioned luminescence lifetime.

Fig. 3. Different types of electronic transitions in phosphors. Reproduced from Ref. [9] with permission of the Royal Society of Chemistry.

The first category of transitions are between the valence and conduction band states, called interband transitions (A as shown in Fig. 3). An electron is promoted to the conduction band by the absorption of excitation light, the attraction between the electron in the conduction band and the hole in the valence band leads to an exciton state slightly below the bandgap. Transitions back to the valence band lead to the recombination “edge” luminescence of semiconductors, an example being the 387 nm emission band of ZnO at room temperature, shown in Fig. 4. Such transitions are often very fast, with luminescence lifetimes below a nanosecond. Historically, the phosphor thermometry community has made little use of the temperature sensitivity of interband transitions. The same basic mechanism may still be responsible for the luminescence of the primary “host” compound in other cases, to use the same example, for ZnO:Zn and ZnO:Ga. Additional to the edge luminescence, local crystal imperfections or impurity elements may locally modify the band structure and lead to other interesting properties, e.g. the yellow luminescence in gallium nitride GaN, or the green emission of ZnO [150].

By comparison, optical transitions between energy levels belonging to lanthanide or transition metal ions that are deliberately doped into the host compound have so far found far more use for thermometry, and it is probably fair to state these materials are the most

Fig. 4. Room-temperature excitation and emission spectra of the phosphors YAG:Dy³⁺, YVO₄:Dy³⁺, YAG:Pr³⁺, BAM:Eu²⁺, and ZnO. The excitation spectrum is recorded at the peak of the emission spectrum. Note that the resolution of the spectra recorded for YVO₄:Dy³⁺ was insufficient to resolve the fine spectral features. Data courtesy of Phosphor Technology, UK (YAG:Dy³⁺, YVO₄:Dy³⁺, YAG:Pr³⁺, BAM:Eu²⁺) and from the authors (ZnO).

common conception of what a thermographic phosphor is. Transitions take place between electronic states of the dopant ion inside the bandgap, as designated in Fig. 3 by intra-lanthanide transitions, B. Examples are transitions between 4f subshells and between the 4f and the 5d shells in rare-earth-ion doped compounds, as well as between d shells in transition metal doped compounds. A common feature of these transitions is that they take place between unfilled inner shells which receive some degree of electronic shielding from outer shells. For this reason, the electronic structure of the free ion plays an predominant role in the positioning of the energy levels and therefore the luminescence emission.

This is particularly true for transitions within the 4f shells in lanthanide activated compounds. The relative position of the electronic energy levels in any host are very similar to that of the free ion, and the emission lines are sharp, as shown in the emission spectrum of YAG:Dy³⁺ and that of YAG:Pr³⁺ above 450 nm in Fig. 4. The energy levels of the 4f shell for trivalent lanthanides have been measured and are summarised in a so-called Dieke diagram [151]. It is important to note that these electronic transitions are usually forbidden on the basis of quantum-mechanical selection rules, in this case parity forbidden, and often also spin-forbidden. The main effect is that the luminescence decay time is usually of the order 100's μ s to ms at room temperature. While the host hardly alters the shape and position of the emission lines, it has a strong influence on the excitation spectrum, see for example the difference in the excitation spectra of YAG:Dy³⁺ and YVO₄:Dy³⁺ on Fig. 4. Likewise the host also has a strong effect on quenching processes, that is, non-radiative transitions between excited and ground states, and energy transfer to the host or between dopant ions (see below).

Transitions between the 4f and 5d shells of lanthanides are parity-allowed, featuring broad emission bands and short lifetimes. Examples are 5d–4f transitions observed in BAM:Eu²⁺, with a lifetime at room temperature of 1 μ s, or in YAG:Pr³⁺ with a lifetime of 10's ns. Such broad bands can be seen on Fig. 4; the band centered at 445 nm in BAM:Eu²⁺ and that around 325 nm in YAG:Pr³⁺. The host compound dictates the position of the emission band due to crystal field splitting of the degenerate 5d orbitals. For example, the position of the emission peak of divalent europium in different hosts can range from the near UV to the red spectral region [152].

Transitions between the d shells of transition metals show a variety of cases. Due to the degeneracy in the dⁿ orbitals, the relative position of the energy levels are dictated by the strength of the host crystal field as described in so-called Tanabe–Sugano diagrams (see Ref. [153] for the diagram and further detail). Those transitions are parity forbidden, but depending on the charge of the ion, its electronic configuration (d¹, d³ or d⁵), and on the host, transitions from the lower excited states to the ground state are either spin-allowed or spin-forbidden. Also for some ions such as Mn²⁺, the emission wavelength is influenced by the host compound, but this is not the case for Mn⁴⁺. Spin-forbidden d³ transitions such as ²E → ⁴A₂ in Al₂O₃:Cr³⁺ or in Mn⁴⁺ activated compounds result in a sharp emission lines with long lifetimes (several ms). On the other hand, spin allowed transitions such as ⁴T₂ → ⁴A₂ in Mg₄Nb₂O₉:Cr³⁺ result in broadband emission with a decay time of around 100 μ s.

Charge-transfer transitions involve the transfer of an electron between the dopant ion and the host crystal (C, Fig. 3). Such transitions have a high oscillator strength, and can therefore be an efficient excitation pathway for 4f–4f transitions e.g. in Y₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ but this is dependent on the host-dopant combination.

Finally, an electron can also be transferred between two lanthanides, see inter-lanthanide D in Fig. 3. Er³⁺, Yb³⁺-doped upconversion phosphors are a good example. Absorption takes place in the infrared directly in the ytterbium states and the energy is then transferred to the erbium ion, whose transitions leads to green and red emission lines. When co-doping facilitates the excitation process, the absorbing ion is called a sensitiser.

From the foregoing we remark that 1) in phosphors the optical transitions take place within the crystal structure of a solid particle and so in principle these transitions should be unaffected by the surrounding environment; 2) phosphors have a rich variety of different and often broad spectroscopic features. The consequence is they can be excited using a correspondingly wide range of light sources, and, since many phosphors were developed and characterised for display or lighting purposes, the luminescence is often in visible spectral regions and can therefore be easily detected, without the need for image intensifiers or IR sensitive cameras. If the luminescence properties of these transitions (lifetime, spectral position) are affected by temperature, then the observation of the luminescence emission following excitation can in theory allow remote thermometry as follows.

Influence of temperature on the emission lifetime

With increasing temperature, higher energy vibrational modes in the crystal lattice are populated, promoting non-radiative de-excitation pathways. The increase in the rate of non-radiative transitions results in a faster depopulation of the excited state and therefore a shorter luminescence lifetime. There are a variety of non-radiative de-excitation processes (crossover relaxation, multi-phonon emission, intersystem crossing, photoionisation to the conduction band), which are also strongly dependent on the host-dopant combination. While an in-depth discussion is beyond the scope of this article, the understanding and predictions of those processes is an active area of research [154]. Nevertheless, owing to the almost infinite variety of host-dopant combinations, for phosphors that have been so far studied the drop of the luminescence lifetime with temperature occurs over almost any temperature range from 40 to 1700 K, and with various degrees of sensitivity. Graphs gathering the lifetime versus temperature characteristic of many phosphors can be found in review articles such as Refs. [10–12], one of which is reproduced in Fig. 22 in Section 4 of this article.

Influence of temperature on the emission spectrum

Two broad categories of changes in the emission spectrum with temperature may be identified.

The first is a change in the bandshape of luminescence emission spectra involving several distinct electronic transitions, i.e. one emission line grows relative to another. A well-known example is YAG:Dy³⁺, where the light emission originates from transitions from two closely spaced levels ⁴F_{15/2} and ⁴F_{9/2} separated by 1000 cm⁻¹ and located above a large gap of 7500 cm⁻¹, as shown in Fig. 5. With

Fig. 5. Schematic energy level diagram for free ions Dy and Sm. Reproduced from [155] with permission of the Institute of Physics.

an increase in temperature, emission from the higher level $4I_{15/2}$ increases with respect to the lower one $4F_{9/2}$, so that a Boltzmann distribution of electrons between these two emitting states is proposed as an explanation for this behaviour. Feist and Heyes fitted the ratio of measured emission intensities of the two lines to a Boltzmann distribution and extracted an energy difference of 1100 cm^{-1} , a value only 10% higher than that reported for the free ion [155]. They also pointed out that Sm^{3+} shows a similar arrangement of energy levels also shown in Fig. 5, which is also reflected by a temperature induced bandshape change of the emission spectrum as observed in $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Sm}^{3+}$. However, in this case, there is little agreement with the Boltzmann distribution, presumably due to the presence of low lying charge transfer states in the Y_2O_3 host, allowing a non-radiative transfer between the two levels.

Changes in the emission bandshape are also found for Pr^{3+} doped in YAG and $\text{Y}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_9$ (YAM) hosts. In Pr^{3+} , the $3P_0$ state is located 4000 cm^{-1} above the $1D_2$ state, itself 7000 cm^{-1} above the $3H_4$ ground states, as shown in Fig. 6. Jordan and Rothamer noticed that in the YAG host, the ratio of the $1D_2 \rightarrow 3H_4$ to $3P_0 \rightarrow 3H_4$ transitions increases from room temperature to 1100 K, followed by a decrease in the 1100 to 1400 K range [46], which clearly disagrees with a Boltzmann distribution. The emission spectrum of YAG: Pr^{3+} at room temperature is displayed on Fig. 4. Kaczkan et al. later proposed a mechanism based on two competing cross-relaxation processes between neighboring Pr^{3+} ions [156], which is likely to be responsible for such non-monotonic behaviour. A less pronounced bandshape behaviour has also been observed in $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$, corresponding to transitions to different ground states [157], but, to our knowledge, no mechanism is proposed for such behaviour.

The second type of spectral change is a shift and/or broadening of the emission band, and is observed in 5d-4f transitions, as well as for interband transitions, both consisting of a single broad emission band (see the emission spectra of BAM: Eu^{2+} and ZnO on Fig. 4). For 5d-4f transitions, with increasing temperature higher vibrational levels of the excited state are populated, leading to a broadening of the emission band via electron-phonon interaction [158], as shown in Fig. 7 for BAM: Eu^{2+} . In such transitions, the position of the lower 5d state depends strongly on the crystal field, so that anisotropic thermal expansion can have a complex effect on the position of the emission peak, which may be responsible for the subtle blue-shift observed in BAM: Eu^{2+} with increasing temperature. With increasing temperature, the bandgap of semiconductors tends to decrease, with contributions from electron-phonon coupling and lattice expansion [159]. As a result, the near-edge luminescence band shifts toward longer wavelengths as observed in ZnO [14], see Fig. 9.

Fig. 6. Schematic energy level diagram showing YAG: Pr^{3+} energy levels. Reproduced from [46] with permission from Springer.

Fig. 7. Emission spectrum of BAM: Eu^{2+} reproduced from Ref. [13].

In some cases, quantum mechanical explanations provide a qualitative understanding of the observed behaviour. However, the complexity of the processes involved is such that a quantitative prediction is generally not possible. As a result, the luminescence properties of the material must be tested and if deemed suitable for thermometry, a calibration of their response is necessary to convert the measured quantity (lifetime or intensity ratio) to temperature.

2.2. Desirable luminescence properties for flow temperature measurements

Among the almost infinite range of phosphor materials, it is important to define the luminescence properties which allow precise and accurate measurements of fluid temperature.

- Efficient excitation. Excitation via transitions with a high transition probability is necessary to allow sufficient laser light to be absorbed by the particles. For example, for the phosphor YAG: Dy^{3+} , 355 nm excitation has a rather poor overlap with a spin allowed parity forbidden 4f-4f transition. For the same dopant in a YVO_4 host, an efficient excitation pathway via a host charge transfer transition is possible at the same laser wavelength, which leads to much higher signal levels.
- Quantum efficiency. A high conversion efficiency of the absorbed light to the emission line probed is desired. The quantum efficiency of phosphor used in fluorescent lamps, e.g. BAM: Eu^{2+} or $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$ tend to lie in the range 50–100 % [158]. In YAG: Pr^{3+} , when probing the abovementioned 4f-4f transitions, a large fraction of the absorbed light is lost to a 5d-4f transition centered around 325 nm, as can be observed on the emission spectrum of YAG: Pr^{3+} shown on Fig 4.
- Fast rate of radiative transition. For measurements in turbulent gas flows, the measurement duration must be limited to a few microseconds, to prevent any displacement of the particles during the measurement caused by the fluid motion which would result in spatial averaging. The use of phosphors with fast transitions (e.g. BAM: Eu^{2+} , 1 μs or ZnO, < 1 ns) ensure that the entire luminescence emission resulting from the excitation by a single laser pulse is integrated in time. Probing spin and parity forbidden 4f-4f transitions at these time scales would mean collecting only a few percent of the total luminescence intensity.
- High sensitivity to temperature, that is, a pronounced change of the emission spectrum or lifetime with temperature.
- Absence of cross sensitivity of the emission spectrum or lifetime on parameters such as the excitation fluence, gas composition

or pressure, to minimise uncertainty linked to variations in those parameters.

This method probes a dilute dispersion of particles. For a given particle number density (i.e. seeding density) the three processes of excitation, energy transfer between different states/ions and emission dictate the light level. Depending on the luminescence mechanism, each of these three processes can affect the signal by several orders of magnitude, and so the light level emitted by single particles will vary enormously from one phosphor material to another. Measuring the luminescence signal of phosphor particles is therefore essential to establish the feasibility of using a given phosphor for precise temperature measurements. This is discussed in Section 4.4.1.

Some other properties are also favourable in some environment or measurement situations:

- Long-wavelength excitation. While most phosphors can be excited by UV radiation e.g. a frequency quadrupled Nd:YAG laser at 266 nm, the use of such short wavelengths has disadvantages. It can lead to the luminescence of metal or glass surfaces, or to the luminescence and/or photo-dissociation of species present in fuels. In addition, for measurements at kHz-repetition rates, the thermal loading of frequency mixing crystals in diode pumped solid state lasers or pulse burst systems significantly reduces their lifetime. When possible, excitation nearer the visible spectrum is preferred, for example the third harmonic of a Nd:YAG laser (355 nm). A few phosphors have excitation pathways in the visible (e.g. Cr^{3+} in high crystal field hosts) or infrared range (upconversion phosphors, e.g. host co-doped with Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+}) of the optical spectrum, which offer interesting perspectives in media with high UV absorption, or to avoid fluorescence from the fuel and solid surfaces.
- Decay time in the μs range. In some cases, temporal separation from fast fluorescence from e.g. fuel species is desired, which can be achieved by gating the camera exposure 10's of ns after a short (10 ns) laser pulse when using a phosphor with a decay time on the μs scale.
- Emission in the blue spectral region. In some combustion applications, an emission spectrum in the blue region is preferred to minimise interference from blackbody radiation of soot particle or surfaces. The blue region also allows efficient detection by non-intensified cameras in comparison with emission peak in the 300–400 nm range.

2.3. Phosphor synthesis and sourcing of tracer particles

While a huge range of phosphors have been synthesised, nearly all of them were produced for the previously-mentioned applications, especially lighting and displays. Therefore the vast majority of phosphors are optimised for these purposes, where the temperature dependence of the luminescence emission is usually seen as detrimental to performance. However, studies frequently appear in the literature which report synthesis of phosphors which show a potentially useful temperature response. These normally focus only on the temperature sensitivity and rarely on realistic experimental considerations, or the overall signal level and its temperature dependence. Rather more useful are research efforts to synthesise phosphors specifically for surface temperature measurements [160–163], because they also place emphasis on practical excitation sources, measurement duration, sensitivity to interfering signals etc. Also, in the case of flow measurements, the particle size, shape and state of agglomeration impose more stringent requirements. These latter parameters are primarily a function of how a phosphor powder is manufactured.

High temperature solid-state reactions are used to produce the majority of rare-earth/transition metal doped phosphors. The prepared material precursors including host compound, dopant, and sensitizer elements, plus flux(es) to try and obtain product powders with the desired particle diameter, morphology and crystallinity are thoroughly blended/mixed (see Ref. [158], the “Phosphor Handbook”, a text of reference in the phosphor community). These are then fired in a furnace, often in a controlled atmosphere e.g. oxidising, inert, or reducing depending on the necessary reactions (Ref. [164], the book “Inorganic Phosphors”, contains instructions of how to make thousands of phosphors). Diffusion, crystal formation and particle growth take place. Additional firing may be used to control oxidation state and host compound phase. The product particles usually emerge in the form of a sintered cake. Controlling the particle size and morphology is difficult and it depends on the quantities and particle sizes of the raw materials, the fluxes used, and firing conditions, and then washing, grinding/milling, sieving steps to obtain the final powder (see phosphor synthesis process diagram in Ref. [158] p343). Solid-state methods are employed in the manufacture of lamp, display, CRT and scintillator phosphors. Depending on the relative expense of the phosphor to be made and the nature of the luminescence excitation, particles between 1 and 10 μm are produced for maximum efficiency. The powders generally have a broad size distribution and varying shape and state of agglomeration (see Fig. 8 for images of BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO particles). Using sieving or

Fig. 8. Scanning electron microscope images of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles (top, from Ref. [13]) and ZnO particles (bottom, from Ref. [14]) (with permission of the Optical Society of America).

sedimentation to separate powders is expensive and inefficient for particles in the μm size range. Hard milling to reduce the primary particle size may damage the phosphor, reducing the efficiency [158,164], so it is recommended to produce particles with a size distribution centered at a suitable size in the first place.

Other condensed-phase methods to prepare phosphor particles include wet chemical techniques and combustion synthesis. There are techniques to prepare films for surface temperature measurements that do not rely on mixing prepared powders with a binder, such as the sol-gel method, and physical and chemical vapour deposition techniques [12]. Also relevant are methods including pure gas-phase synthesis, for example to manufacture zinc oxide, where a flow of vapourised zinc reacts with oxygen to form ZnO particles (see Fig. 8), as well as techniques often employed to make nanoparticles, e.g. laser-heated evaporation, flame synthesis, flame (-assisted) spray pyrolysis. In terms of producing seeding material, these methods may offer flexibility in terms of particle size distribution, morphology, crystallinity and production scale-up.

At this stage nearly all phosphor particles used for gas thermometry were synthesised via solid state reactions. These are generally obtained from lighting companies (Philips, Osram) or specialists like Phosphor Technology in the UK. It can be seen that it is not always possible to obtain particles with a size and shape tailored for flow tracing. It would be great value to systematically and independently vary critical parameters such as the dopant, dopant concentration, host etc., and also the particle size, to optimise the materials for the application, for example, high irradiance pulsed excitation and maximum absorption. Though there have been some insightful studies aimed at systematic characterisation [41,165,166], most phosphors have not yet been characterised in the context of thermometry. Comparing different phosphors is not trivial, particularly in terms of absolute signal levels, because the absorption/scattering characteristics can lead the results to depend on the state of agglomeration of the particles. Characterising phosphor particles is the subject of Section 4.

A frequently asked question is ‘what health and safety precautions must one take when seeding phosphor particles into flows?’. The answer is that, while it is true that many phosphors are considered chemically stable and non-toxic, since they are nm- to μm -scale particles dispersed as a dilute aerosol they pose a risk of inhalation, with potential and unknown health implications. Specific phosphors also possess more significant or particular hazards, for example zinc oxide is harmful to aquatic life in high concentrations and should be discarded using appropriate waste disposal channels; CdWO_4 used in Ref. [167] for surface measurements is considered carcinogenic by European Council regulations, and should be used with great caution if the material is stably adhered to a test surface, and likely not at all in flows but for the smallest-scale, fixed-volume fluid measurements. Wearing a respirator with appropriate particle filters and gloves whilst directly handling phosphor powder, adequate general ventilation, extraction system for gas flows with appropriate outside exhaust and particle filters, proper procedures for storage, disposal and spillage (HEPA filtered vacuum cleaner, for example) are all routinely employed in our lab.

3. Methods and instrumentation

This section describes how the temperature dependence of the luminescence properties of thermographic phosphors is utilised in experiments to derive the fluid temperature. The first part compares the temporal and spectral methods for flow measurements. This is followed by a description of the instrumentation used in terms of light sources, detectors and optics, their implementation, and finally the various post-processing steps. Some of the sections apply only to certain fluid thermometry approaches. This section serves as a point

of reference for those wishing to use phosphor particles in flows, and need not necessarily be read in order.

3.1. Principles of phosphor thermometry

As discussed, the two useful temperature response of thermographic phosphors are the luminescence decay time and emission spectrum. The raw luminescence intensity is also temperature dependent, but to use this for thermometry would require, as in the single-wavelength detection tracer LIF approach, a uniform distribution of the tracer in the fluid. This condition is particularly difficult to meet, especially when seeding particles into gas flows.

3.1.1. Spectral method

For the spectral method, the temperature dependence of the emission spectrum is exploited using interference filters, as shown in Fig. 9. In the simplest form, the luminescence emission following excitation is simultaneously acquired using two detectors, each having a specific spectral response defined by the optics/detectors. The filters are chosen so that the *intensity ratio* of the two signals is a function of temperature, which is in theory independent of the excitation light intensity and seeding density. For imaging, a thin excitation light sheet is formed and the luminescence emission of the particle field is imaged on two separate sensor arrays. With this approach, a single exposure is sufficient to derive the temperature field. The key aspect of this method is that the integration time can be made as short as the detector permits, bearing in mind that if the luminescence lifetime is long, a short exposure will (drastically in some cases) reduce signal levels. This is by far the most widely-used configuration for phosphor thermometry in fluids.

For ratio-based measurements at a point (or line), the ratio of two regions of the spectrum recorded with a spectrometer can be used, e.g. [26]. Another point measurement approach was developed (“thermographic LDV”), where individual phosphor particles traverse a focused continuous wave laser beam. The luminescence is collected and then spectrally separated and directed towards two photomultiplier tubes, producing luminescence burst signals which can be divided on a per particle basis [21].

3.1.2. Temporal method

The temporal method consists of temporally resolving the decay of the luminescence intensity following the excitation laser pulse. This method has been employed for point measurements using PMTs and two-dimensional measurements on surfaces using high speed CMOS cameras. By reducing the region of interest on the camera chip, frame rates approaching 1 MHz can be achieved. As an example, the Photron SA1.1 camera used in [169] allows a frame

Fig. 9. Emission spectrum of ZnO particles using 355 nm excitation [14]. Two filter bands are superimposed on the spectrum; the intensity ratio of the red divided by blue channels increases with temperature. Reproduced from Ref. [14] with permission from the Optical Society of America. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Temperature / decay time characteristics for $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6\text{:Mn}^{4+}$. Reproduced from Ref [168] with permission from Elsevier.

rate of 675,000 fps for a region of 64×16 pixels. If the luminescence lifetime over the temperature range of interest varies in the range $50 \mu\text{s}$ – 3 ms (e.g. $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6\text{:Mn}^{4+}$ in the range 300–900 K as shown on Fig. 10), then operating the camera this way permits the resolution of each luminescence decay with at least 100 datapoints over the full range of lifetimes, allowing a 2D determination of the lifetime with a reduced spatial resolution but a high precision. In the thermal quenching range where the lifetime rapidly drops with temperature, e.g. 700–800 K for $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6\text{:Mn}^{4+}$, this approach permits measurements with a precision as good as 1 K, [170]. The point is that the lifetime is a very sensitive function of temperature, and this technique takes advantage of that by covering a wide range of lifetime. However the integration time ($\sim 1 \text{ ms}$) is too long for measurements in turbulent fluids.

Someya et al. explored a 2D lifetime imaging concept for gas-phase measurements using a pulsed laser and four consecutive exposures of a high speed CMOS camera as described in Fig. 11. This approach was applied for temperature and velocity measurements in a motored internal combustion engine over the range 620 to 820 K [52]. After each laser excitation pulse, 4 images of the luminescence signal of $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6\text{:Mn}^{4+}$ particles seeded into the flow were recorded within $100 \mu\text{s}$ starting $5 \mu\text{s}$ after the laser pulse. The displacement of the particles between the 4 images was used to determine the velocity field using PIV. During motored operation of the engine, at top dead centre (TDC), the measured in-cylinder gas temperature is about 820 K, at which the luminescence lifetime of the phosphor is $50 \mu\text{s}$ (see Fig. 10). Under these conditions, four frames are evenly distributed over the $1/e^2$ decay waveform, allowing a very precise evaluation of the lifetime. A single-shot pixel-to-pixel

Fig. 11. Concept for combined temperature and velocity measurements proposed by Someya et al. [52]. Reproduced from Ref. [52] with permission from the Optical Society of America.

standard deviation better than 5 K is reported. At 30 crank angle degrees (CAD) before top dead center (BTDC), the gas temperature is 600 K and the luminescence decay time is 1.7 ms, which means only a small fraction ($\sim 6\%$) of the decay is covered by the four exposures. As a result, the difference in recorded intensities is less than 5% so that the lifetime evaluation is very sensitive to random errors in the intensity of each exposure. While allowing highly precise measurements, this 4-frame concept is inherently limited to a narrow range of lifetimes, and hence temperatures.

The concept also relies on the fact that the displacement during the $100 \mu\text{s}$ measurement is sufficient for particle image velocimetry but small enough for the temperature change to be negligible. This assumption is acceptable in this slow-moving in-cylinder engine flow with velocities in the range 0–0.7 m/s [52], and also in some liquid flows where for example a similar approach was used by Kim et al. [171]. However significant errors may arise in faster flows. At higher flow velocities, in addition to averaging errors, adopting an Eulerian approach means that the decay time is evaluated from different particles which may have different luminescence intensities or which have been exposed to different excitation fluences. A Lagrangian “tracking” approach is preferred in such cases, where the luminescence intensity of each particles or group of particles is tracked in time following the laser pulse.

Operating at faster frame rates would allow shorter measurement times necessary for turbulent flows. In the single-camera approach described by Someya, this would further reduce the already limited resolution (512×256 pixels) used for the PIV evaluation. Then, the velocimetry should be performed with a separate camera and laser system, see Section 3.2.6.

It does not seem likely that the extraordinary sensitivity of the lifetime can be exploited over a wide temperature range (100's K) in turbulent flows. However, a phosphor with lifetime varying in the range 1 – $10 \mu\text{s}$ over a smaller temperature range of interest would open interesting perspectives for precise thermometry in a wider range of applications. For example an ultrafast framing camera running at 100 MHz was used with the $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S:Eu}^{3+}$ phosphor (the lifetime of the $^5\text{D}_2$ line used is $12 \mu\text{s}$ at room temperature) to image the temperature in falling droplets and sprays [28]. These measurements are discussed in Section 6.1. A precision as high as 0.6 K could be obtained over the temperature range 290–340 K. Even in this case, in the spray, it was reported that the particles moved during acquisition leading to measurement errors. For slower flows, high-speed CCD cameras (frame rates around 1 MHz) or even a simple dual-frame temporal ratio approach using an interline-transfer CCD camera are possibilities. The latter method was tested using the YAG:Dy^{3+} phosphor and a dual-frame intensified CCD in a calibration furnace and in pre-mixed flames, albeit using two very long exposures (0.5 ms) [36].

For point measurements the luminescence decay waveform of particles in the fluid phase can be temporally resolved with a much faster data rate by PMTs as in e.g. heated jets [31,39] and water droplets [26,27]. In those studies, a pulsed laser was used, which means that point measurements are obtained at low sampling rate (10 Hz). As mentioned above, with this Eulerian approach, particles entering the probe volume during the decay time have not been excited, and the luminescence from particles leaving the volume is no longer collected. For phosphors with a long lifetime, the decay waveform can be significantly distorted by this effect. A recent study has demonstrated a point-based method for gas phase temperature and velocity measurements using excitation with the time-modulated output of a cw laser. The temperature was inferred from the temperature dependent phase shift between the luminescence and scattering waveforms from single BAM:Eu^{2+} phosphor particles crossing the probe volume [22], which is a function of the lifetime and the modulation frequency. With this approach, the sampling rate is dictated by the rate of particles crossing the probe volume, and can be as high as several kHz. Using a modulation frequency of 1 MHz, the

Fig. 12. Simultaneous Doppler burst (514.5 nm) (a), Mie scattered UV excitation (375 nm) and luminescence emission waveforms (447 nm) (b) for a single BAM:Eu²⁺ particle crossing the probe volume formed by the overlapped UV and green laser beams at a temperature of 840 K and a velocity of 6.2 m/s. The continuous wave output of the UV laser was modulated at 1 MHz by a half-sine wave modulation. A detailed view of (b) is shown on (c). Reproduced from Ref. [22] with permission from the Optical Society of America. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

phase shift of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles was probed in the range 600 K – 850 K where the lifetime changes from 1 μs to 50 ns [42]. For this range of lifetime, the particle displacement is not a problem. An example of simultaneous Doppler, Mie-scattered excitation and luminescence emission bursts recorded as a single particle crosses the probe volume at a temperature of 840 K is shown on Fig. 12. Here the frequency of the Doppler burst is function of the velocity, while the frequency of the excitation and emission burst is the UV laser modulation frequency, here 1 MHz. The phase shift between excitation and emission is measured to derive the temperature. A measurement precision of about 1% could be obtained at 835 K. An important feature of this approach is that by adjusting the frequency of the modulation frequency, the sensitivity of the phase-shift can be tuned by virtue of the \tan^{-1} function [22], allowing very precise measurements in specific temperature ranges.

Since the decrease of the luminescence lifetime is the result of an increase in non-radiative transition rate, there is a compromise between the temperature sensitivity and the signal level. A phosphor with slow luminescence transitions which is far in its thermal quenching regime (e.g. TiMg₂O₄:Mn⁴⁺ at room temperature) would show a suitable range of lifetime (1–10 μs), but also an inherently low quantum efficiency, leading to poor signal levels in fluid flows.

In conclusion, the lifetime method is a potential option for high-precision thermometry over a narrow temperature range, but phosphors with an appropriate lifetime and signal levels over the temperature range of interest must be carefully chosen.

3.2. Instrumentation

3.2.1. Particle seeding

To be able to measure the fluid temperature using thermographic phosphor particles, the particles must be dispersed in the fluid i.e. into a tank of liquid, or into a gas flow upstream of the test section. As will be discussed in Section 4.4.1, for some phosphors it has been established that the range of seed concentration required for precise temperature measurements is 10^{10} – 10^{12} particles/m³, which translates to 0.02–2 g/m³ considering 1 μm spherical particles with a density of 4 g/cm³.

The dispersion of particles in liquid streams is in principle relatively straightforward. Early studies reported simply mixing the powder into the liquid [26–29] and also often continuous stirring of the dispersion. A small quantity of surfactant was reported to aid dispersion of La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ in water [28]. It should be noted that the mass load was usually stated to be around 1% by weight which is very high (10 g/L in water) compared to the value stated above (see Section 4.4). Our findings were that in water and using ZnO phosphor powder even vigorous stirring does not break up large agglomerates which remain visible on the bottom of the vessel [15]. Laser diffraction measurements showed that the particle size distribution in this case was bimodal, with some large agglomerates in

the range 10–100 μm. Therefore a procedure was developed to add particles to the liquid (~0.1% by weight) and disperse the particles using an ultrasonic homogeniser to generate a turbid mixture. This is diluted in subsequent steps to end up with mass loads in the range 1–5 mg/L, which is clear to the eye in an ordinary 1 L laboratory beaker. It was verified using laser diffraction measurements that following this method no large agglomerates remain [15]. Ultrasound actuators were also used to continuously disperse YAG:Dy³⁺ and YVO₄:Eu³⁺ in Jet-A/water mixtures [38,172].

As Self and Whitelaw wrote in 1976, “the dispersion of micron-size solid particles into gaseous flows can be achieved in various ways ... but it is not entirely straightforward to achieve a steady, controlled feed of deagglomerated particles” [173]. In fact, Geldart’s classification of powders indicates that phosphor particles in the 1–10 μm range belong to the group C of “cohesive powders” which cannot form a fluidised bed in a strict sense [174]. Instead group C powders tend to form channels, resulting in an unsteady rate of entrainment of the powder and the presence of many agglomerates. In this respect, only a basic and qualitative understanding of the dispersion and de-agglomeration processes combined with the observation of the “seeding quality” in terms of seeding level, uniformity and consistency over time form the grounds for guidelines. Few research articles provide a discussion on seeding tracer particles, the article of Melling being so far the most extensive [56], while Ref. [175] provides additional discussion on seeder design and particle deposition.

In terms of seeders, the apparatus designed for PIV/LDV seeding are directly applicable here, since the physical properties of phosphors and PIV/LDV seeding materials e.g. Al₂O₃, TiO₂ are very similar. The simplest seeder design consists of two plenums separated by a sintered plate on which the powder rests. This would allow the formation of a fluidised bed (as these seeders are usually referred to) when fluid flows upwards through it. The concentration in seeding particles is then controlled by the ratio between the stream that goes through the seeder, and the stream that bypasses it. While it is tempting to design one’s own fluidised bed seeder, from our experience, it proved extremely difficult to produce a steady stream of seeding. Some large fluidised bed seeders (e.g. PIVtech PIVsolid seeders) operate rather reliably, but are generally limited to flow rates above 50 L/min and seems to require large quantities of powder (> 2 kg). Another concept is based on a reverse cyclone separator as presented by Glass and Kennedy in [176] (Fig. 13) but no commercial systems are available. Due to the two counter-rotating vortices, large agglomerates which are entrained at first should be collected at the

Fig. 13. Schematic illustrating the functioning principle of a basic cyclone seeder. Reproduced from [56] with permission from the Institute of Physics.

bottom of the seeder (underflow), while smaller particles exit with the fluid through an aperture at the top of the vessel. With our in-house built reverse cyclone seeder, we observed a steady seeding density at flow rates above 200 L/min. For both seeder designs, lower carrier gas flow rates result in an insufficient concentration of seeding particles. Hybrid concepts based on both mechanical stirring using a rotating magnet and a swirling flow (e.g. LaVision particle blaster), have shown satisfactory results from 10 to 50 L/min. A range of powder dispersers for dust particles for applications in particle filter quality testing have been developed commercially (BEG 1000, Palas; 3400A, TSI; SAG 410, Topas GmbH), some of which have been specifically designed for cohesive ceramic powder. Systems based on a belt with grooves to transport the powder from the feeder to a fluid nozzle where it is entrained in the fluid may provide accurate particle feed rate and therefore concentration. To our knowledge, none of these systems are rated for a carrier gas flow rate below 5 L/min, and seeding lower flow rates remains very challenging.

As for other methods for seeding phosphor particles, Omrane et al. dispersed phosphor particles in alcohol, then sprayed the solution in the gaseous stream using a nebuliser, which was then directed to a heated tube causing the liquid to evaporate [39]. In this case the seeding density was reported to be too low, and highly inhomogeneous. Concerning other seeding devices, we note the use of a screw feed causing the powder to fall in a cross stream of carrier gas [46,47], a fluidised bed from which the gas is sucked toward the outlet of a venturi tube [37], and particles placed above a loud-speaker [36].

To reduce the presence of agglomerates entrained in the flow, several steps have been reported. First in terms of powder preparation, the application of a SiO₂ or Al₂O₃ nanoparticle coating (e.g. Ludox or Aerosil) reduces agglomeration. For BAM:Eu particles, this coating was shown to have no effect on the emission spectrum [177] but the study may not have been sufficiently sensitive (see Section 4.4.4). It has been confirmed that there is no effect of SiO₂ particle coating on the emission of YAG:Dy particles [43]. Experience shows that drying the particles in an oven at about 150 °C for several hours before use removes excess moisture which favours coagulation. Downstream of the seeding device, de-agglomeration or size selection can be achieved using a sonic (or subsonic) nozzle to break agglomerates through shear forces or particle impactors [46,47] which promote the deposition of large particles and offers some degree of particle size selection. We emphasise that seeders with some degree of swirl such as the cyclone seeder described above tend to reduce the occurrence of large particles in the aerosol.

3.2.2. Light sources

Since the luminescence must be collected within a short time period relative to the flow motion, a sufficient signal level requires high pumping rates and high luminescence emission rates, which are achieved with high power density pulsed lasers, and phosphors with a short lifetime. Pulsed lasers with pulse durations in the range of tens to hundreds of nanoseconds and pulse energies up to 1 J offer very high power densities which allow a fast pumping of the excited state. It was stated before that most phosphors have a broad excitation spectrum, which means it is generally not necessary to tune the laser emission wavelength, e.g. with a dye laser. With either frequency-tripled or frequency-quadrupled Nd:YAG lasers (355 and 266 nm respectively), it is possible to excite many phosphors, which is a significant advantage of these tracer materials. The pulse energies of commercially available Nd:YAG lasers typically reach 100's of mJ at low repetition rates (10 Hz). By adding a non-linear frequency conversion crystal, a common PIV laser can be converted to deliver either UV outputs. On the other hand upconversion phosphors require IR excitation which may be useful to reduce photolytic interferences and also for biomedical applications, to target the so-called biological windows, spectral bands where the scattering and

absorption of biological tissue is minimal. For gas thermometry, in Ref. [45] a frequency-doubled Nd:YAG OPO/OPA was used to excite the upconversion phosphor Y₂O₂S:Er³⁺,Yb³⁺ at 980 nm.

The amount of energy required depends on the tracer material used. Our studies of BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO showed that a pulse energy of only 1–2 mJ is sufficient for precise measurements over a region (field of view) of 5 × 5 cm by a sheet thickness of a few hundred μm, corresponding to a fluence around 10 mJ/cm², as discussed in Section 4.4.1. However a very wide range of fluences have been used in different studies, often 100's of mJ/cm² ([178]) and sometimes in excess of 1 J/cm² [49], presumably because some phosphors otherwise emit very little light.

For measurements at kHz repetition rates, diode pumped solid state lasers (DPSS) with a pulse energy of 1–5 mJ at 355 nm can be used [19,20]. Note that frequency tripling or quadrupling is not straightforward with these lasers. Often DPSS lasers have a pulse duration of >100 ns, and use intra-cavity frequency conversion. Slab lasers, e.g. those supplied by Edgewave GmbH, have a short (~ns) pulse duration and the wavelength is converted outside the cavity. In general, the 355 nm line is preferred if the phosphor allows it, since this reduces photolytic interferences, does not require fused silica optics, and is less prone to heat load and thermal lensing. This latter consideration is especially true at high repetition rates. The advantage that some phosphors (e.g. ZnO, BAM:Eu²⁺) require very little laser fluence is critical in the application of the measurement technique at high repetition rates. Phosphors demanding high fluences cannot be used with DPSS lasers because the energy output is 2–3 orders of magnitude lower than from 10 Hz lasers. In that case, pulse-burst systems [83,179] could be used instead but these are expensive and the total number of pulses per measurement sequence is limited. They may also lead to significant laser-induced heating of the particles due to the high energy delivered over a short duration. The influence of the excitation fluence on the luminescence properties of phosphor particles is discussed in Section 4.4.4.

Looking at other light sources, for the thermographic laser Doppler velocimetry concept, the Mie scattering and luminescence signals from individual particles passing through a probe volume are detected. The probe volume is formed by two crossing continuous wave green beams and a continuous wave UV beam at 375 nm [21]. A diode laser with a continuous output of 65 mW was used, which for a particle transiting at a velocity of 1 m/s through a beam of 150 μm diameter results in a fluence of several mJ/cm², i.e. not dissimilar to the range of fluence mentioned above.

LEDs have been used for phosphor thermometry on surfaces e.g. Refs. [180–182]. In fluids (silicon oil) a 3.2 W 385 nm UV LED was used to excite the phosphor Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ by Kim et al. [171], but the illumination had a duration of 50 ms and was volumetric. Thus the temporal resolution was very limited and the spatial resolution only afforded by studying a confined flow limited by a 2 mm channel. Besides the low peak power of a pulsed LED, creating a thin light sheet to attain spatial resolution in the depth direction for imaging is an issue, a problem also encountered using white light LED sources for TLC illumination. Forming a thin (<1 mm) light sheet (or point) is easily done with laser sources, even for DPSS lasers with an M² of ~30.

It has been determined that for some phosphors, for example ZnO, the intensity ratio between the emission intensities in the two spectral bands of interest is also a function of laser fluence [14]. Then, stability of the laser beam profile and pulse-to-pulse energy output may be important. In our experience the output of flash-lamp-pumped Nd:YAG lasers were suitably stable (within 2–4%) in this regard. These lasers have a near-Gaussian beam profile. Because of a possible fluence dependence, it is favourable to reduce the spatial variation in laser fluence. This can be done either with a beam homogeniser [183], for example as used for flow thermometry using BAM:Eu²⁺ particles in a wind tunnel [20], or just by expanding the

light sheet far more than the vertical height of the field of view, for example for imaging ZnO particles [14], and also reducing the beam waist variation along the direction of propagation by collimation.

Excitation spectra of many phosphors can be found in the literature (e.g. Ref. [158]) or provided by the manufacturer and serve as useful guides for the choice of laser wavelength. It should be noted however that such data are nearly always obtained using a continuous light source in the mW range. The power density of pulsed lasers easily reach the MW/cm² range and for these high irradiances, saturation of the luminescence transitions was observed in both BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO. Thus the low power density excitation spectra may not be particularly relevant. The investigation of alternative excitation schemes (different wavelength, longer pulse duration) is still ongoing, with some examples given in Section 4.4.4. There may be exciting prospects to increase the luminescence signal, most especially at high temperatures where thermal quenching is a problem.

3.2.3. Detectors

Photo-multiplier tubes (PMTs) can be used to resolve the luminescence decay for point lifetime measurements in flows e.g. [24,26,27,31,39]. In another approach, two filtered (see below) PMTs were used for ratio-based point measurements for the aforementioned LDV thermometer setup using BAM:Eu²⁺ [21].

For low-repetition rate imaging measurements, e.g. 1–10 Hz, the interline transfer charge coupled device cameras (CCD cameras) typically used for PIV are suitable for the detection of the luminescence signal from phosphor particles. Most phosphors emit in the visible range of the optical spectrum, where the quantum efficiency of typical non-intensified CCD cameras is high (~50%). This is a particularly favourable feature of thermographic phosphors. With regard to the measurement integration time, using the example of a PCO Sencam QE CCD camera (12 bit, thermoelectrically-cooled, 1376 × 1040 pixels), a camera also sold as LaVision Imager Intense, the minimum exposure time is 500 ns. For temperature imaging using the phosphors BAM:Eu²⁺ (lifetime 1 μs at room temperature) and ZnO (lifetime < 1 ns at room temperature), we use an exposure time of 5 μs and start the exposure before the laser pulse. This way the measured intensity ratio is unaffected by the jitter between the trigger pulse and start of exposure (for the PCO Sencam QE CCD cameras mentioned here, by experiment, the jitter was determined to be about 40 ns [44]).

An attractive feature of the CCD camera is that the pixels can be hardware binned, which consists of converting the charge of a larger “superpixel” instead of that of every individual pixel, therefore increasing the ratio of signal to readout noise. This is a very useful feature at low light levels. If the aim is correlated temperature and velocity measurements, in principle the spacing between independent measurements of each quantity (temperature/velocity) should be the same. PIV yields a vector spacing in the image plane on the order of the size of an interrogation area (e.g. 16 × 16), much larger than the single pixel resolution so one is nearly always able to afford 4 × 4 hardware binning on the luminescence detection camera, plus some additional smoothing.

In interline transfer cameras, the accumulated charges are shifted at the end of the exposure to the interline pixel rows, where they are stored while the long sequential readout process (typically in the range of 1–100 ms) takes place. However, illumination of the chip during the readout process can result in an additional accumulation of charge in the storage pixels, determined by the number of incident photons during the readout time and the extinction ratio (for example, 1:2000 for the PCO Sencam QE CCD camera). As a result, in the presence of a continuous light source, the effective exposure time can be an order of magnitude longer than the electronically-controlled exposure of the active pixels. In addition, this contribution is non-uniform even for uniform illumination, since the accumulated charge is proportional to the position of the pixels in the

readout sequence. In flows with any significant continuous background spectrally overlapping the luminescence emission, e.g. flame luminosity, this effect leads to an unacceptably high background, in which case intensified cameras must be used for their superior gating. Also, if a phosphor with a lifetime on the order of 1 μs is used, the very precise timing (ns) of intensifiers can also be used to discriminate against fast fluorescence signals from e.g. fuel molecules or walls.

When a very short exposure (ns) or delay with respect to the laser pulse are not needed, or there is no need to image signals below 350 nm (where the borosilicate windows and microlens arrays in ordinary CCD or CMOS cameras normally prevents their use), nonintensified cameras offer improved imaging characteristics, in term of dynamic range, linearity, signal to noise ratio, and spatial resolution. Indeed, Neal et al. reported an imaging resolution equivalent to 12 unbinned camera pixels and a non linearity worse than 6% below 2000 counts for a Pi-Max 3 (Princeton Instruments) with a P46 screen [47]. “Scientific” (sCMOS) cameras based on complementary metal-oxide semiconductor sensors could also be used, but they remain to be fully tested for quantitative imaging.

High-speed temperature imaging

For temperature imaging at high repetition rates, non-intensified high-speed CMOS cameras were used [19,20]. The latest high speed CMOS camera models are capable of frame rates as high as 20,000 frames per second at a resolution of 1 megapixel, e.g. Fastcam SA-Z, Photron or the Phantom v-series, Vision Research. Large on-board memories (up to 64 GB) allow more than 40,000 frames to be recorded at full resolution, which translates into approximately 4 orders of magnitude in terms of time scale. CMOS cameras have a very useful feature: the cameras are continuously capturing images, but the memory is constantly rewritten on a first frame in first frame out basis. By feeding a single trigger pulse to the camera, the re-writing process can be stopped, so that the thousands of frames recorded before the trigger pulse are saved, which can then be downloaded from the camera for evaluation. Coupled with continuously running DPSS lasers this functionality proves essential when one is concerned with investigating the cause of a rare phenomenon, e.g. flashback in a combustor, since the recording captures the evolution of the velocity and temperature field leading up to that event. The main limitation on the repetition rate when using DPSS lasers is the pulse energy which dramatically decreases with repetition rate. However the record length is only limited by the onboard camera memory since DPSS lasers operate continuously (unlike pulse-burst systems).

When performing temperature-velocity measurements, another sampling rate limiting factor is the high-speed CMOS used for PIV, which must be operated at high resolution for accurate evaluation of the displacement field and at twice the sampling rate of the thermometry, to obtain an image pair per sample.

At high repetition rates, the fact that the luminescence emission can be detected by non-intensified cameras is an even more important advantage of this fluid thermometry approach. Charge depletion effects arise from the incomplete recharging of the multi-channel plate between frames in high-speed intensifiers. These make a quantitative evaluation of light intensity very difficult, in particular in transient flows where the signal changes a lot, as the responsivity of the sensor depends on the irradiance during the preceding frames, an effect that may even be localised. In Ref. [184], the responsivity and noise characteristics of intensified and non-intensified high-speed CMOS cameras are investigated. This study and other high-speed scalar imaging investigations e.g. Refs. [19,84] have evaluated the characteristics of high-speed CMOS cameras alone, typically finding the performance (linearity and variable pixel-to-pixel response) to be suitable for measurements, see also reviews (Refs. [8,65]), and the discussion of linearity/offset stability in Section 5.

However for high-speed intensifiers, severe non-linearities of up to 35% depending on the gain and specific intensifier unit and up to 5% pixel-to-pixel variation in the linearity of the whole system were reported [184]. Further investigations of these devices are reported in Ref. [85], which emphasise that a detailed study of the specific intensifier unit for the implemented framing rate, exposure time and irradiance levels is mandatory to establish the range over which the unit can be used accurately, derive corrective functions, and thereby extract any quantitative measurements.

3.2.4. Filters

For lifetime measurements, the spectral band of interest simply needs to be isolated or certain spectral regions blocked, for example around the excitation laser line. However when the temperature dependence of the emission spectrum is exploited for intensity ratio measurements, e.g. for temperature imaging by using two cameras with distinct interference filters, the filter choice is critical. The knowledge of the luminescence emission spectra at different temperatures is a pre-requisite to design a two-colour experiment, and is most often obtained from a stack of phosphor powder placed in an optically accessible furnace (see Section 4.3). For a given set of filters, the intensity ratio φ at various temperatures can be estimated by digital integration, as in:

$$\varphi(T) = \frac{\int_0^\infty E(\lambda, T) \tau_B(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty E(\lambda, T) \tau_A(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (2)$$

where $E(\lambda, T)$ is the spectral flux at the input of the spectrometer and τ_A and τ_B the spectral transmission functions of the two channels, which also includes the transmission function of the lens and quantum efficiency of the sensor. The temperature sensitivity ψ (in %/K), the normalised change in the intensity ratio with temperature) is then defined as:

$$\psi(T) = \frac{1}{\varphi(T)} \frac{d\varphi(T)}{dT} = \frac{d \ln(\varphi(T))}{dT} \quad (3)$$

A simple estimation of the average temperature sensitivity ψ over the range of interest can be obtained from the slope of a straight line fitted through the $(\ln(\varphi(T)), T)$ data.

The two primary functions of the filter combination are 1) to minimise the random temperature uncertainty over the temperature range of interest and for a given level of luminescence intensity and 2) limit interference signals from any other sources of light (Mie scattering, flame luminosity, thermal radiation from surfaces) while transmitting as much signal as possible. At a given temperature the random uncertainty in the measured temperature is:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\psi} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{I_A}}{I_A}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{I_B}}{I_B}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

where I_A and I_B are the estimated recorded intensity in channel A and B respectively, and σ_{I_A} , σ_{I_B} the random uncertainty in these values. In other words σ_{I_A}/I_A is the inverse of the signal to noise ratio in channel A. One can infer from Eq. 4 that it is generally the inverse of the product of the temperature sensitivity ψ and the signal to noise ratio in the weakest channel which determines the temperature precision, so this product must be maximised to minimise the uncertainty.

Predicting signal to noise ratio for a given measurement configuration is not always straightforward, requiring the knowledge of the emission intensity either per particle or for a specific particle concentration, for a given excitation fluence and temperature, as well as the noise characteristics and sensitivity of the sensors. The luminescence intensities of the phosphors BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO have been quantified in the studies described in Section 4.4. In Ref. [13], we describe a model for the prediction of the measurement uncertainty based on these data. Lee et al. mention the use of a similar model to optimise the filter combination for BAM:Eu²⁺ [16]. Using our model

and particle signal levels measured in a completely independent study, we came to the same conclusions. Basically, it is critical to perform the analysis for realistic signal levels in the fluid, otherwise it is possible that a highly sensitive but low throughput set of filters will be chosen. Both total transmission and sensitivity must be balanced, and it is important to optimise the filters for the particular temperature range of the experiment. In other words, for a given phosphor, one set of filters might be better at low temperature, another at high temperature. More sensitive filters are favoured when there is a significant fixed error contribution to the intensity ratio precision (see Section 5.1).

For phosphors where the temperature dependence comes from two distinct energy levels, the gating of the two exposures can be used to tune the temperature sensitivity, as the lifetime of two lines or group of lines have different lifetime versus temperature characteristics. Ref. [47], used an “optimised” camera timing with the YAG:Pr³⁺ phosphor which improves the temperature sensitivity of the intensity ratio from 0.46 to 0.87 %/K in the range 600–800 K (this estimation is based on digitised curves from Ref. [47]). Again, the effect on the level of the recorded luminescence signals should be quantified, and taken into account when assessing the performance of a specific timing scheme.

As a guideline, it is preferable to have the intensity ratio close to unity in the middle of the temperature range of interest as large difference in signal between the two channels are challenging due to the dynamic range and linearity of the sensor. The rejection of scattered laser light is also essential, as this process is much stronger than the luminescence and we recommend optical densities of 4 or more at the laser wavelength. For some of the setups described in the next section, the use of a suitable dichroic beamsplitter in place of a spectrally flat 50/50 beamsplitter can double the signal level in each channel.

3.2.5. Two-colour imaging setups

To derive the two dimensional temperature field from phosphor particles with a temperature dependent emission spectrum, it is necessary to form two images of the same particle field, each filtered in a specific spectral region, on two distinct sets of pixels. The main point is that these must be spatially matched prior to division. This can be aided by software but from an optical point of view some setups are advantageous. The following applies only to two-colour intensity ratio imaging methods because generally, for the lifetime imaging approach using high-speed CMOS cameras, single images are formed on a single detector.

In the simplest setup, two cameras with two different interference filters are positioned next to each other and both are slightly angled so as to form two different views of the same object, as shown in Fig. 14 a). This was used for temperature measurements in a heated jet using the phosphor YAG:Dy³⁺ [178]. In such case, a Scheimpflug adapter on at least one of the cameras is necessary to tilt the object focal plane of the camera so that it lies in the measurement plane defined by the laser sheet, so that the whole measurement plane is imaged in focus. Because two different viewing angles of the particle fields are used, a relative perspective error still exists between the two images. Particles appear in different locations depending on their depth position in the light sheet as depicted on Fig. 15. This displacement error is a function of the distance between the camera and the object. The depth-dependent position is the optical principle behind stereoscopic PIV. In an intensity ratio imaging approach, it is necessary to compare spectrally filtered signals from the same particle or group of particles. Therefore this relative displacement of the particle intensity field is problematic and must be corrected for, normally using software mapping, which is discussed in Section 3.3. However, due to the stereoscopic effect, different corrections should be applied to different planes within the light sheet. A correction simply based on the mid-plane results in a residual

Fig. 14. Two colour imaging system: stereo setup with two Scheimpflug adapters a), two cameras on opposite sides b) two camera - beamsplitter arrangement c), image doubler (LaVision) d), Optosplit (Cairn research) e). Note that the last two devices have been plotted with a larger scale for visualisation.

displacement δ in the measurement plane between two images of the same particle depending on the position in the light sheet:

$$\delta = \tan\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)z \quad (5)$$

where θ is the angle between the optical axes of the two imaging systems, and z the position of the particle relative to the mapped plane as illustrated in Fig 15. Using such a setup, we have found that, for a light sheet 700 μm thick and a field of view 43×36 mm, a stereo angle of just 9° reduces the intensity ratio precision by a factor 5 compared to the beamsplitter arrangement described below, because the particle fields do not match. Increasing the angle to 60° made the measured ratio field so noisy as to be unworkable.

One way to avoid this perspective error is to place the two cameras on opposite sides of the measurement plane, as shown in Fig. 14 b), so that the optical axis of the two imaging systems are colinear. This system was previously used for particle imaging in the gas phase [37,45]. Such arrangements require optical access from both sides. In addition, the luminescence light emitted by the particles can be reflected by the interference filters and collected by each opposing camera. This degrades the spatial resolution of the technique. Furthermore, as in the stereoscopic arrangement described above, the optical paths of the two imaging systems are separate so that any difference on the optical paths, for example from dust,

Fig. 15. Perspective error using a stereo arrangement. The two particles marked by the black dots are physically located in the same x position, but the particle at the back of the light sheet in a different z position appears in a different x location in the image plane, and will not be corrected properly using a mapping procedure applied in the centre of the light sheet.

particles or droplets deposited on windows, or beam steering effects due to a non-uniform temperature field, may cause problematic intensity differences between the two images.

A more robust approach is to use a beamsplitter and two cameras positioned at 90° as shown in Fig. 14 c). Spectral separation can be achieved either by interference filters in front of the respective camera objectives and/or using a dichroic i.e. spectrally selective beamsplitter. In this configuration, if the relative position of the two cameras is adjusted, the optical path between the object and beamsplitter can be made nearly identical for both imaging systems, so that spectrally flat attenuation caused by, for example fouled windows, has the same effect on both images, and thus in principle divides out in the division. The matching of the optical paths, single-sided optical access, and robustness to interference are good reasons why this is a very popular approach to intensity ratio imaging and has been used for flow thermometry in many studies [14–16,19,20,44,46,47,172,185,186]. Note the angular dependence of the dichroic may lead to strong variations in reflection and transmission spectrum across the field of view, requiring corrective procedures described in Section 3.3).

Different systems have been used to form two spectrally distinct images of the same object on the same camera. This has the obvious benefit that it saves one image sensor. The stereoscope (“image doubler” as it is often referred to) shown in Fig. 14d) is an assembly of two apertures, two adjustable mirrors and a prism that are all mounted in front of the camera objective. A stereoscope was used in Refs. [29,31–33,35,39,42,43]. With this system, two views of the same object are projected on the two halves of the image sensor. Interference filters are placed over each aperture. The image doubler suffers from the same perspective error issue as the stereoscopic arrangement. The key problem with these systems are that the spatial extent of the image formed by the lens through one aperture is not limited to half of the sensor. Then an object peripheral to the field of view can be imaged via one aperture onto the wrong side of the chip, in addition to the object of interest imaged through the other aperture. This is a severe problem if light is emitted adjacent to the field of view, which may very often be the case in practical situations. To prevent this so-called cross-talk, the aperture can be reduced, which decreases the transmission of this secondary image due to vignetting. Based on the transmission curve provided in the literature for a commercially available stereoscope sold by LaVision GmbH, a f -stop as high as 5.6 is necessary to reduce the transmittance of the secondary image to below 10% of the primary image over 75% of the field of view. We confirmed these values experimentally. This results in a factor 16 reduction in the throughput as

opposed to a two camera system with $f/1.4$ objectives. A good way to deal with cross-talk is to use the laser sheet to define the spatial extent of the region where light is emitted in the axis in which the image is doubled. For example, if the laser propagates horizontally and if the image doubler is mounted vertically, the height of the laser sheet can be adjusted so that it just matches the size of the primary field of view defined by the projection of half the sensor, removing any light source which could form secondary objects. This solution was adopted for 3D mixture fraction imaging using acetone LIF [187].

The Optosplit from Cairn Research is another system for single sensor/two-colour imaging which was developed for fluorescence microscopy. As shown in Fig. 14 e), a first lens is used to form an image onto a rectangular aperture, which defines the spatial extent of the object, preventing cross talk. The light is then collimated by an additional lens, split by a beamsplitter, and redirected by a set of mirrors through a lens to form two duplicate images side by side on a single sensor. The mirror arrangement is designed to compensate any path length difference so that relative perspective distortion between the two images is avoided. However, this particular system is designed for microscopy, so the small size of the optical elements result in a dramatic drop in light throughput for the demagnification typically used for the field of view of most fluid flow experiments. A custom system following a similar approach to the Optosplit was used with success by Yokomori et al. in a heated jet of air [53].

3.2.6. Integration with velocimetry

A major advantage of thermometry techniques based on phosphor particles is that much sought-after simultaneous velocity measurements are possible, usually using Mie scattering from the phosphor particles. First, we address a question we are often asked: “why not use the luminescence particle images for PIV?”. As discussed previously for the high-speed camera approach of Someya et al. [52], the lifetime-based temperature diagnostic may be influenced by the motion of the particles, which has the disadvantage that it effectively limits the range of flow conditions, and therefore applications. A similar principle (using the long luminescence decay of some phosphors following a single laser pulse to record time-separated images of the particles) was also exploited in Ref. [53]. Instead, for thermometry a two-colour ratio imaging approach was used, as shown in Fig. 16. If properly optimised, this can eliminate any adverse effect of the particles moving on the temperature measurement. Another approach is to use two excitation laser pulses with a short time delay, for example with a dual cavity 355 nm laser,

Fig. 16. Concept for simultaneous temperature and velocity imaging using a single laser, and a two-colour single camera dual-frame system (the detection system used is discussed below in Section 3.2.5). Reproduced from [53] with permission from the Society of Automotive Engineers.

and record two subsequent luminescence images of the particles for PIV, as was recently done in Ref. [185].

These methods are tempting because they remove the PIV system altogether. However, for thermometry often the luminescence imaging cameras are hardware-binned to reduce noise levels, and lenses are set to maximum aperture ($f/1.4$ or higher) to maximise the signal level. This directly conflicts with the ordinarily high pixel resolution and a stepped down aperture necessary to optimise the particle images for PIV algorithms. Therefore these approaches require further consideration of the loss in PIV measurement quality in relation to depth of field and pixel locking effects; and drop in signal-to-noise ratio in the thermometry if the camera hardware binning is reduced. A careful analysis is called for.

In general, to achieve the best possible temperature measurements, it is usually preferable to decouple the thermometry and velocimetry systems by detecting the particle Mie scattering with a separate detector(s), and using additional lasers as necessary. For example, for additional velocity measurements using LDV a conventional argon-ion laser and PMT may be used, or for PIV, add the usual double-pulse PIV laser at 532 nm and camera. Another option for PIV is to frequency triple (or quadruple) the output of the PIV laser, so as to use only one laser for both luminescence excitation, and velocimetry using the Mie scattering at 355 nm, as in [17]. Also, the residual green output from a single cavity frequency tripled (or quadrupled) laser can also be extracted and combined with an additional second single pulse laser at 532 nm as in [44].

The experimental setup for integrated LDV and point thermometry is relatively straightforward [21,22]. For the simultaneous application of PIV using particle Mie scattering (or for particle counting as described in Section 4), the extra camera required may be positioned in various ways. It can be on the same side of the measurement plane as the luminescence imaging cameras, and fitted with a Scheimpflug adapter as in [20,44]. However, there is then a perspective error inherent to single camera PIV originating from out of plane motion, which increases with the angle between the camera axis and the normal to the measurement plane. If the test rig allows two sided optical access, another solution is to place the camera on the opposite side of the measurement plane. A coloured glass filter can be positioned at an angle to minimise interference with the luminescence detection system [16,51].

If neither is possible, an additional beamsplitter can be used, which in combination with a two-camera plus beamsplitter arrangement means that the three cameras are imaging the particles from the same side and on the same axis. Off-the-shelf long pass dichroic mirrors can be used, i.e. with the Mie scattering camera in transmission, but the problem is that the particle luminescence is imaged onto one camera via two reflections. In our experience, this led to an unacceptable level of optical aberrations, due to waveform distortion at the beamsplitters. Using 532 nm shortpass dichroic mirror would avoid that any of the luminescence images are acquired via two reflections, but for the phosphors BAM:Eu²⁺ or ZnO, for example, which emit in the near visible-blue spectral range, such optics proved hard to find. Since the Mie scattered light is often a lot more intense than the luminescence light, a spectrally flat low reflectivity plate or pellicle beamsplitter can be used as the first beamsplitter, which reflects the Mie scattering and transmits most of the luminescence. This approach was employed in Ref. [47] for simultaneous temperature and velocity imaging in gas flows using YAG:Pr³⁺.

3.3. Image acquisition and processing

The flow diagram in Fig. 17 presents the processing steps to generate a temperature field using the spectrally resolved method (intensity ratio). Some operations are corrections to account for interfering signals (offset and background subtractions), alignment of the detector(s) (image mapping) or for the response of the

Fig. 17. Processing diagram from the acquisition of the two luminescence images to the derivation of the temperature field, for two-colour intensity ratio imaging. Steps in parentheses may not always be necessary.

phosphor (fluence correction, temperature conversion). Some steps are also taken to reduce statistical measurement uncertainty (cutoff filter, spatial filter) at the expense of the measurement resolution.

The reasons for the focus on the two-colour intensity ratio approach are its popularity for flow temperature imaging and the peculiarities of particle-based two-colour scalar imaging, which are quite unique since they require the very accurate overlap of particle images. Curve fitting algorithms for the lifetime for point and 2D methods are extensively described in the literature for surface phosphor thermometry (see reviews [10–12]) and other fields, and are not explained here. Therefore some of the steps mentioned in the following are specific only to the two-colour imaging method, but the background correction, nonlinearity correction, spatial filtering and fluence correction are all also relevant to lifetime-based approaches.

3.3.1. Background subtraction

The term background designates any signal that does not originate from the spectrally filtered luminescence collected from the particles in the elementary probe volume, and so it must be subtracted. Luminescence from particles deposited on the surfaces, either directly imaged or reflected by other surfaces, surface flare, and flame radiation are example of background sources. The number of counts in the raw image can be described by:

$$G = G_{lum} + G_{bg} + G_{dc} \quad (6)$$

where the first term is the desired light contribution from the phosphor tracer particles in the probe volume, the second term the light contribution from other light sources, including those induced by the laser pulse, e.g. surface scattering, signal from particles attached to walls and laser induced fluorescence (window, fuels), and the last term for the camera offset.

Note that often the offset and background light originating from stable sources can be subtracted together $G_{bg} + G_{dc}$ as an average image without particle seeding. However there are reasons why these contributions may be separated in the analysis: 1) that the camera offset (and the background, see below) may be unstable and require specific consideration; and 2) that for accurate linearity

correction, the offset-subtracted background signal G_{bg} must be evaluated separately.

The uncertainty in the background evaluation increases with the intensity of the background signal, so that it is essential to minimise it, via removing, cleaning or blacking out reflective surfaces, and choosing filter combination that minimises interferences from other light sources such as flame luminescence or stray light. Also often, the background varies in time, so it cannot be accurately evaluated. Uncertainties originating from interfering background signals are discussed in detail in Section 5.4.

3.3.2. Image mapping

Accurate mapping between the object and image space is important for any imaging technique to correlate the measured temperature/velocity to the spatial location (x,y). Here, in addition, because it is necessary to divide two highly structured luminescence particle images we must minimise any relative displacement between the two images, otherwise sharp gradients in the intensity field would lead to extreme values after division.

The traditional approach to two-colour imaging consists of roughly adjusting the two sensors in space so as to achieve the best spatial overlap between the two images which maximises the useful part of the active sensor area. There may still be a displacement of several pixels between the two images of the same object resulting from translation, rotation and scaling, which is then corrected by software mapping as in various flow thermometry studies using phosphor particles [16,19,37].

For the beamsplitter setup described in Section 3.2.5 (Fig. 14), fine mechanical alignment of the two sensors can be used to further maximise the sensor useful area, and to guarantee the best overlap between the optical paths of the two image systems. By placing the reflection camera on two translation stages, and the beamsplitter on a mount with two rotation axis, relative distortion between the two images can be minimised. It is actually then possible to run a PIV algorithm with a coarse vector spacing (e.g. the interactive PIV mode of the DaVis program from LaVision GmbH), to continuously display the displacement field during adjustment of the sensor, which provides very useful feedback to the user setting up the experiment. To derive the displacement field, either a target with evenly spaced lines, or the particles themselves can be used. With such approach, for a PCO sennicam QE CCD sensor with 4×4 hardware pixel binning, and a magnification of 0.3, mean values of the residual displacement field in the range 0.15–0.25 pixels can be achieved, as shown on Fig. 18. The residual displacement is likely due to a relative distortion caused by the beamsplitter. In such cases, no software

Fig. 18. Residual distortion between two filtered images after manual alignment or two-camera plus beamsplitter system. The axes designate the binned pixel number. The mean absolute displacement is 0.18 binned pixels.

mapping was performed before division of the particle images, and only a simple scaling of image was applied on the temperature field [14,44].

In cases which larger displacement, or to further improve the mapping between the images, a target consisting of equally spaced dots or crosses can be imaged and a calibration procedure used. The idea behind software mapping is to identify the distortion between an object and its image in order to apply the inverse distortion to the recorded particle images. To map two cameras with each other, both images are mapped to the same physical coordinates. A detailed description of the process can be found in Ref. [188]. In this procedure, the accurate positioning of the calibration target in the measurement plane is necessary, in particular for off-axis imaging system (stereoscopic cameras and image doubler).

Since luminescence images are highly structured, a PIV-like cross-correlation between the particle fields in both channels can also be used to derive the relative displacement field between the two sensors. In post-processing, one of the two images can then be deformed by the displacement field, which consist of a 2D interpolation of its intensity field for each sub-regions used in the vector calculation. This approach can be viewed as a simple planar version of the self-calibration method for stereo PIV which corrects the mapping functions of the two cameras in case of a misalignment of the 3-D calibration target and the thin laser sheet, using disparity maps extracted from particle image cross-correlation [189]. Particle image based approaches are also employed in Refs. [45,53].

It is unclear at this stage whether accurate manual alignment, or a deformation of the images in post processing after rough alignment offers the lowest uncertainty. Certainly, in general it is likely that using image mapping is a more versatile approach. In any case, this is always possible following manual alignment, where the manual procedure still serves to maximise the overlap between the two detection paths, as well as the use of the sensor active areas.

For measurements with CCD cameras that are hardware binned, it is possible to improve the accuracy of the mapping based on images of particles or target at full sensor resolution, as shown on Fig. 19. At high measurement resolution (e.g. 200 μm), the measurement precision is significantly improved (15% to 9%) when using a mapping function derived at full resolution. Here the measurement resolution was adjusted by the size of the moving average filter (see following section) and was measured as the 10–90% distance of the edge spread function from an equally processed image of a calibration target. In reality the improvement is even larger, because the spatial resolution is degraded when dividing two images with a relative

displacement. At lower spatial resolution ($> 300 \mu\text{m}$), the measurement precision is less sensitive to small residual displacement, and so the benefit of this approach becomes negligible.

3.3.3. Filtering

After the background subtraction, and possibly the image mapping, an intensity cut-off filter is generally applied. The role of this filter is to exclude areas of low signal where very few particles are present from further processing. Temperature information will not be provided for these pixels. This is in order to only provide temperature information which has a sufficient degree of confidence in terms of statistical uncertainty. This allows further discrimination when performing subsequent spatial or time averaging to define confidence. For example, if at a given pixel position the averaging area contains an insufficient number of non-zero pixels for statistical confidence, it should also be discarded from further processing. In Ref. [16], a filter conditioned on a Mie scattering image of the particles was also used. Via cross-correlation, the Mie scattering image and the luminescence image were matched, and from the Mie scattering, regions where too few particles are present were identified and removed from the luminescence images.

An additional filter should also be used to remove saturated pixels, which obviously have a non-linear response. For non-intensified cameras, the threshold must be the maximum pixel intensity. For intensified cameras, saturation effects may already be observed below the full well capacity of the camera, requiring a lower filter level [190].

Usually a moving average, moving median filter, or simply binning is then used to increase the signal to noise ratio at the expense of spatial resolution, as shown in Fig. 19. Note that in Ref. [16], these filtering operations were performed after division of the background subtracted images. Addition and division not commuting, the operation order may affect the numerical values, so the same order should be also used for generating correction and calibration data.

The final resolution of the measurement is then established using equally smoothed images of a resolution target, e.g. a knife edge, a Siemens star or a 1951 USAF target. Unfortunately, this information is missing in many published works on fluid thermometry using phosphor particles.

3.3.4. Corrections

After the cutoff and spatial filter, the two resulting images can be divided. To determine whether further corrections are needed, the intensity ratio is expressed as a function of various experimental variables:

$$\varphi = \varphi(x, y, T, F) \quad (7)$$

where x and y are the location in the object plane, T the fluid temperature and F the local fluence. The dependence on the spatial coordinate x and y originates from non uniformities in the collection efficiency and from the angular dependence of the spectral transmission function of the filters and beamsplitter.

A dependence of the intensity ratio on the laser fluence has been observed for BAM:Eu²⁺ [13,16] and ZnO [14] to various extents, the origin of which will be discussed in Section 4.4.4. Assuming that the dependencies can be separated [14]:

$$\varphi(x, y, T, F) = \alpha(x, y)\beta(T)\gamma(F(x, y)) \quad (8)$$

The first term describes the “white field” correction (also sometimes referred to as flat field), assuming this is independent of temperature. The second term describes the dependence of the intensity ratio on temperature, and the third the dependence of the intensity ratio on the overall spatial distribution of the fluence field. The separation of these last two terms assumes that the relative change of the intensity ratio with temperature is independent of the laser

Fig. 19. Intensity ratio precision and spatial resolution obtained from particle images after image mapping based on full resolution target images or on 4x4 hardware binned target images.

fluence. These assumptions have been explored and are summarised in Section 5.6.

Non-uniformities in the collection efficiency described by the first term can be caused by for example mechanical vignetting. Such effect is pronounced for two-colour single-camera systems, e.g. using an image doubler (see Fig. 14). In addition, the spectral transmission profiles of interference filters are sensitive to incidence angles. The profile as specified by the supplier is only valid for collimated light with a given incidence angle, so in general, for imaging, it is broadened towards the UV even for a point directly on the optical axis because uncollimated light is imaged through the filter. More importantly, the incidence angle of rays originating from a particle in the field of view varies with its spatial location, so the effective spectral transmission profile is position-dependent, with a strong effect on the intensity ratio, in particular for the beamsplitter, and requires correction.

To correct for both effects, a phosphor pellet can be placed behind a diffusive screen as to mimic the spectral content and the Lambertian light emission characteristics of the phosphor and imaged on both channels as was described in Ref. [44]. Particle images can then be divided by this intensity ratio field for white field correction.

Examples of white field images obtained with the phosphor BAM: Eu^{2+} using an image doubler and a beamsplitter arrangement are shown in Fig. 20 (note the different scaling). For the image doubler, the white field image is strongly dominated by mechanical vignetting causing a very pronounced gradient from left to right. For the beamsplitter arrangement, the variations are far smaller. The left-to-right gradient, and the circular pattern are believed to be caused by the angular dependence of the beamsplitter and interference filters respectively. In Ref. [37], defocused images of a white paper were recorded, which should in theory produce a uniform illumination on each sensor, allowing to account for non-uniformity in pixel sensitivity. However since the spatial information is lost by defocusing, vignetting and angular dependence cannot be fully corrected this way.

Using the luminescence from seeded particles and the exact same optics (including windows) is the best approach to the white-field correction when a suitable uniform temperature condition can be generated in a straightforward fashion [19,45]. The intensity ratio image obtained from the uniform field at a reference temperature field is then used to correct the measured ratio images under non-isothermal conditions by division, as in:

$$\varphi_n = \frac{\varphi(x, y, T, F)}{\varphi(x, y, T_{\text{ref}}, F)} = \frac{\alpha(x, y)\beta(T)\gamma(F)}{\alpha(x, y)\beta(T_{\text{ref}})\gamma(F)} = \frac{\beta(T)}{\beta(T_{\text{ref}})} \quad (9)$$

This makes the normalised ratio a function of temperature only, meaning it is independent of the fluence distribution and non-

uniformity in light transmission. In this case, a statistically significant average image must be compiled to limit the propagation of uncertainty when applying the correction. Often a room temperature flow is used, which generally has the advantage that it is simple. However, in some cases such as internal combustion engines, this may not be straightforward. Neal et al. used images recorded at the start of the compression stroke where the temperature was assumed to be homogeneous, and known from a thermodynamic calculation [47].

Additional correction for fluctuations in the pulse-to-pulse variations in the laser fluence may be necessary. An error analysis derived from the various assumptions made in these corrections are discussed in Sections 5.6 and 5.7.

3.4. Temperature calibration

To convert the processed data into temperature, the temperature-dependence of the measured quantity must be established. For example, to calibrate the intensity ratio, luminescence spectra recorded from a stack of powder or phosphor coating placed in an optically accessible furnace can be digitally integrated using Eq. (2) to yield a theoretical temperature response of the filter combination. However, such a calibration method may be inaccurate because:

- The spectral transmission functions of the various optical components (camera lens, interference filter, sensor) in each channel may not be accurately known. For cameras and lenses, this is particularly true in the near-UV spectral range. In addition, spectral characteristics of interference filters are usually provided for collimated light only and, as discussed above, may not accurately correspond to imaging situations.
- Section 4.3 will show there may be differences between the luminescence properties of particles recorded in the dispersed-phase and in powder form, due to phenomena such as heating under repeated laser illumination, thermal degradation (oxidation), multiple scattering and self-absorption. Several previous studies of thermographic phosphors have recognised that optical interactions may lead to uncertainty when results obtained from densely-packed powders are used to calibrate flow experiments [49,51,178].

For these two reasons, the absolute value of the measured quantity and its variation with temperature may differ between the calibration and the actual experimental environment and setup. It is also important to note that because of the variability inherent to some of the phosphor manufacturing processes discussed in

Fig. 20. Examples of white field images for the image doubler (left) and two-camera beamsplitter arrangement (right). Note the difference in the colour scale. The axes correspond to vertical and horizontal pixel numbers for a 4x4 hardware binned PCO Sencam QE camera.

Section 2.3, every batch of phosphor should be experimentally characterised to avoid calibration problems.

More generally, in light of these considerations, an in-situ calibration performed with the same optical setup as for the actual measurements is preferred when possible, to minimise the temperature uncertainty. One approach used by Lawrence et al. used a 300 μm diameter thermocouple coated with a 30 μm layer of phosphor, which they inserted into a heated jet and a flame and imaged to extract an intensity ratio which was associated to the thermocouple reading [35]. While such system is relatively simple and avoids uncertainty linked to the transfer function of the optical components, differences may still arise from the fact that the coating is still and as a result repeatedly illuminated and exposed for a relatively long time to high temperature and to possible self-absorption effects.

Instead, a typical way to calibrate the optical system/phosphor combination in-situ is to add the particles to a temperature controlled liquid, or seed the phosphor particles into a gas jet while adjusting the jet exit temperature. For temperatures in the range 300 to 800 K, an in-line electrical heater is typically used. For measurements at higher temperatures, a tube can be placed inside a high temperature furnace, and measurements performed at the exit of the tube as described in Ref. [13]. To avoid thermal expansion displacing the tube exit, a fused silica tube can be used. For temperatures below room temperature, a similar tube can be placed inside a liquid nitrogen flask. Under controlled conditions, the jet forms an extended isothermal region with a steady temperature which can be measured by a thermocouple probe, as discussed in Section 6.2. Sources of uncertainty in the reference temperature are discussed in Section 5.7, and depend on the temperature range, probe geometry, and immersion depth in the fluid.

A suitable fit is then found for the measured datapoints, and used to convert the images into temperature. A second order polynomial was found to well describe the intensity ratio response of BAM:Eu²⁺ [44] while a power law was found to be more suitable for ZnO [14]. A description of the uncertainty associated with the calibration and temperature conversion process is given in Section 5.7.

As an outlook, measuring luminescence spectra from particles dispersed in the fluid over the temperature range of interest offers interesting perspectives. First it would improve optimisation of the filter choice, which is free of the systematic errors linked to the bulk powder studies. In the particular cases where the transmission functions of the optics are accurately known, it would also alleviate the need for an extra calibration with the imaging system.

4. Characterisation of phosphor particles for flow thermometry

The following section presents a summary of the current state of knowledge about the luminescence properties of phosphor particles that have been used for flow thermometry. The emphasis is placed on properties that are particularly relevant to fluid thermometry, such as the luminescence emission intensity and the sensitivity to the surrounding environment. There are various phosphor characterisation methods, which stem from the observation that the information extracted from studies of bulk powder may not always be relevant to the case of dispersed particles, prompting the need for in-situ characterisation studies. These methodologies are summarised and the advantages and limitations of each are discussed. We then review the findings of the characterisation work so far undertaken for some phosphors in the context of fluid temperature measurements.

4.1. Phosphors used for flow thermometry

To the best of our knowledge, Table 1 below lists all the thermographic phosphors used to date for fluid temperature measurements,

and/or characterised in the fluid phase in the context of fluid thermometry. For each phosphor, the thermometry strategies employed and applications are provided. Intrinsic physical parameters (particle size), luminescence properties (luminescence lifetime) and experimental parameters that are closely related to the luminescence characteristics (excitation and detection wavelengths) are also listed.

It can be seen that one of the most important parameters, the luminescence lifetime at room temperature, varies by more than six orders of magnitude among these different phosphors. Note that some phosphors have different lifetimes for different emission lines, and here when two groups of lines are used for the temperature evaluation, the lifetime of the longest group is given. A range of excitation wavelengths has been used, primarily the UV harmonics of pulsed Nd:YAG lasers at 355 and 266 nm but also 375 nm (cw diode laser [21,22]), a line in the infrared spectral range at 980 nm (using an OPO/OPA system) for the upconversion phosphor Y₂O₂S:Er³⁺,Yb³⁺, and 337 nm generated using a pulsed N₂ laser. The luminescence emission may be comprised of relatively sharp lines or of a broader band as in the case of ZnO and BaMgAl₁₀O₁₇:Eu²⁺, as was shown on Fig. 4. The detected spectral range is always visible or near-visible. Just this small selection of phosphors is indicative of the previously-mentioned flexibility in excitation and detection wavelengths. Where specified in the original articles, the particle size is usually in the 2–5 μm range, but both larger (8–10 μm) and much smaller (50 nm) particles have been employed. These phosphors were variously used in liquids and gases, with temporal and spectral methods, and for both point and planar measurements. Note that in the table, spectral ratio and intensity ratio are used respectively to differentiate between a temperature measurement derived from a recorded luminescence spectrum, and one based on spectral selection using optical filters on the detection channel(s).

4.2. The aims of phosphor particle characterisation

Naturally the success of a measurement using a given phosphor depends on the thermometry strategy and execution, calibration and so forth. As discussed in the previous and the following sections, these directly determine or influence the temperature range, precision, temporal and spatial resolution, and temperature accuracy. However, the similarities and differences summarised in Table 1 serve to indicate that the choice of phosphor itself is critical. The question is: which phosphor to use in a given application? For example, eight different phosphors were used in heated free jets of air using the intensity ratio method. For a fixed short ($\sim \mu\text{s}$) integration time (camera exposure) the signal levels from phosphors with lifetimes ranging from ns-ms must vary widely. These different phosphors have different temperature sensitivities. Yet together these two parameters govern the intrinsic precision of the temperature measurement, as described by Eq. (4). The chosen particle size also varies considerably, but this directly affects the flow and temperature tracing accuracy and also the luminescence signal. Most notably, among these studies there are reports that appear to be inconsistent, e.g. for Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Dy³⁺, where some of the cited experiments were in fact deemed unsuccessful under certain conditions [35,36,38,46].

That many different phosphors have been chosen for temperature measurements in fluids is perhaps to be expected, for very few studies have provided measurements of the “absolute” luminescence intensity of phosphor particles, especially in the framework of fluid thermometry. Furthermore, the possibilities to theoretically predict in a generalised fashion whether a phosphor will offer useful functionality for flow thermometry are somewhat limited. The luminescence signal of the material at a given temperature depends on the absorption coefficient at the excitation wavelength and the quantum efficiency of the transition(s) detected for thermometry. Due to the complexity of the luminescence processes in inorganic

Table 1
Phosphor particles used for flow thermometry studies and/or characterised in the fluid phase in the context of fluid thermometry. Unless referenced otherwise, all studies using a given phosphor were conducted using the stated experimental parameter(s).

Phosphor	Lifetime	Excitation wavelength (nm)	Detected spectral lines/region (nm)	Particle size (μm)	thermometry strategy	application/fluid
$\text{La}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Eu}^{3+}$	12 μs ^a	355, 337 [24]	512	10 [24], unknown [26,28], 5 [27]	lifetime - point [24,26,27], 2D [28]	LiBr-water falling films [24], falling/suspended water droplets [26–28], water sprays [28]
$\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6\text{:Mn}^{4+}$	3 ms	266 [26], 355, 385 (LED) [171]	632/657 ratio, >560 [52], unknown [171]	unknown [26,39], 8 [29], 4–6 [52], 5 [171]	spectral ratio - point [26]; intensity ratio - 2D [29,39]; lifetime - point [39], 2D [52,171]	water droplets [26], n-dodecane sprays [29], heated air jet/recirculating flows [39], motored IC engine [52], silicon oil jet [171]
ZnO , ZnO:Ga ^b [42]	<1 ns	355 [14,42,185], 266 [15]	387 band	2, 5 [42]	intensity ratio - 2D	heated air jet flow [14,185], water thermal plume [15], burning methanol droplets [42]
$\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}\text{:Dy}^{3+}$, $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}\text{:Dy,Er}$ [178,186] ^c	~1 ms	355	458/497 ratio, 458 peak [36], 400–600 [38,49], 410–470/470–490 [46]	4 [31–33,43], 2 [178], 2.5 & 10.2 [35], 3.5 [186], 1.7 [36,49], unknown [46], μm -size & < 50 nm [38]	spectral ratio - point [38,49]; intensity ratio - 2D	[31–33,35,43,46,178,186]; lifetime - point [31], 2D [36]
IC engine HCCI [31–33]; Diesel [43], heated air jet flow [31,35,46,178], calibration cell [186], ambient N_2 [36], premixed flame [36,49], jet-A/water [38]						
$\text{BaMgAl}_{10}\text{O}_{17}\text{:Eu}^{2+}$	1 μs	355, 375 (cw) [21,22], 266 [13], 376 ^d [13]	450 band	2.4–2.9 ^e , 4 [43,50], 3.5 [37]	intensity ratio - 2D, point [21]; spectral ratio - point [50]; lifetime (phase-shift) - point [22]	Diesel IC engine [43], high-pressure combustion vessel [37], heated/ambient air jet flow [16,18,19,21,22,35,44,50,51], heated N_2 flow [13], Von Kármán vortex (air) [19], effusion film cooling (air) [20], N_2 -diluted hydrogen diffusion flames [17]
$\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Er}^{3+}$, Yb^{3+} ^f	50 μs	980	500–540/540–575	8	intensity ratio - 2D	heated air jet [45]
$\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}\text{:Pr}^{3+}$	190 μs ^g	266	484/610	1.8	intensity ratio - 2D	heated air jet [46], motored IC engine [47], air/vitiated stream shear mixing layer [48]
$\text{YVO}_4\text{:Eu}^{3+}$	~300 μs ^h	355	535–592/618–620	<50 nm [38], 1.8 [172]	spectral ratio - point [38]; intensity ratio - 2D [172]	jet-A/water [38], liquid jet-A injection into hot air crossflow [172]
$\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{:Eu}^{3+}$	1 ms	266	587/611	4	intensity ratio - 2D	heated air jet flow [53]

^a Lifetime of $^5\text{D}_2$ line;

^b Only the edge luminescence of ZnO is detected;

^c Only the emission from Dy^{3+} is detected;

^d broadband excitation, 200 cm^{-1} ;

^e same grade and supplier used (KEMK63/UF-P1/2, Phosphor Technology, UK);

^f upconversion phosphor, Er^{3+} emission;

^g Lifetime of $^1\text{D}_2$ line;

^h Lifetime of $^5\text{D}_0$ line.

solids (see Section 2), these quantities are already difficult to determine in advance simply from the known composition, dopant concentration, phase, impurities etc. For almost all phosphors, the absorption coefficient is not available, and the quantum efficiency is only provided as a relative measure.

The spatial extent of the material, in this case nm- to μm -scale particles, also determines the nature of the laser-particle interaction. The quantity of light absorbed (and scattered) by a particle is given by the absorption and scattering cross-sections. These are usually calculated using Maxwell's equations, often considering spherical particles for simplicity, with knowledge of the particle diameter and optical constants. The cross-sections may also have a complex dependence on the particle shape, structure, state of agglomeration and even orientation.

Although the direct measurement of these parameters either for powders or single particles would be very useful, for our purposes this is not the main goal of characterisation. Rather, with a pragmatic

focus on improving and broadening the capabilities of the measurement technique, the primary aim is to systematically characterise the luminescence characteristics of phosphor particles relevant to flow thermometry. First, quantitative measurements of the luminescence signal of a known quantity of particles are required. This allows the accurate comparison of different phosphors. Second, the temperature-dependence of the signal and spectrum and/or lifetime must be known. Together this information enables the prediction of signal levels and temperature precision for practical applications. Third, from the perspective of error analysis it is also important to analyse possible cross-dependencies of either the measured temperature or luminescence signal on other parameters, such as the fluid composition, particle seeding density, excitation laser fluence and irradiance as well as practical considerations such as possible irreversible particle damage.

Special attention should be paid to the first requirement. For characterisation purposes it is crucial to have some measure, for

example the mass of particles or the particle number density, to know, for a given phosphor and for specified conditions, how many particles are required for a successful measurement. The luminescence emission intensity varies greatly between different phosphor materials, and in principle, the luminescence signal is a direct function of the seeding density. It is then tempting to infer that one may seed orders of magnitude more particles into a flow to compensate in situations with low signal levels for example, at high temperatures (low quantum efficiencies); where excitation fluence is limited, or simply where the phosphor is unfavourable for flow thermometry in the first instance i.e. poor absorption, inefficient or possessing a long lifetime. However inviting, this approach will not work, not least because in heavily seeded fluids multiple scattering may unacceptably reduce the accuracy and spatial resolution (see Section 5.5), and/or in reacting gases alter the volumetric heat capacity and even directly quench the flame (see Section 5.8). To be clear, the number of particles does not routinely need to be known for the technique to function effectively, but it is essential to be mindful of the seeding level to ensure it is reasonable and does not unduly compromise the accuracy, resolution or non-intrusive character of the measurement.

With said goals in mind, the next sections describe various phosphor particle characterisation methods and their advantages and disadvantages in providing the necessary information.

4.3. Characterisation methodology

First we present methods to study particles in *bulk powder* form, taken to mean the case where the particles are densely packed as a powder or coating. However, when the intended application is fluid temperature measurements, there are some limitations to studying particles in this way, and so secondly we introduce procedures used to characterise *dispersed* particles.

4.3.1. Bulk powder methods

The luminescence emission spectrum and lifetime of many phosphors are available from literature, usually measured from particles in the form of bulk powder. The books “The Phosphor Handbook” [158] and “Inorganic Phosphors” [164] cover thousands of materials. However, often the effects of temperature are not known, unless either this has a strong effect on the luminescence pertaining to the phosphors intended original application, e.g., lighting, displays, or the phosphor has been studied for surface thermometry (see for example reviews [10–12] and reports [41,165,166]).

Spectroscopy instruments

If no information is available, the spectral/temporal temperature response of a small amount (gram quantities) of powder can be readily determined. Simple setups consisting of a spectrometer and a line/array detector (CCD or intensified CCD) provide spectrally-resolved detection of the luminescence emission. In characterisation experiments of bulk powders, the material is placed in a ceramic crucible inside a temperature-controlled environment, often a furnace (tube or chamber type) with optical access. Temperature gradients across the powder sample must be minimised, so that a thermocouple or resistance thermometer placed in the vicinity supplies an accurate measure of the temperature of the particles probed. Systems that permit variation of total system pressure and/or purging with different gases must be used to determine cross-sensitivity of the luminescence emission to for example O_2 partial pressure (e.g. Refs. [13,191,192]). The excitation light is directed onto the sample and the luminescence emission is collected and focused onto the entrance slit of a spectrometer, see for example Fig. 21. Except for very spectrally sharp transitions, for example trivalently-doped rare-earths, spectral resolution is not a limiting factor and small USB spectrometers can be used to cover a broad wavelength range. The spectral transmission efficiency of the complete detection system

Fig. 21. Generic setup for characterising bulk phosphor powder.

must be calibrated using a known reference spectrum, such as that of a tungsten halogen lamp. This is necessary to recover the correct relative intensity of different emission lines or spectral bands, especially if operating in spectral regions where the efficiency of the diffraction grating, CCD quantum efficiency, or collection lens/objective are steeply changing.

To measure luminescence decay times a PMT or (amplified) photodiode are commonly used. In some spectrometers, a rotating mirror allows the direction of the dispersed light either towards the sensor array or towards a slit, to which a PMT or photodiode can be mounted so as to resolve spectra and decay times with a single system. For phosphors in the millisecond range, spectrally resolved luminescence decays can also be measured using a high speed CMOS camera and a spectrometer, offering a comprehensive picture of the luminescence transitions following a single laser shot [193]. Down-sized or simplified systems e.g. using an optical fiber, and automated systems for lifetime measurements have been developed, for example by Emerging Measurements, Inc., Sensor Coating Systems Ltd, and Lund University [194]. It is also instructive to measure the excitation spectrum of the powder using for example an integrated fluorescence spectrometer instrument.

Advantages

Investigating bulk phosphor powders in this way is a relatively simple task. There are far more particles in the probe volume compared with the dilute dispersion in the gas phase. Consequently the signal level is generally high, even for low fluences, except for exceptionally inefficient phosphors or at extreme temperatures where the transition is almost entirely thermally quenched. The particles do not move or change within the probe volume as they would in a continuous flow, so conditions are easily reproduced. Investigating luminescence at high temperatures or pressures can be achieved using a small, convenient temperature controlled furnace or oven system.

Luminescence characterisation of bulk powder provides essential information in designing experiments using the emission spectrum and the lifetime measured over a range of temperatures. Sensitive filter combinations can be chosen for ratio-based imaging, and the most temperature sensitive emission line/band in a given temperature range for a phosphor can be chosen for the lifetime method. Phosphors can be directly compared in this fashion. For example Fig. 12 in Allison and Gilles [10] and Fig. 7 in Aldén et al. [11] (reproduced below in Fig. 22) are especially useful.

Still, as discussed, the luminescence intensity is of critical importance. In principle, from bulk powder studies, it is possible to obtain data on how the signal varies with temperature i.e. temperature quenching, and as a approximate comparison, compare signal levels between phosphors (in the bulk powder state) [195,196]. However, there are some significant limitations to this approach.

Interferences in bulk powder studies

The material state of the powder in such investigations is important, and is described most elegantly in the Phosphor Handbook “The optical properties of a particle depend on the state of

Fig. 22. Temperature-dependence of the luminescence lifetime (left axis) and intensity ratio (right axis) of many common thermographic phosphors. Reproduced from Ref.[11].

assemblage of particles; a dilute dispersion of particles has different properties from thick powder aggregates such as those encountered in powder beds or in paints. In the former state, the optical character of individual particles dominates, whereas in the latter, complicated multiple scattering occurs."

For example, in fluid thermometry experiments the particle dispersion is dilute to the extent that the luminescence signal is directly proportional to the absorption cross-section. In a packed bed of powder, strong multiple scattering between particles of both the excitation light and the emitted luminescence means that the overall luminescence signal will also be a function of the scattering cross-section and the arrangement of particles. Thus it is impossible to conduct a complete analysis to recover the signal from an individual particle [158]. Yet it is the per particle emission intensity or the signal from a given mass of particles *in a diluted state* that are the parameters of critical interest for flow measurements. For the purpose of comparing phosphors, simply keeping the mass of bulk powder the same is not sufficient. The propagation of light through the bed may be approximated using several approaches (Kubelka–Munk, the Johnson method, Monte–Carlo simulation - for

details refer to [158], Chapter 16). Still, the excitation penetration depth will be difficult to ascertain exactly, and therefore to know the mass of particles that emits the detected signal and the excitation irradiance that was used. In fact, light propagation in packed powders is of significance for surface thermometry because it determines at which location(s) inside the phosphor coating the temperature is effectively measured from, complicating the interpretation of the results [197,198].

Clearly it is difficult to obtain results representative of individual dispersed particles when examining bulk powders or dense coatings. Here we also describe two series of experiments conducted in our laboratory which show additional complications that may arise in characterisation studies of bulk powder.

In the first experiment, a stack of BAM:Eu²⁺ powder (Phosphor Technology KEMK63/UF-P1) was intermittently illuminated by a pulsed laser emitting at 355 nm with a fluence of 80 mJ/cm² and pulse duration of 10 ns. The laser was operated at 15 Hz and, when needed, blocked for many pulses using a shutter. With the aim of measuring the intensity ratio independently of the high-irradiance excitation, halfway between two laser pulses (blocked or not), the

same powder was illuminated by a 0.5 mW 308 nm LED during 1 ms, resulting in a fluence of a few $\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$. The luminescence emission spectrum from the powder was recorded during the LED pulse using a spectroscopy system similar to that in Fig. 21. For each LED pulse, an intensity ratio was derived from the spectral data using the transmission functions of the spectral filters used in imaging experiments, so that the ratio is a monotonic function of particle temperature.

The results are presented in Fig. 23. Note that at the start of the recording sequence, the pulsed laser had been firing at a fixed fluence for several minutes. The intensity ratio measured with LED illumination between laser pulses is higher than the intensity ratio measured when the laser illumination is turned completely off (as indicated by the dotted line). Using the spectral data presented in Fig. 7 and recorded at $1 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$, the temperature difference is estimated to be $\sim 200 \text{ K}$, although the relevance of this estimate is not certain due to the several orders of magnitude difference between both fluences. Between $t \sim 8$ and $t \sim 14 \text{ s}$, the powder was no longer illuminated by the laser, and the intensity ratio indicates a near exponential decay behaviour with a relaxation time of several seconds which may reflect the cooling time in the bulk powder. When the illumination of the powder by the laser was resumed, an exponential rise in the intensity ratio was observed. This relatively long rise time indicates that there is a cumulative heating effect of the powder, so that the energy deposited by the first pulse is not fully dissipated before the next pulse, the temperature of the powder increasing until the temperature difference between the powder and the surroundings is large enough to dissipate the laser energy and steady state is reached.

This may be compared with the case of individual particles in the fluid phase. Section 5.2 shows that the cooling and heating time for a $2 \mu\text{m}$ particle, for example, is approximately $100 \mu\text{s}$. In this case, at least for repetition rates up to 10 kHz , the particles will completely cool down between two laser pulses. Furthermore, at the typical rate of 10 Hz , the same particles are not ordinarily probed by successive laser pulses due to advection in and out of the probe volume by the flow field. Therefore, repeated illumination of the bulk powder leads to a cumulative heating effect that would not occur for individual particles dispersed in a fluid. For example, in Ref. [16], a fluence of $70 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ was used to excite the same BAM:Eu²⁺ phosphor in bulk powder form for spectroscopy. Indeed for some phosphors, fluences of the order of $100\text{'s mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ were often used to obtain

Fig. 23. Time series of the excitation laser fluence (top) and spectrally derived intensity ratio determined under low fluence ($\mu\text{J}/\text{cm}^2$) LED excitation between two laser pulses (bottom), for bulk BAM:Eu powder. The dotted line corresponds to the intensity ratio measured when the laser is continuously off. See main text for additional information.

sufficient signal in fluids. However, according to the results of the experiment above, examining the luminescence emission at fluences relevant to fluid-phase studies may always be complicated by heating and accompanying hysteresis effects. Note that it cannot be excluded at that stage that the observed behaviour under repeated illumination may partly be due to some reversible photochemical effects.

In the second experiment, a stack of bulk ZnO powder (96479, Sigma–Aldrich) was illuminated using the third harmonic (355 nm) of a Nd:YAG laser with a nominal pulse duration of 10 ns and pulse repetition rate of 5 Hz . The laser energy was measured and the beam area was adjusted using an iris ($\sim 5 \text{ mm}$ diameter) to provide a fluence of $17 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$. A time series of recorded spectra is shown in Fig. 24.

Some laser shots evidently cause a pronounced narrowing of the emission peak and increase of the luminescence intensity. These do not correlate with peaks in the pulse energy (7% pulse-to-pulse variation). Therefore this behaviour is random in this regime of laser fluence. Previous studies of ZnO powder have attributed this irregular behaviour to amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) [199,200]. The emitted luminescence is multiply scattered by the particles and illuminates particles containing excited luminescent centres, thereby amplifying the luminescence by stimulated emission. Two factors are important, first that the transition probabilities and laser irradiance are conducive to population inversion; and second that the multiple scattering between particles provides optical feedback and serves to increase the optical path length [201]. The occurrence of ASE then depends on the particle size distribution, particle arrangement and packing density [199]. This inherent inhomogeneity of the packed bed leads to the random lasing behaviour. In comparison, lasing action is presumed very unlikely within single particles acting as a cavity, because the primary particle size is of the order of or (in this case) shorter than the light wavelength; or in dilute dispersions, because of the low solid angle subtended between individual particles.

Another problem may be laser-induced damage of the phosphor material. In the same experiment a ZnO powder stack was then subjected to fluences in excess of $100 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ for several hundred laser shots and then left for several minutes to allow any heat buildup to dissipate. Afterwards the powder was visibly discoloured and the emission intensity using a lower fluence was reduced by a factor 4–5, indicating permanent damage possibly caused by cumulative heat buildup. While the influence of laser-induced damage or lasing action does depend on the phosphor (for example, no such

Fig. 24. Time series of the luminescence emission spectrum of bulk ZnO powder following pulsed excitation at a fluence of $17 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$.

behaviour was observed for BAM:Eu²⁺ for approximately the same range of fluence), these experiments indicate that obtaining spectra free of these types of interference may be difficult in bulk powder. Besides laser induced heating, degradation, and amplified spontaneous emission, it should be noted that heating bulk powder in a furnace for extended periods (1 h) at high temperatures (1000 K) can alter the crystalline structure of the powder, in turn degrading or improving the luminescence characteristics. This additional and potentially prominent hysteresis effect in bulk powder must be checked after the phosphor has cooled back to room temperature. Further discussion may be found in Section 4.4.3.

To summarise, reliable measurements from dispersed particles are not only needed to properly evaluate signals from thermographic phosphors. They may also be required to avoid complications specific to the study of bulk powder that prevent the quantitative transfer of information from powder studies to the fluid-phase. Therefore, methods are required to characterise dilute particle dispersions, where the nature of the laser-particle interaction much better matches the intended use for fluid flow experiments.

4.3.2. Dispersed particle methods

There are several approaches to studying dilute dispersions of particles. One may isolate single or a few particles using acoustic waves or an electromagnetic field, or cast particles in a transparent solid of some kind. Such methods would be attractive in that physical (size, shape) and luminescence properties could be correlated for individual particles, providing very detailed fundamental information. Particles can also be dispersed in a single droplet. In Ref. [27] La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ particles were mixed with distilled water in a ratio 1% (by mass) and droplets with an initial diameter of approximately 2 mm were suspended in an acoustic levitator. Although droplet heating during initial levitation, non-uniform particle distribution within the droplet, motion/rotation of the droplet and droplet evaporation were all mentioned in this study, if these processes were well-controlled then this method could be used to probe a few particles. Interestingly, when the droplets completely evaporated, Ref. [28] reported that particles remained suspended, so for a low enough initial mass loading of the droplets, single particles could potentially be studied in the gas phase without a liquid carrier.

On the other hand, the process is time consuming to obtain significant statistics relevant to a batch of phosphor and signal levels may be low in relation to standard spectroscopic approaches described above. Two approaches that have been used to characterise phosphor particles for flow thermometry in larger fluid volumes are now described, suspension in liquids, and particle-gas streams (aerosols).

Liquids

Adding a known mass of particles to a small quantity (10's ml) of liquid is one approach to study dispersed particles. Either luminescence spectra or lifetime can be measured as described above, or the luminescence signal measured for a given mass using a two-colour system.

A simple liquid characterisation method is to probe dispersions contained in a cuvette or similar [15,38]. Both of the cited studies found that ultrasonic dispersion was necessary to remove agglomerates. Both also found that the number density of particles was not constant in time, where either the particles sedimented at the bottom of the tank (even with continuous ultrasonic agitation) [38], or appeared to be attracted to the walls of the 30 ml fused silica cuvette used in Ref. [15] (even with continuous stirring after initial dispersion by ultrasound). The latter study proposes the use of a container with a larger volume to surface ratio or a recirculation system to improve the certainty in the mass of particles contributing to the measured luminescence signal.

Using this approach only a small amount (milligrams) of powder is required compared to seeding particles into gas flows (see below), making the comparison of the signal levels from many different dispersed phosphor powders a simple matter. However, the temperature range is inherently limited with water or oils.

Gases

For the characterisation of particles dispersed in the gas phase, the number of particles in the probe volume must be measured for two reasons. First, the inherent difficulties in seeding μm -size particles into gas flows means that the rate of entrainment of particles into the gas stream cannot be set and maintained over long enough periods of time. The luminescence signal is coupled to these variations in the seeding density. Thus some method of accounting for these variations is required, to independently assess the luminescence signal when parameters such as the excitation fluence are varied.

Second, as mentioned previously, if measurements in the gas phase are to be used to compare two phosphors, it is necessary to have an idea of how many particles are needed for a successful measurement. In contrast to liquid studies where the initial mass of particles is controlled, in gases this is not so. The operation of seeders (see Section 3.2.1) is such that large volumes of powder are needed for the process of entrainment, but the rate of entrainment is comparatively very low and a significant portion of particles stick to pipes so it is not possible to weigh the mass of particles which made their way to the test section. Instead the number of particles in the fluid must be measured.

On the one hand, this additional diagnostic increases experimental complexity and furthermore normally larger (100 g) quantities of powders are needed for the seeders ordinarily used for gas flows. On the other hand, measuring in gases is a prerequisite to study dispersed particles at high temperatures and to examine the effect of different bath gases for short time scales. Knowledge of the particle number density has the additional benefit that the luminescence signal per particle is determined, which is more relevant to fundamental studies of laser-particle interaction because potentially, using quantum efficiency data from the literature, the absorption cross section can be derived. Note that by itself the mass concentration, which can be measured in liquid phase studies, may not be reliably related to the particle number density because the particle morphology, state of agglomeration and size distribution are not known with sufficient certainty.

Particle counting

A particle counting system was developed by Fond et al. [51]. Only a brief overview of the main considerations are outlined here. The system is based on laser-sheet illumination and high-resolution imaging of the particle Mie scattering signal. It basically uses the same hardware as for a PIV experiment, with a thin (100–200 μm) light sheet and camera equipped with imaging optics to facilitate a high resolution to resolve closely spaced particles (the measured spatial resolution of our systems used in, e.g., Refs. [13–15,51] is approximately 10 to 15 μm). Mie scattering images may then be processed using a program that determines the number of local maxima in each image, serving as a measure of the number of particles. To determine the particle number density, the laser sheet thickness must be measured. The reader is referred to the original article for details of this system [51].

The goal is to detect all the particles in the measurement volume defined by the light sheet and camera field of view. The laser pulse energy must be so that the peak intensities of weak particle scattering signals are sufficiently beyond the noise floor of the camera, though it should be noted that it may be difficult to detect all of the very smallest particles amongst a given size distribution. Though the size, shape and orientation of the particles affect the scattering

cross-section, for spherical particles, for example, the scattering cross-section at 90° is only a weak function of particle diameter between 500 nm and 3 μm . Therefore, particles in this size range can be detected with equivalent certainty. The counting system should be optimised i.e. by controlling the laser fluence, camera dynamic range, and considering the particle image size and the camera field of view; in order to specify the maximum number density that can be measured. For example, a particle counting system is also described by Lee et al. [16]. These Mie scattering images recorded for PIV were used for counting purposes, which has the advantage of experimental simplicity. The field of view of the camera was therefore matched to that of the thermometry system and the laser sheet thickness was between 450 and 700 μm . This has the drawback that an order of magnitude less particles can be counted. The cutoff threshold of 500 counts that was used to process the scattering images may indicate that in this case small particles were excluded from the number of particles counted. A system based on Mie scattering at 355 nm and an intensified CCD is also mentioned in Ref. [186]. We also refer to a method derived from an LDV system, for example Ref. [176]. By extracting the fraction of time $\sum_i t_i/T$ that particles are inside the LDV probe volume $\pi r^2 L$, the particle number density can be estimated at a fixed point in the flow using:

$$N_p = \frac{\sum_i t_i/T}{\pi r^2 L} \quad (10)$$

A comparison of these different approaches and harmonisation of the methods are important to compare future work by various research groups.

The counting method of Ref. [51] has several advantages, foremost that it is simple: the same hardware as for a generic temperature-velocity imaging experiment is needed, and so some basic tests of a new phosphor can be made quickly and with little effort. One can easily compensate for fluctuating seeding levels which would otherwise obscure possible trends of interest. Also, the number density and luminescence signals can be evaluated from the same particles in time and space, as opposed to using an additional LDV probe or an extinction based technique. As an example, the system was used to sample the luminescence intensity of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles for a fixed excitation laser fluence in a jet of air [51]. Fig. 25 shows a 10 Hz time series of the luminescence intensity before and after correction with the simultaneously measured particle number density. Before correction, the signal fluctuates due to the variable seeding density; after correction, the fluctuations are strongly reduced. Therefore the variation of the signal due to the variation of

Fig. 25. 10 Hz time series of the luminescence signal of BAM:Eu particles seeded into a jet of air, for a fixed excitation fluence. Data is shown before and after correcting for the instantaneous seeding density. Reproduced from Ref. [51].

another parameter such as the excitation laser fluence can then be clearly discerned.

Most important is that the method does not just account for seeding fluctuations in a relative sense, but provides a quantitative measure of the particle number density. For a given batch of phosphor, the number of photons emitted by a single, “average” phosphor particle can be determined, for known excitation parameters. This quantity can also be determined using the thermographic LDV probe [21] since it directly measures luminescence intensity of individual particles. However, due to the cw excitation, only lower range of fluence ($\sim 10 \text{ mJ/cm}^2$), and a low range of irradiance ($\sim 100 \text{ W/cm}^2$) can be investigated, which cannot be readily related to studies with pulse laser excitation.

Note that once the luminescence intensity per particle is quantified, if in an actual thermometry experiment one operates within the conditions the phosphor has been characterised (in terms of excitation fluence and temperature) and knows the imaging and camera parameters of the system well, the recorded luminescence intensity can be used as a measure of the seeding density, to determine, for example, whether the flow is reasonably seeded. This approach can also be used to calibrate the Mie scattering intensity of the PIV images at room temperature, to then in turn use the PIV images themselves as a 2D measure of the seeding density for unknown conditions (see Ref. [17]).

4.3.3. Additional diagnostics

Lastly, of course additional characterisation methods deserve a mention. In the context of fluid thermometry it is necessary to determine the particle size distribution using laser diffraction and Coulter counter methods, the latter method providing the distribution of volume-equivalent spheres. It is important to recognise the limitations of these methods imposed by irregularly shaped particles. Qualitative information about the particle morphology may be obtained using SEM imaging. SEM images of BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO particles are shown on Fig. 8. The crystal structure may be examined using X-ray diffraction. Thermal properties can be measured using a variety of techniques for example differential scanning calorimetry for the heat capacity (again being mindful of the difficulties related to the study of inhomogeneous powders). Though invaluable, these diagnostics are beyond the scope of this review and the reader might wish to refer to books on particle technology and materials characterisation.

4.4. Phosphor particle studies

This section illustrates various applications of the previously-introduced systems to quantitatively characterise the phosphor particles listed in Table 1, in the context of fluid temperature measurements.

4.4.1. Luminescence signal

One of the primary goals is to benchmark phosphors to establish how many particles are needed for temperature measurements, that is, to provide a sufficient signal for an adequate temperature precision. The previously discussed luminescence imaging and particle counting system was first used to probe 2.4 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles seeded into an air flow [51]. It was shown that the recorded luminescence signal was a linear function of the seeding density in the tested range 10^{10} – 2×10^{11} particles/ m^3 . The cited paper was novel in establishing the particle number density to generate sufficient luminescence signal to achieve a certain single-shot, pixel-to-pixel temperature precision. At room temperature, a precision of $\pm 12 \text{ K}$ ($\pm 1\sigma$, 4% of the absolute temperature) at a spatial resolution of 600 μm can be achieved with BAM:Eu²⁺ at 2×10^{11} particles/ m^3 and using pulsed (10 ns) 355 nm excitation at a fluence of 23 mJ/cm^2 . Knowledge of the absolute particle number density

Fig. 26. Unfiltered luminescence signal of seeded ZnO (96479, Sigma-Aldrich) and BAM:Eu²⁺ (KEMK63/UF-P2, Phosphor Technology, UK) particles recorded using pulsed (10 ns) 355 nm excitation at a fluence of 50 mJ/cm², in air at 296 K. Each datapoint is the average luminescence intensity of a single laser shot. Reproduced from Ref. [14] with permission from the Optical Society of America.

made it possible to evaluate for example that in these conditions, the particles have a negligible effect on the bulk gas properties, as discussed in Section 5.8.

Following from this work, detailed studies of two phosphors BAM:Eu²⁺ [13] and ZnO [14] ensued. Fig. 26 shows the relative signal from these two phosphors as a function of particle number density. A procedure outlined in Ref. [13] accounts for laser sheet thickness, objective lens collection efficiency, filter transmission and camera parameters (ADC conversion, chip quantum efficiency, (binned) pixel size) and field of view in the evaluation of the luminescence emission intensity on per particle basis. One reason for the development of this procedure is to facilitate comparison of particle characterisation experiments conducted with completely different setups, so the signals plotted in Fig. 26 are representative of the total luminescence emission of the dispersed particles. The aforementioned linear behaviour of signal with particle number density is evident.

Each of these phosphors has a somewhat different morphology as revealed by SEM imaging, as shown on Fig. 8. The BAM:Eu²⁺ particles are hexagonal disc-type shapes [13], with a median diameter based on volume of 2.4 μm as measured using a Coulter counter by the manufacturer. Images of the ZnO particles reveal ~200 nm primary particles in the form of 1–2 μm agglomerates [14]. Though the projected size is similar, the exact distribution of size and shape is unknown, as are the absorption coefficients and quantum efficiencies. Nevertheless, by the counting measurements the luminescence signal in the gas phase could then be compared for the same level of particle seeding, indicating that for practical measurements the signal is in a similar range for both phosphors. Consequently, for filters which integrate a similar fraction of the total luminescence intensity the single-shot, pixel-to-pixel precision of the recorded intensity ratio images is the same. However, comparing the spectra in Figs. 7 and 9, quite evidently the spectral shift of ZnO is more pronounced than that of BAM:Eu²⁺ for the same temperature difference, so the temperature sensitivity is higher, as shown in Fig. 27. As a consequence, it was demonstrated that a threefold improvement in the temperature precision could be achieved for the same particle number density, laser fluence, collection efficiency and final spatial resolution. These results exemplify the need to compare measured luminescence signals (and temperature precision) for the same seeding density.

Also, the procedure in Ref. [13] permits calculation of the number of photons emitted by a single particle. BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO particles in air produce ~3 × 10⁶ photons/particle using pulsed (10 ns) 355 nm excitation at fluences ~20 mJ/cm² (the value of fluence is not critical due to saturation of the luminescence signal, see below).

Fig. 27. Temperature calibration curves and sensitivity for ZnO and BAM:Eu²⁺. Calibration data for ZnO is derived from flow measurements in the heated gas; for BAM:Eu²⁺, intensity ratios were extracted from digitally-integrated luminescence spectra (from Ref. [19]). A fit (of the form $a + bIR^c$) to the datapoints is shown. The evaluated sensitivity, based on the fit of intensity ratio to temperature, is plotted in dashed lines and can be read on the right axis. Reproduced from Ref. [14] with permission from the Optical Society of America.

Such absolute measures of the signal are essential to compare results between different experiments or laboratories/research groups, and useful for planning experiments in challenging applications.

In Ref. [15], the same type of ZnO particles (96479, Sigma-Aldrich) were dispersed using ultrasound in deionised water, finding that the same signal is emitted per particle in water and air. For a known mass load, the number of particles was also counted to show that 1 mg of particles in 1 L of water (0.0001% by mass) corresponds to ~5 × 10¹¹ particles/m³. In liquids this mass load of ZnO affords high signal levels and a good precision (± 3 K at 298 K). Miller et al. used a similar mass load of 2.5 mg/L for point measurements using La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ [24]. Relating this to those phosphors listed in Table 1 where some indication of the seeding density was reported, it is surprising to note that mass loads 3–4 orders of magnitude higher (0.1–1%) were reportedly used in liquids [26–29,38,42,172]. In fact, Ref. [171] used 10%. This could be due to a non-optimised experimental setup for example weak excitation, poor collection efficiency, detection strategy; or it could be because the phosphors used have poor absorption and a low quantum efficiency, or a long lifetime where a short exposure must be used to freeze a fast-moving flow. Note that useful information on the probable room temperature relative intensity of the phosphors in Table 1 can be established just by considering the luminescence spectra and lifetime. For La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺, the ⁵D₂ line used for lifetime-based thermometry emits only ~0.3% of the total luminescence emission at 300 K, due to quenching via the low lying charge transfer state to the ⁵D₁ and ⁵D₀ levels [202]. For Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Pr³⁺, most of the emission is via the allowed 4f5d–4f luminescence not used for thermometry, as shown on the corresponding emission spectrum of Fig. 4. Clearly, it is not favourable that much of the absorbed excitation energy is lost to transitions not used for thermometry, but this is by no means a complete picture and highlights that further investigations are required to determine the relative signal level of dispersed particles at room temperature.

In addition to BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO, there are many gas phase studies using YAG:Dy³⁺ as evidenced by Table 1. The stated reason is normally to achieve measurements at flame temperatures, and historically the basis for using this phosphor is because luminescence signals in packed powder in a furnace have been obtained at nearly 2000 K [30]. However there are only a few studies which provide information about the signal, either as an estimate or relative measure.

Ref. [49] estimates the number of photons for a 1.7 μm YAG:Dy³⁺ particle as 2 × 10⁶ at room temperature, albeit using a very high fluence of 1.5 J/cm² at 355 nm. This value, adjusted for temperature, was found to be consistent with measurements in a flame, where

the number of particles was estimated using a calibrated scattering technique. Presuming this value is correct, for reasonable exposure times in turbulent flows (e.g. 15 μs as used for YAG:Dy³⁺ in Ref. [178]) the signal level at room temperature would be 1–2% of that from BAM:Eu²⁺ for the same seeding density and presuming the entire 440–500 nm luminescence band of YAG:Dy³⁺ is detected. The luminescence of a known number of dispersed YAG:Dy³⁺,Er³⁺ particles was investigated in a recent study [186], but no quantification of the luminescence intensity per particle was reported.

Facing a lack of signal with this phosphor, in several studies the authors chose an alternative phosphor, and offered some comparison. Jordan and Rothamer compared YAG:Dy³⁺ particles with YAG:Pr³⁺ particles, presumably of the same grade (1.8 μm), finding that (using a 50 μs exposure) the YAG:Pr³⁺ signals were a factor 60 and 230 \times higher than those of YAG:Dy³⁺ for the strongest and weakest channels respectively [46]. The study of Lawrence et al. concluded that 10.2 μm YAG:Dy³⁺ particles produce a high enough signal for average temperature measurements up to 850 K in a jet of air, but 2.5 μm particles do not. 2.9 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles, however, were found to produce sufficient signal for single shot measurements and were recommended [35]. However, unfortunately these assessments were not compared for a known seeding density.

Ref. [38] provides two interesting findings derived from experiments where the mass load of dispersed particles was kept constant. First, it was shown that the time integrated emission of YAG:Dy³⁺ was ~ 20 times weaker than YVO₄:Eu³⁺, a result to be expected since the absorption through the YVO₄ host is more efficient than the forbidden 4f-4f transition of dysprosium in the YAG host. Second, the luminescence emission of YAG:Dy³⁺ particles with diameter < 50 nm was weaker than YAG:Dy³⁺ particles of the order 1 μm . Results like these raise interesting questions related to host-dopant combinations or composition; or for example whether the particle luminescence depends on the square (i.e. surface area) or cube (i.e. volume) of the particle diameter. This study is also notable for its use of rare-earth doped nanoparticles, which are having major impact in fields such as biomedicine [203], optoelectronics including laser sources and solar cells [204], and thermometry at sub- μm -scales [54,55].

4.4.2. Thermal quenching

2.4 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles have been studied in a jet of heated air to study the dependence of the luminescence signal on the temperature [13]. Particle counting was implemented to correct for the seeding density and obtain the curve shown in Fig. 28. The results indicate that at 920 K the luminescence signal per particle is 10% of the room temperature intensity. Ref. [13] also plots the same data

Fig. 28. Normalised luminescence signal for dispersed BAM:Eu²⁺ particles [13] and for ZnO particles [14] in heated jets of air. Data from spectroscopic studies of bulk BAM:Eu²⁺ powder are also plotted, extracted from the spectra in Ref. [13].

per unit volume of gas, which is the relevant parameter for constant pressure experiments. The luminescence intensity is 3% of the room temperature value if the drop in particle number density due to gas thermal expansion is taken into account.

The same data was also recorded in a similar manner, for dispersed ZnO 1–2 μm particles in air [14]. These results, also shown Fig. 28 indicate rather more significant quenching, where at 475 K the signal per particle was reduced to 25% of the room temperature intensity. Characterisation at temperature above 475 K would be useful, as ZnO has a strong temperature sensitivity.

Considering lower temperatures, it should be noted that in general there is no immediate reason why a phosphor should not also be sensitive for at least some part of the temperature range below room temperature, and in fact, depending on the onset of thermal quenching, signal levels may be significantly higher than at room temperature. Spectra for Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ and La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ at 11 K have been measured [205]; La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ was used for surface temperature measurements down to 193 K [206], for example. Spectra of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles down to 217 K were presented as part of a gas turbine film cooling flow study where the phosphor particles were used to measure temperatures in a liquid-N₂-cooled cooling air flow [20]. For ZnO, the temperature dependence of the emission spectrum in the range 10–300 K was measured, illustrating a high temperature sensitivity at least down to 150 K [207].

There is a lack of data on the temperature-dependence of the luminescence emission intensity for the other phosphors listed in Table 1, as dispersed particles. This is especially true for higher temperatures where normally signals are low, but this is the range of interest for flame studies. One issue is that it is not simple to establish stable and uniform gas flows at temperatures beyond 1000 K. Instead, as previously mentioned (and accepting the perhaps large errors stemming from optical interactions between packed particles), one must turn to results taken from bulk powder, as a guide. From using the absolute intensity data from the spectra in Fig. 7 obtained from bulk powder, and applying the appropriate filter curve, the additional curve shown on Fig. 28 results, which qualitatively agrees with the results of gas-phase studies.

Measurements of the luminescence lifetime as a function of temperature can also be used as an approximation of quenching behaviour. The decrease in lifetime is mainly due to an increased non-radiative transition rate, so it is closely linked to the drop in phosphor quantum efficiency. However such an approach has limitations, since the total signal which is of interest is also a function of the absorption probability and overlap of the absorption band with the excitation laser line. Indeed it should be noted that the trends of lifetime and total luminescence emission with temperature do not always agree. BAM:Eu²⁺ is an example: the lifetime starts decreasing only above 600 K [41], whereas the results of Fig. 28 show that the emission intensity has already dropped to 50% at this temperature.

4.4.3. Fluid environment

The luminescence of thermographic phosphors originates from centers within the crystal lattice. Therefore, in principle, a significant advantage is that the luminescence emission is unaffected by the surrounding fluid environment. In general there are two matters at hand: 1) whether the luminescence depends on the local environment i.e. by quenching mechanisms, and 2) whether the particles are affected by exposure to different conditions (for example, extreme temperatures, types of liquid e.g. fuel, etc.), via chemical reactions and/or diffusion. Such changes can be reversible or permanent. Also a distinction should be made between sensitivity of the measured quantity (intensity ratio, lifetime) and/or the total luminescence emission (signal) to the environment.

Two studies have tested the effect of oxygen partial pressure on the luminescence of YAG:Dy³⁺ by placing the powder in a furnace, and changing the bath gas. Feist et al. showed that the oxygen partial

pressure has no effect on the emission lifetime in the tested range 0.21–1 bar [191] while Yu et al. showed that the temperature dependence of emission spectrum is also not affected in the range 0.21 to 1 bar [34]. ZnO:Zn and ZnO:Ga powders were also investigated for O₂ concentrations of 0–100% at pressures up to 4.5 bar and temperatures up to 400 K, revealing no difference in the emission spectra [42]. A study performed in an oxygen-free environment (silicone oil) showed that the luminescence of BAM:Eu²⁺ is insensitive to pressures of up to 1000 bar [208]. The slight dependencies of the luminescence emission of many phosphors at very high pressures (1000's bar) is summarised in Ref. [10]. Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺, La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ and Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ powders were also exposed to a range of gases including N₂, O₂, CO₂, CH₄, He and water vapour at 10 bar, using air as a reference [192]. Temperatures were varied by placing the gas chamber inside a tube furnace. The decay times were measured for the appropriate range of temperature for these phosphors, finding that for Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ and La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ there was no influence of the gas composition or pressure on the decay time.

On the other hand, Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ showed decreasing decay times for increasing O₂ concentration. This was also confirmed by the study of Feist et al. [191]. A recent study attributed this phenomenon to diffusion of oxygen vacancies towards the surrounding oxygen-containing environment [209]. These undesired effects prompted the synthesis of the phosphors Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Eu³⁺ and YAlO₃:Eu³⁺ as alternative phosphors for surface thermometry [162]. Interestingly, in contrast to Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ [192], it was found for Y₃Al₅O₁₂:Eu³⁺ that in a reducing environment the lifetime decreases, which would rule out any effect of oxygen quenching.

In liquids, for La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺, there was no difference in the measured luminescence lifetime between particles dispersed in LiBr solutions and bulk powder [24]; or between particles dispersed in isoctane and when the phosphor was coated on a surface [26]. However for Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ a shift in the luminescence spectrum was noted when the particles were dispersed in water or n-dodecane, corresponding to a temperature difference of 4 K in the intensity ratio calibration curve, which was deemed significant relative to the low shot-to-shot standard deviation of 0.5 K [29]. As already mentioned, the signal of ZnO particles dispersed in water or seeded in air is the same [15].

The duration of the exposure to these environments was at least a few minutes, but the duration may have an influence in these reversible processes, in particular if the process requires diffusion through the solid as it is the case for Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺, which showed a dependence on the O₂ concentration. It is not clear whether the particles would immediately respond to changes in the environment on shorter timescales, encountered for example in a flame.

Oxygen quenching for BAM:Eu²⁺ was investigated by heating a jet of pure N₂ seeded with particles [13]. The results are presented in Fig. 29, indicating no difference in the signal per particle for O₂

partial pressures up to atmospheric conditions. It was also shown that the intensity ratio response is also unaffected by oxygen concentrations in the same range [13]. Together these results mean that with BAM:Eu²⁺ there is no compromise in either the temperature precision (due to decreased signal) or accuracy (altered intensity ratio) of the measurements caused by varying O₂ concentrations.

Permanent changes have also been observed for various phosphors. Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ exposed to temperatures of 1173 K [40] showed a significantly shorter decay time at room temperature than untreated samples. Irreversible changes to the decay time of Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ were observed after changing the absolute air pressure, an effect which is enhanced by increasing the temperature [192]. The thermal degradation of BAM:Eu²⁺ has been investigated in detail because of its significance for the manufacture of plasma display panels. Many studies reported evidence of degradation occurring in BAM:Eu²⁺ powder samples after extended 1 h exposure to temperatures exceeding 770 K [210], conditions typical of display panel manufacture [211]. There are two effects, first that the oxidation state of the europium ions increases from 2+ to 3+, causing a marked and permanent drop in the blue divalent emission and the appearance of the sharp red lines of the trivalent ions (see Refs. [212,213] for a detailed discussion of the use of this response for thermal history sensing). Second, this in turn modifies the crystal field experienced by the remaining divalent ions causing a small shift of the broad blue line [213]. To avoid this effect, in Ref. [13], the spectra of BAM:Eu²⁺ was measured up to 1100 K in a box furnace flushed with N₂. After this treatment, a near negligible difference in the room temperature spectrum (0.1 nm blueshift) was observed.

Such results prompt the question of whether phosphor particles are irreversibly damaged if exposed to extreme temperatures for very short times, which would be typically encountered in flames. In the 2010 study of Yu et al., YAG:Dy³⁺ particles were collected after passing through a 2000 K flame and calibrated to determine if the intensity ratio response was the same as an unexposed YAG:Dy³⁺ sample. The temperature sensitivity was unchanged [34]. Van Lipzig et al. used BAM:Eu²⁺ for temperature imaging in a high pressure combustion chamber, and compared the pre-combustion, room-temperature intensity ratio, with calibration curves obtained from the cooling phase post-combustion (see description in Section 6.3 for more detail). Their results seem to indicate that the intensity ratio remained unchanged after exposure to temperature of nearly 2000 K [37]. This result is consistent with the minor spectral change observed for long exposure times (see Ref. [213]). However, no information was provided on a possible decrease in emission intensity per particle after combustion, which in view of the above-mentioned studies is a more suitable marker of degradation. Unfortunately the Yu et al. study did not compare the luminescence intensity of bulk YAG:Dy³⁺ powder before and after flame exposure either [34].

In a recent study, the luminescence intensity of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles was measured in the post-flame region of a hydrogen non-premixed flame to investigate the survivability [17]. Particles were probed directly in the flow, downstream of the flame after mixing of the (seeded) exhaust gases with ambient air. In this case, it was estimated from the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, that the particles have resided for 0.5–1 s at temperature above 1700 K (up to maximum of 2400 K). The luminescence intensity, temperature and seeding density were measured for regions of the flow containing particles. The result, also shown in Fig. 29, indicates that the luminescence emitted by these particles at temperatures of 500 K matches the luminescence intensity of particles at the same temperature that have not been exposed to flames. These results suggest that BAM:Eu²⁺ particles may be used for measurements downstream of flames, in the exhausts of large combustion facilities, or in cases where exhaust gases are recirculated within the burner

Fig. 29. Normalised luminescence signal for dispersed BAM:Eu²⁺ particles in heated jets of air and nitrogen [13]. The luminescence signal of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles measured in the exhaust gases of an H₂/CH₄ (96.9%/3.1%) diffusion flame [17] are also presented. Reproduced from Ref. [17] with permission from Elsevier.

or trapped in the cylinder of IC engines, as long as the particles are not in this environment for extended periods of time.

To summarise, if a phosphor is unaffected during exposure to a range of conditions for an extended duration (tens of minutes to hours), for example for $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$, one could infer that for short exposures, for example the time between seeding to a gas stream and probing in the test section, the phosphor is also unaffected and can be used without concern about cross-dependencies. On the other hand, to take $\text{BAM}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ as an example, temperatures in the region 900 K unquestionably cause degradation in air over long durations (>30 mins) but this is not an issue if exposed for a short (seconds) duration, as the comparison between dispersed particles in air and in nitrogen indicated.

Since the effect of various processes of diffusion, oxidation, and phase change (and even sublimation and melting) on the temperature measurement must depend on the exposure time, the intended application of a phosphor must be considered. In liquid studies the particles are generally immersed for a long time either in the test object (e.g. convection tank) or before delivery to the test section (e.g. injection rail). An investigation of the longer term effect of specific fuels, e.g., methanol, Jet-A, n-dodecane (as mentioned above in Ref. [29]) would seem warranted. Also, some of these effects might be surface related and in that case smaller particles might be influenced differently. The overall picture, though, is that the touted advantage of thermographic phosphor particles as being robust tracers seems justified. This is a key feature compared with many LIF tracers, which are sensitive to the fluid environment (in particular the oxygen partial pressure), are chemically active and burn in flames.

4.4.4. Laser excitation effects

The excitation process is key to the luminescence emission. The wavelength, linewidth, irradiance and duration of the excitation may influence the luminescence characteristics, for example, emission intensity, spectrum, and rise time and decay time in the case of pulsed excitation.

Luminescence signal

An examination of Table 1 indicates that most studies have used the third or fourth harmonics of pulsed Nd:YAG lasers. These typically have pulse durations of around 8–10 ns, with which it is easy to generate peak powers of the order of MWs and more. While studies have used a wide range of fluence, between $5 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ [14] to more than $3.3 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$ [49], few have reported the variation in the luminescence signal with laser fluence for a given phosphor when the particles are dispersed in a fluid.

The dependence of the luminescence signal of $\text{BAM}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particles on the laser fluence was investigated in a free jet of air using pulsed 355 nm excitation [44,51]. For this study it was necessary to count particles to ensure that fluctuations in the seeding density were accounted for. These results are shown in Fig. 30, revealing that the luminescence signal departs from linear behaviour at around $2\text{--}3 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ and the rate of increase of the signal with laser fluence continuously drops. At a fluence of $400 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ the luminescence intensity was an order of magnitude lower than that expected from linear behaviour [51].

This behaviour was termed “saturation”, and in this review we use the same terminology. Note that the continued rise in signal intensity in the saturation curve might be expected because the “wings” of the Gaussian laser beam are never in the fully saturated regime leading to a component of the signal that always increases. Measurements with a homogenised “top hat” laser beam would be useful in this respect. This is also true for studies of bulk powder, where the excitation fluence depends on the position in the bulk powder, and the laser penetrates further into the bulk powder with increasing fluence [44].

Fig. 30. Luminescence intensity of dispersed $\text{BAM}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particles as a function of 355 nm laser fluence, normalised to the intensity at $10 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$. Inset shows detail in the range $1\text{--}10 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$. Reproduced from Ref. [51].

With the aim of increasing the signal, subsequent works examined the reasons for the saturation behaviour [13]. Ground-state depletion of the active ions was identified as a consistent hypothesis to examine. Europium ions reside in different sites within the BAM crystal lattice [214], with the consequence that the ions have site-dependent absorption characteristics. Following the theory of Ref. [214], 266 nm and 355 nm excitations were compared, with the aim of targeting europium ions residing in different sites. For this, the narrow-linewidth excitation of a pulsed Nd:YAG laser ($< 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used. In addition, to test the possibility that narrow-linewidth excitation only targets ions under the influence of a specific crystal field, excitation using a broadband dye laser with a bandwidth of 200 cm^{-1} at 376 nm was also tested. However, neither of these approaches altered the saturation behaviour [13]. Regarding the comparison of narrowband 266 and 355 nm excitation, either both wavelengths in fact target the same site, or the europium population is the same for each site.

The dependence of the emission intensity on excitation irradiance was also studied for ZnO in air and in water, also showing evidence of saturation [14,15]. 266 nm excitation was also investigated with the original motivation to avoid the Raman scattering from water which neatly overlaps the ZnO emission spectrum if using 355 nm [15]. The signal is a factor two lower using 266 nm excitation, which agrees with the excitation spectrum which was also measured in that study using a low-irradiance source (xenon lamp and monochromator).

A consequence of the saturation observed for $\text{BAM}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ and ZnO is that no significant gain can be achieved by simply increasing the laser fluence, at least for the excitation parameters tested. This may not be true for other phosphors, for example a fluence of $500 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ was used to excite $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Yb}^{3+}$ [45], and $1.5 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$ for $\text{YAG}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$ [49]. An increase in luminescence signal by a factor 16 when the laser fluence was only increased by a factor 5 between 20 and $100 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ was reported for $\text{YAG}:\text{Dy}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}$ [186]. Disregarding this latter, potentially erroneous result, it is possible that these phosphors do not show saturation at these fluences, which is an important consideration when comparing signal levels between phosphors. On the other hand, that sufficient signal for a good temperature precision can be achieved with $\text{BAM}:\text{Eu}^{2+}$ and ZnO at fluences $\sim 10 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ means that high-speed diode-pumped Nd:YAG lasers, with pulse energies nearly two orders of magnitude lower, can be used for kHz-rate temperature imaging as in Refs. [19,20].

These studies of dispersed particles are also important to characterise phosphors and understand where gains in signal might be made. Excitation scans at high laser fluences using, for example, a dye laser or OPO, may be different from the low power density excitation spectra examples shown in Fig. 4. The tests described here with different excitation wavelengths and linewidths are only a start. Though useful for achieving temporal resolution, extremely high laser irradiance with ns pulsed lasers may be a significant factor in saturation behaviour because the photon arrival rate is so high relative to processes of relaxation (luminescence) or internal energy transfer between excited states of the luminescent centres.

Using lasers with longer pulse durations, say that generated with a pulse stretcher (which are employed to prevent laser-induced breakdown in diagnostic situations where high-energy ns pulses are used, for example, for spontaneous Raman scattering [215], or CARS [216]), may be fruitful to study the effect of irradiance and increase the luminescence signal.

Luminescence spectrum and lifetime

It is clearly preferable if the luminescence spectrum and lifetime are independent of the excitation irradiance. Note that in a temperature measurement situation, excitation will be performed with the laser with a fixed wavelength and bandwidth but the laser irradiance may change. In normal experiments, the excitation irradiance varies spatially due to the laser beam profile and may fluctuate temporally or spatially. The review of Allison & Gillies in 1997 already remarked that “there is evidence for a decrease in fluorescence decay time with increasing laser fluence” [10]. This was reported, for example, for $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$ powder samples and coatings at room temperature and 855 K using a 355 nm Nd:YAG laser at a 10 Hz repetition rate [40] and $\text{Mg}_2\text{TiO}_4:\text{Mn}^{4+}$ coatings at room temperature using a 266 nm diode-pumped Nd:YAG laser at a 6 kHz repetition rate [217]. In the latter article this effect is attributed to laser-induced heating caused by the high average power of the high-speed laser.

Luminescence emission spectra from 4.2 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ phosphor particles dispersed in a free flow of air at ambient conditions, were recorded as a function of 355 nm laser fluence by Lindén et al. in 2009 [50]. They detected the luminescence signal using a spectrometer coupled to an intensified CCD camera. Over the range 0.1 J/cm² to 1.5 J/cm², no measurable difference in the luminescence spectrum or the intensity ratio derived from two spectral bands (400 ± 20 nm and 456 ± 5 nm) could be ascertained. It was reported that a fluence of 10 J/cm², however, caused laser-induced breakdown. Ref. [46] observed a similar behaviour for YAG:Pr³⁺ and YAG:Dy³⁺ particles. Later, again in a free flow of ambient air, our group studied 2.4 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles using a two-camera system to evaluate the effect of the laser fluence on the intensity ratio up to 400 mJ/cm² [13]. Contrary to the Lindén study and previously reported results of our own [44], a slight dependence of the intensity ratio on the fluence was observed up to ~200 mJ/cm², beyond which the dependence was weak. By converting this intensity ratio difference into an assumed temperature difference using calibration data, the variation over this range of fluence, if uncorrected, amounts to approximately 50 K. Another study of dispersed BAM:Eu²⁺ particles in air found a 5% increase in the intensity ratio from ~10–80 mJ/cm² at 295 K, which can be translated to ~5 K, but no detectable increase over the same fluence range if the air was heated to 615 K [16]. The study acknowledges that measurements with lower uncertainties are needed and we agree that this is probably the reason for the aforementioned discrepancies in the various findings. Similar issues were also noted in a study of YAG:Dy,Er particles [186]. Regardless, the functional temperature range of BAM:Eu²⁺ spans 200–900 K and so relative to this, these small sources of error can be reduced with simple corrective procedures as discussed in Section 5.6.

Fig. 31. Effect of the laser fluence on the intensity ratio of ZnO particles in a free jet of air at room temperature for 355 nm excitation and pulse durations of 10 and 170 ns. Reproduced from Ref. [14] with permission from the Optical Society of America.

The other phosphor that has been applied for fluid temperature measurements and investigated in this respect is ZnO. The particles have been studied in air using pulsed 355 nm excitation with two different pulse durations (10 and 170 ns) [14]. The results are reproduced in Fig. 31. Using 10 ns excitation the intensity ratio of ZnO is considerably more sensitive than for BAM:Eu²⁺, a result confirmed by Fan et al. [185]. Converting the intensity ratio difference between 5 and 60 mJ/cm² into an assumed temperature difference using calibration data indicates a 100 K difference. This prompted a detailed examination of the intensity ratio-laser fluence dependence for ZnO particles at different temperatures [14], to confirm the universal applicability of corrective procedures to extract temperature field measurements.

Some investigations of the origin of the intensity ratio dependence of ZnO were conducted [14]. Laser-induced particle heating was identified as a plausible explanation for the intensity ratio increase. Another possibility is that the high irradiance (MW/cm²) generated with pulsed laser excitation has an effect on the luminescence emission independent of heating. Fig. 31 also shows data measured in the same study for the same total pulse energy but significantly longer pulse duration (170 ns), generated using an intracavity frequency-tripled diode-pumped Nd:YAG laser. At a given fluence, a lower intensity ratio was observed with the longer excitation pulse duration, from which it was inferred that part of the intensity ratio increase with fluence can be attributed to the excitation irradiance only. This is consistent with a redshift of the ZnO emission caused by a decrease in the band gap with increasing density of excited luminescent centres in the material [201].

5. Uncertainty analysis

In this section, possible measurement error sources related to the use of phosphor particles in flows are considered. These are classified as a temperature measurement uncertainty (precision and accuracy) or in some cases, it is more straightforward to quantify the error in terms of loss of temporal resolution (instantaneous measurement duration) or spatial resolution (measurement probe volume). Generally only the temperature measurement is considered, because the velocity measurement is ordinarily based on well-established techniques (PIV, LDV), for which error analysis has been described elsewhere in the literature. Only a short overview of the particle velocity tracing response is given for comparison.

In the following, random uncertainties which affect the precision of single shot measurements that can be reduced by statistical averaging, for example detector noise, are distinguished from other sources of systematic error which may affect both single shot measurement and average measurements, for example calibration errors.

5.1. Random uncertainty

The effect of random noise on the temperature measurement depends on the emission intensity of the phosphor particles, the collection and conversion efficiency of the detection system, the detector noise characteristics, the temperature sensitivity of the method and phosphor used, and the temporal and spatial resolution. For all approaches where in the probe volume there are several particles that contribute to a single measurement, the random noise also depends on the particle number density. With knowledge of the appropriate parameters the random error can be predicted. For example, the model presented in Ref. [13] was used to compare the precision of intensity ratio measurements using BAM:Eu²⁺ particles and the predicted error. The comparison showed that the photon sampling noise contributes to more than 50% of the measurement precision. The addition of a fixed error term (independent of the seeding density) was proposed to account for the remainder [13]. For conventional intensity ratio imaging this remaining error might stem from residual displacement between the two particle images. Actually, if the number of particles is increased the intensity field becomes more homogeneous, and so the remaining error contribution may be better modelled as an inverse function of the seeding density. On the other hand, for thermographic LDV, measurements are performed on single particles and the seeding density does not affect the random uncertainty.

An accurate model for random measurement uncertainty can be used to decide whether measurements in a specific situation are feasible, e.g., much larger field of view, improved spatial resolution, different laser fluence, for a given seeding density, and particularly at higher temperatures, as done in Ref. [13] for BAM:Eu²⁺. It enables the theoretical comparison of different detectors, and, since an optimum filter combination is a compromise of signal level and temperature sensitivity, the selection of appropriate filters. Also, to compare a set of temperature measurements acquired with phosphor particles to other measurements or simulations, the theoretical precision can be evaluated, and provided as an estimate of the minimum uncertainty.

5.2. Particle tracing properties

The technique is based on the luminescence emission of solid particles entrained in the flow, and it is the temperature and the velocity of the particles that are measured. Any slip or temperature difference between the particles and the surrounding fluid are sources of measurement error. The tracing abilities of phosphor particles are addressed in the following.

5.2.1. Temperature response

To evaluate the temperature response, a typical approach is to consider a cold particle which is initially surrounded by a warmer fluid, and analyse the evolution of the particle temperature over time. This is representative of instantaneous heating, e.g. a particle crossing a flame front. For the particle to match the fluid temperature, heat must be transferred from the fluid to the particle. In addressing this heat transfer problem in the context of flow thermometry using particle tracers, initial studies either considered heat convection to the particles using a Nusselt number correlation [31,39], or that the surface of the particle was initially at the gas temperature and analysed the heat conduction within the particle [34]. In 2012, two heat transfer analyses were provided independently by van Lipzig et al. [37] and by our group [44]. Both recognised that even for relatively high slip between the fluid and the micron-size particles, owing to the low Reynolds number of the particles, the dominant mode of heat transfer is by conduction. Also it was observed that the thermal conductivity of phosphor particles (in

the range 10–30 W/m · K) is orders of magnitude larger than that of the fluid, and that the temperature of the particle can be considered uniform while the fluid locally changes temperature. The change in the particle temperature is therefore limited by conduction heat transfer through the fluid.

Determining the temperature response of a particle consists of solving the heat conduction equation in the fluid phase (without heat generation):

$$\rho_f c_{p,f} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_f \nabla T) \quad (11)$$

Considering a spherical particle in a semi-infinite fluid, the equation reduces to the one-dimensional time-dependent heat conduction equation:

$$\rho_f c_{p,f} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(k_f r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \quad (12)$$

which for uniform thermal properties gives :

$$\frac{1}{\alpha_f} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha_f = k_f / \rho_f c_{p,f}$ is the thermal diffusivity of the fluid. The assumption of uniform particle temperature translates into a zero-dimensional time-dependent energy equation for the particle:

$$m_p c_{p,p} \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = q_{cond} = 4\pi R^2 k_f \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R} \quad (14)$$

In Eqs. (11)–(14), c_p is the specific heat capacity, k is the thermal conductivity, m the mass, r the radial coordinate, ρ the density and R the particle radius. Subscripts f and p refer to fluid and particle respectively.

Different solutions to this problem have been implemented. First, Konopliv and Sparrow had previously provided an analytical solution to Eq. (12) for constant (and uniform) fluid thermal properties [218]. Second, our group solved for Eq. (12) using a finite-difference numerical model. The advantage of this approach is that it can account for local (temperature-dependent) fluid thermal properties, as well as incorporate the effect of radiation from the particles to the surroundings. This model was validated against results of the Konopliv and Sparrow solution for uniform fluid thermal properties [44]. Finally, in a lumped capacitance approach, van Lipzig et al. [37] assumed

$$m_p c_{p,p} \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = hA(T_{f0} - T_p) \quad (15)$$

with

$$Nu = h \frac{R}{k_f} = 2. \quad (16)$$

h is the heat transfer coefficient, A the area, Nu the Nusselt number and T_{f0} the initial temperature of the semi-infinite fluid domain. This textbook $Nu = 2$ solution is simply the solution of Eq. (12), neglecting the time dependent term on the left-hand side, which simplifies to:

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dT}{dr} \right) = 0 \quad (17)$$

with $T = T_p$ at $r = R$ and $T = T_{f0}$ at $r = \infty$. An attractive feature of this approach is that it provides a simple expression for the dimensionless particle temperature:

$$\theta_p = \frac{T_p - T_{f0}}{T_{p0} - T_{f0}} = e^{-t/\tau_T} \quad (18)$$

where T_{p0} is the initial particle temperature and

$$\tau_T = \frac{\rho_p c_{p,p} d_p^2}{12k_f}. \quad (19)$$

Table 2

Temperature response times for 2 μm spherical phosphor particles in air initially at 2000 K. The gas thermal properties are constant and evaluated at 2000 K, the heat capacity and density are those of a YAG particle ($c_{p,p} = 622.1 \text{ J/kg} \cdot \text{K}$, $\rho_p = 4.55 \text{ g/cm}^3$) [149].

Model	$t_{95\%}$ (μs)
Lumped capacitance (Eq. (19))	26.9
Konopliv and Sparrow [218]	26.9
Finite difference [44]	26.9

The response time is proportional to d_p^2 . For uniform fluid thermal properties, in air at 2000 K, the 3τ 95% response time calculated by all three approaches are in excellent agreement, as shown in Table 2 for an undoped YAG crystal. This indicates that neglecting the time-dependent term as in Eq. (17) is a valid assumption, owing to the low volumetric heat capacity of air (and gases in general).

However, for large temperature ranges, e.g. across a flame front, the change in thermal properties of the fluid cannot be neglected. Since the thermal conductivity of air increases from $26 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$ to more than $100 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$ from 300 to 2000 K, the question arises: which value of the fluid thermal conductivity should be used in Eq. (19)? In this case, as heat is transferred from the gas to the particle, the temperature in the vicinity of the particle will cool down, which will reduce its conductivity and therefore slows the heat transfer [44]. Van Lipzig et al. evaluated the fluid thermal conductivity at the initial particle temperature of 300 K [37]. Using the numerical model, it is possible to vary the fluid thermal properties in time and space (distance r from the particle) as a consequence of the local temperature. The numerical model was also adapted to account for radiation assuming the particle as a pure blackbody ($\varepsilon = 1$) [44].

The results of the numerical model are compared to those of the lumped capacitance approach for the thermal conductivity evaluated both at the initial particle temperature and at the fluid temperature in Table 3. Using the cold thermal conductivity overestimates the response time by a factor 3. Using the hot thermal conductivity value results in a slight underestimate of $t_{95\%}$ (-24%). This result supports the use of Eq. (19) as a simple estimation of the particle response time, with the recommendation that the thermal conductivity is evaluated at the initial fluid temperature.

Note that, because Eq. (19) is independent of the step difference in the fluid temperature that is imposed on the particle, the result on the second line of Table 3 may be used as a guide for the response time for a particle undergoing a small temperature change around 300 K.

Radiation was shown to play very little role, even at 2000 K, with the response time hardly changing and the final particle temperature being only 10 K lower than the initial fluid temperature [44]. For μm -size particles, the heat gained or lost by radiation is rapidly balanced by heat conduction from the fluid. A consequence of this in combustion is that the influence of radiation from the flame on particles in the cold reactants is largely unimportant. This is a

Table 3

Temperature response times for 2 μm YAG particles in air initially at 2000 K for different treatments of the gas thermal properties. Note that the result at $T_{eval} = 300 \text{ K}$ is representative of the response time of a particle undergoing a small temperature change around 300 K.

Model	T_{eval} (K) ^a	$t_{95\%}$ (μs)
Finite difference [44]	variable	35.0
Lumped capacitance (Eq. (19))	300	108.0
Lumped capacitance (Eq. (19))	2000	26.8

^a Temperature at which k_f is evaluated

particularly important result were thermographic phosphor particles used as flame front marker, as suggested in Ref. [219].

The thermal conductivity of liquids is typically an order of magnitude higher than in gases, so broadly speaking larger particles can be used for an equivalent response time. The same numerical model was used by our group to assess the response time of 5 μm ZnO particles in water [15]. Between 273 and 373 K, the 95% response time is $< 35 \mu\text{s}$. The thermal diffusivity of liquids is several orders of magnitude smaller than in gases. Because the lumped capacitance approach neglects the time-dependent term, even for fixed fluid thermal properties, there is an error which increases with decreasing thermal diffusivity. For comparison, at 293 K the response time evaluated by Eq. (19) is 29.5 μs compared to 33.1 μs (-12%) for the numerical model [44] and the analytical solution [218].

Volume-equivalent non-spherical particles also have a faster temperature response time than their spherical counterparts [220]. For example, in a film cooling study using phosphor particles [20], the analysis of Wadewitz and Specht [220] was used to evaluate response time of oblate spheroid BAM:Eu particles with a volume-equivalent diameter of 2.4 μm . In air at 300 K, the 95% response times ranged between 99 and 143 μs for aspect ratios between 0.1 (a flat disc-shaped particle) and 1 (a perfect sphere). Although the response time is likewise faster because of the increased ratio of surface area to volume, obtaining a realistic estimate of the response time of the ZnO particles used in Refs. [14,15] is more difficult. Fig. 8 indicates that the ZnO particles are agglomerates comprised of several $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$ particles. Therefore, the thermal lag of particles should be measured in well defined flows. For example, the work described in Ref. [221] used oblique shocks to determine the velocity response time of PIV tracer particles in the time domain. A turbulent jet with well-characterised energy spectrum could also be used as a test in the frequency domain.

5.2.2. Velocity response

For the velocity response time the particle equation of motion has to be solved, generally assuming a spherical particle. The particle Reynolds number $Re_p = \rho_f U_s d_p / \mu_f$ (where U is the velocity, $U_s = U_p - U_f$ is the slip velocity between the particles and the fluid, d_p is the particle diameter and μ_f is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid) is an important governing parameter. In air, water and many other fluids, Re_p is below 1 for slip velocities up to 0.1 m/s and particles in the μm diameter size range. Then in the viscous regime, Stokes' drag law applies and the drag force is $F_D = -3\pi\mu_f d_p U_s$. (If the initial slip velocity is very high the drag force would be larger than that predicted by this expression in which case the following calculated response times would actually be overestimated [56]). Then, the equation of motion may be used in two ways. One, the time-independent slip velocity in a quiescent fluid, termed the settling velocity $U_t = (\rho_p - \rho_f)gd_p^2/18\mu_f$, can be derived. This is useful to determine the lower limit range of velocities that can be accurately measured. The settling velocity is below 1 mm/s for 2 μm particles in air, and two orders of magnitude lower in water.

Two, the particle response time can be determined. Often the analysis in the literature imposes a sudden acceleration i.e. a step change in the fluid velocity to yield a particle velocity response time. In gases, it can be assumed that $\rho_p \gg \rho_f$ and so terms with ρ_f are dropped in the equation of motion to yield [60]:

$$\tau_U = \frac{\rho_p d_p^2}{18\mu_f} \quad (20)$$

The quadratic dependence on the particle diameter makes this the most important parameter for the tracing ability of phosphor particles.

In air at 293 K a spherical phosphor particle 2 μm in diameter with a density of 4 g/cm^3 has a 95% response time of 150 μs . The

question of flow tracing is the same as for solid particles typically used as PIV tracers e.g. Al_2O_3 or TiO_2 , and for this some analyses use the frequency of the turbulent velocity fluctuations to determine the appropriate particle size [56,57]. Generally particles $\sim 2\text{--}3\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter are acceptable to track fluctuations around 1 kHz [56]. Smaller particles are needed for accurate second order statistics in very turbulent flows or high speed flows with extreme velocity gradients. For further useful information the reader is referred to experiments and DNS of PIV particles in turbulent premixed flames [222] and measurements of the particle response times across shocks [221].

In liquids it can be assumed instead that $\rho_p \approx \rho_f$ with the only effect on the response time of Eq. (20) being that the factor is increased to 1/12. This is of minor significance, as typically the response times in liquids are very short because of their dynamic viscosity. That of particles in water, for example, is ~ 2 orders of magnitude lower than in air. For a spherical phosphor particle $5\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, also assuming a density of $4\ \text{g}/\text{cm}^3$, the $3\tau_U$ (95%) response time is $25\ \mu\text{s}$ in water at 293 K. The constraints on particle diameter are considerably relaxed for velocity tracing in liquids.

Two things should be noted. First, because as the gas viscosity increases with temperature, at higher temperatures the response times significantly improve e.g. $d_p = 2\ \mu\text{m}$, $\rho_p = 4\ \text{g}/\text{cm}^3$, $3\tau_U = 67\ \mu\text{s}$ at 1150 K. (Though less critical, in liquids the decrease in viscosity with temperature has the opposite effect). Second, normally phosphor particles are certainly not perfect spheres, as shown by the SEM images (Fig. 8). When the fluid accelerates and there is significant slip, such particles, especially flat disc-shaped particles e.g. as for BAM:Eu, will tend to align so the long axis of the particle is perpendicular to the flow. In comparison to a volume-equivalent sphere, the drag force increases relative to the particle inertia. Therefore these response times may be considered a conservative estimate of the velocity tracing response.

5.3. Detector related errors

Besides the contribution to the random error, the detectors may affect the measurement accuracy due to instability in the detector offset signal and non-linearity in the detector response to incoming light.

Detector offset

Most detectors exhibit some sort of inherent offset signal, for example the image recorded by a camera in the absence of incident light commonly known as the dark image. In theory, this offset can be subtracted in an ordinary background subtraction performed before or after a measurement sequence. However, in a phosphor particle characterisation study using CCD cameras, offset variations during a recording sequence (especially during the first frames of a recording) and variations between recording sequences were observed even after the cameras were turned on and the chip cooling temperature was stable. It was calculated that these offset changes would lead to a significant temperature error at low light levels [13]. Therefore the measurement accuracy may be compromised, even when the noise characteristics of the sensor are suitable for very precise measurements. The same study proposed a simple dynamic background subtraction procedure (see Ref. [13] for details), which is especially useful for accurate temperature measurements or obtaining phosphor characterisation data (for example performing a parameter variation) at low light levels. Different instruments must be checked as necessary: for example in an intensity ratio imaging experiment using high-speed CMOS sensors it was found that the offset was adequately stable if the cameras were powered on for an extended period of time [19].

Detector linearity

Similarly, detector linearity information may not be available from the manufacturer, or only specified over a limited range of operation outside of which the detector is still useful for precise measurements. Extending the useful range by means of linearity characterisation is therefore necessary.

For non-intensified cameras, varying the exposure time for a fixed radiant flux may not be a suitable approach for the evaluation of camera linearity due to the charge accumulation during the read-out process as mentioned in Section 3.2.3. The calibrated light source in integrating sphere systems generally operates continuously, so that the offset level can only be determined after turning the light off. Offset fluctuations may occur, which as discussed may cause a lack of repeatability in the measured linearity response.

Instead, in Ref. [13], the linearity response of CCD cameras was determined using an integrating sphere and a light source that was the luminescence emission of a BAM:Eu²⁺ phosphor pellet following laser excitation at constant pulse energy, which was monitored with a silicon photodiode. This arrangement covered a suitable range of irradiance on the chip during the short exposure time used in the actual measurements, and permitted implementation of the dynamic background subtraction procedure described above. This approach served as a nonlinearity correction, extending the use of the cameras outside the manufacturers tested operation range and into a low light regime where the cameras could be used to produce accurate phosphor characterisation data. As an alternative the linearity can be checked (but not corrected for) without a reference detector for the photon flux, by confirming that the intensity ratio for a given phosphor does not change for increasing signal levels. However, it may be difficult to change the photon flux without affecting the spectral signature of the light. For instance, increasing the laser fluence on the phosphor, or decreasing the camera aperture are unsuitable as they may affect the emission spectrum of the phosphor or the transmission spectrum of the filters (via the angular dependence). As an example of a different method used in this context, Van Lipzig et al. measured the intensity ratio of suspended BAM:Eu²⁺ particles using intensified cameras, while they were settling in a fixed-volume chamber [37], causing the detected intensity to drop. Thus the linearity could be checked, but in this case it must be assumed that the particle size does not affect the emission spectrum.

5.4. Background interference

Any signal which is not laser-induced luminescence from phosphor particles in the probe volume is referred to as the background. Background signals lead to increased random uncertainty, even when it is possible to correctly evaluate and subtract the background signal; or impaired measurement accuracy, if the background cannot be accurately removed.

Background that is not generated by the laser can be of various natures such as ambient light, flame luminosity or radiation from hot surfaces. It is proportional to the effective exposure time of the camera (refer to Section 3.2.3 on effective exposure). The magnitude of the background and its unsteadiness are easily evaluated by turning the laser off. In turbulent reactive flows, a fluctuating flame luminosity may be an issue, as was the case in homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) [32,33] and Diesel engine [43] studies using the YAG:Dy³⁺ phosphor. Near the onset of combustion, measurements were not possible. Therefore careful attention must be paid to the choice of filters to minimise the overlap with the flame emission spectrum. A reduction in the effective exposure time can also be obtained using intensified cameras. Naturally, in this situation, it is essential to use a phosphor with a short lifetime such as BAM:Eu²⁺ ($1\ \mu\text{s}$) or ZnO ($< 1\ \text{ns}$), to allow short exposures without loss in signal.

Background caused by the laser includes elastic scattering from particles and surfaces, Raman scattering from liquids, fluorescence from gaseous species (e.g. fuel, other tracers, radical species, photo-dissociated fragments etc), from walls and windows, and finally luminescence from particles deposited on surfaces. Elastic scattering can be removed using filters with appropriate optical density. The other sources of background can be evaluated by removing particles from the flow, which in some cases is difficult, for example in large liquid tanks, but otherwise just requires stopping seeding the stream. In several IC engine studies using phosphors, various fast (< 100 ns) fluorescence sources were potentially avoided by delaying the ICCD camera exposure after the laser pulse [31–33,43,47]. This is a useful feature of the persistent luminescence of thermographic phosphors. However for this approach to be effective it is necessary that the lifetime is long enough at the temperature of interest to have sufficient integrated signal for the measurement if the exposure is delayed. In the in-cylinder measurements of Ref. [47], where a glass piston was used for imaging and windows in the liner for laser excitation, it was found that later than 30 crank angle degrees before top dead centre, the window luminescence caused by the proximity to the laser sheet would be unacceptable, restricting the measurement to earlier times. It was reported that luminescence from fused silica interfered significantly less with the measurements than that from sapphire, but still that the signal persisted for 10's μ s. Delayed camera gating cannot remove the luminescence in this case. Phosphors that can be excited using 355 nm are preferred because this should strongly reduce such sources of interference. On the other hand, in liquids Raman scattering may be an issue. In Ref. [15] it was found that Raman scattered 355 nm excitation light, corresponding to the water O-H stretch, overlaps the emission spectrum of the ZnO phosphor used for water temperature imaging. The sub-ns lifetime of ZnO prevented time gating the camera exposure. Instead the excitation wavelength was changed to 266 nm, thereby shifting the interfering Raman signal away from the luminescence emission band.

Methods based on the decay time are relatively insensitive to background interferences if the background does not change during the evaluation time window of the decay time, or the laser-induced background is very short-lived compared to the decay time. In these cases, they can be discriminated against by subtraction of a background determined from data (CMOS frames, PMT signal) prior to the laser pulse, and/or by the decay time fitting procedure.

When particles deposit in high concentrations on windows and walls, they may be excited either directly or via scattered laser light, which can produce very high luminescence signals because the number density of particles is much higher than that in the fluid adjacent to the surface. The point is that this signal cannot be filtered either temporally or spectrally. This is a significant problem for two-colour imaging (but can be moderated using some kind of structured laser illumination, see below), and lifetime measurements because the measured temperature has contribution from both wall and fluid temperature. The wall contribution changes in the course of particle deposition i.e. in time.

In Ref. [20], the aim was to measure mixing between a film cooling flow and a main flow above a surface using BAM:Eu²⁺ particles. It was found that when the laser was propagated perpendicular to that surface and impinged upon it (see Fig. 32), signals originating from particle deposited on the test plate prevented measurements as far as 8 mm from the surface. Note that the light was so bright that simply positioning the camera to remove the offending surface (s) from the field of view was ineffective, and that multiple scattering of strong surface emissions by particles in the flow can be significant too (see also Ref. [18]).

The same particle deposition and subsequent background signal interference problems were reported in a study of liquid fuel injection in a hot air cross-flow using YVO₄:Eu³⁺ particles [172]. This

Fig. 32. Image of surface luminescence from BAM:Eu²⁺ particles deposited downstream of an inclined effusion cooling hole. The laser sheet propagates downward, perpendicular to the test plate surface. The white regions in false colour indicate where the camera was saturated.

study tried different wall surface treatments with limited success, and also noted that discontinuities on the surface e.g. joints, steps lead to increased deposition, presumably due to local flow recirculation. Interfering particle deposition was also reported in IC engines using YAG:Dy³⁺ particles, which was apparently reduced using an SiO₂ nanoparticle coating (see Section 6.3) [43].

Where possible it is much better to avoid exciting deposited particles. For these reasons, in the above-mentioned film cooling study, the laser beam was propagated parallel to the surface (using a periscope arrangement positioned downstream in the flow, see Fig. 59 in Section 6.4) [20]. This resulted in orders of magnitude lower excitation fluence for the deposited particles, allowing interference-free temperature measurements to within 3 mm above the surface.

As stated previously, particles deposit on the surface over time and so surface contributions are by nature transient. Therefore subtracting the background taken after the measurements once the measurements are finished may be associated with large uncertainty. Deposition is a limiting factor for the duration of the measurements (not to mention the ease with which particle seeding can be turned on or off, or surfaces flushed/cleaned), so that in some cases, at low repetition rates, only a few temperature fields can be measured, which ultimately offers poor statistical convergence. In this respect, high-speed measurements (e.g. [19,20]) are extremely valuable, providing thousands of images during a second, and accumulation of a large amount of statistics before deposition becomes a problem. The thermographic LDV probe is also very useful in this regard, since the continuous background from the particles deposited on surfaces and excited by the cw laser can be distinguished from the short (~ 10 's μ s) luminescence burst when a particle traverses the probe volume [21].

In general, methods to reduce or eliminate particle deposition in the first place, or prevent them from emitting luminescence once deposited, would be immensely useful. Otherwise, "structured laser illumination planar imaging" (SLIPI) [223] can be used for the evaluation and removal of the surface luminescence. The general principle of structured illumination is to impart some spatially-modulated structure to the laser light sheet. Several sub-images are recorded in which the spatial phase is shifted, either on an average or single-shot basis. Signal (particle luminescence in this case) originating from the measurement plane preserves the spatial modulation, whereas multiply scattered light does not. The image that is reconstructed from subtraction of sub images with one another thereby recovers the signal of interest.

A two-phase time-averaged approach was used to deal with both the effects of surface luminescence and multiple scattering in a jet in coflow configuration [18]. In the study, the modulated laser sheet intentionally impinged on the nozzle which was partially covered with deposited BAM:Eu particles, causing a large signal adjacent to the nozzle (see Fig. 33 a). In the processed intensity images, the SLIPI reconstruction seemed to considerably reduce the signal close to the

Fig. 33. 2D mean count images of the red luminescence channel for both the conventional (a) and SLIPI reconstruction (b) in the center plane of a jet-coflow configuration. The jet flow is unseeded but heated with the jet core at 187 °C. Statistics based on 50 samples. The laser enters the flow from the left hand side and deliberately impinges on the nozzle. Reproduced from Ref. [18] with permission from Springer. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

surface, as shown on Fig 33 b. However, in other experiments in the same configuration, large errors in the recovered temperature field persisted up to 5 mm from the nozzle. More details of this approach are discussed below (Section 5.5) in the context of multiple scattering between particles. Note that due to the transient nature of the particle deposition, only single shot SLIPI approach [224] with two or three laser pulses appears as a suitable option.

5.5. Seeding density effects

In this section, we explore sources of error which may originate from inhomogeneities in the seeding density and from optical interactions between particles, such as multiple scattering and self absorption. Considering a planar imaging configuration, luminescence from particles in the beam path can be scattered by particles located in front or behind the measurement plane towards the detector as shown in Fig. 34. Alternatively, the excitation light can be scattered by the particles in the beam path, which then excite particles in front or behind the measurement plane, and the subsequent luminescence emission is also imaged by the detector. Both scenarios result in luminescence signal which does not originate from particles in the measurement plane. In the following we review experiments designed to reveal these issues and ways to deal with it. Van Lipzig et al. made measurements inside a 10 cm × 10 cm reaction pressure vessel [37]. A slot was used to define the laser light

Fig. 34. Schematic showing a planar imaging configuration for an unseeded central jet surrounded by a seeded coflow. The solid arrow indicates a possible optical path which leads, by multiple scattering, to the imaging of luminescence from the coflow at the location of the unseeded central jet.

sheet vertically and the vertical profile of the resulting particle luminescence was analysed. This profile appearing broader than the slit width, the authors concluded there was a multiple scattering effect. While it is likely that there was a contribution from multiple scattering in their experiment, in view of the high seeding density (6×10^{11} particles/m³), without imaging the laser profile in the absence of particles (using e.g. a dye cell), it is difficult to separate the contribution of multiple scattering to the light sheet broadening from that caused by optical elements and/or diffraction.

More obvious evidence of this phenomenon can be found in an unseeded jet surrounded by a seeded coflow, as shown in Fig. 34. When the seeding density is increased in the coflow, some luminescence signal may appear in locations that correspond to the unseeded jet. The extent of this multiple scattering phenomenon depends on the emission intensity (per particle) of the phosphor particles in the coflow, the scattering cross-section of the phosphor particles, the extent of the seeded coflow, and the number density of particles. In Lee et al., evidence of this was reported for a central jet and coflow of 16 and 140 mm diameter respectively [16]. As shown in Fig. 35, for a seeding density of 4×10^{10} particles/m³ of 2 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles seeded in the coflow (as measured by the authors using a similar approach to the method described in Section 4), the signal in the unseeded central jet corresponds to 8% of the signal in the coflow.

The consequence is that if the same phosphor particles were also seeded in the central jet to image the temperature in both streams, the signal from the central jet would contain a contribution from the particles in the coflow. Were the temperature between both streams different, the detected signal in the central jet, for example its spectral content (intensity ratio), may be biased toward that of the coflow.

The scaling of this contribution with the seeding density is needed to predict or assess the error in a specific configuration. If extinction of either laser light or particle luminescence is neglected, it can be assumed that the light emitted from particles in the measurement plane (defined by the laser sheet) scales linearly with the seeding density, which agrees with experimental observation described in Section 4. The probability that this luminescence light is re-scattered by a particle also scales linearly with the seeding density (also in the absence of extinction) so that one might expect that, overall, the light which is multiply-scattered scales with the square of the seeding density.

To explore this phenomenon further, in Fig. 36, we present our own findings of an experiment in a similar configuration (unseeded

Fig. 35. Radial profile of imaged luminescence intensity in two detection channels for an unseeded central jet (radius $R = 8$ mm) and a coflow (diameter 140 mm) seeded with 2 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles, 4×10^{10} particles/m³. Reproduced from Ref. [16] with permission from Springer.

Fig. 36. Luminescence intensity measured in 10 mm diameter unseeded nitrogen jet as a function of the seeding density of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles in a surrounding 80 mm diameter coflow. A power law fit is also shown. Data from the authors.

central jet, seeded coflow) with the same phosphor particles (2 μm BAM:Eu²⁺) but with a different geometry: the diameters of the central jet and the coflow were 10 mm and 80 mm respectively. As in Ref. [16], a luminescence signal was recorded in the central jet, and the signal increases with the seeding density, but the dependence is less than quadratic. Also, in this case, for the intensity in the central jet to be 8% of that in the coflow, we calculate that the coflow seeding density has to be 2×10^{12} particles/m³, which is considerably higher than in the Lee study [16]. While the geometry accounts for some of the difference (here a smaller coflow diameter is used), it is possible that differences in the particle counting method is the reason for this discrepancy.

The following reviews investigations aimed at determining the impact of this effect on intensity ratio imaging. In Ref. [16], to limit the error, the authors proposed maintaining a lower seeding density in the coflow than in a central jet, and observed that for a ratio $R_{sd} = n_j/n_c^2$ (with n_j and n_c being the seeding densities in the jet and coflow respectively) greater than 0.5×10^{-10} m³/particles, the intensity ratio measured in the central jet (at 615 K) is only a weak function of seeding density, as shown in Fig. 37 (7.5% change up to 4×10^{-10} m³/particles as estimated from the equation displayed on the figure).

From these results, several matters may be expanded upon. For a fixed level of multiply scattered light, the bias in the measured

Fig. 37. Intensity ratio measured in a central jet at 615 K as a function of the seeding density ratio $R_{sd} = n_j/n_c^2$ (with n_j and n_c being the seeding densities of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles in the jet (16 mm diameter) and coflow (140 mm diameter) respectively). Reproduced from Ref. [16] with permission from Springer.

intensity ratio depends on the intensity of the “direct” luminescence from the imaged particles relative to that multiply scattered light. As the temperature of the heated jet is increased, the luminescence intensity per particle drops due to thermal quenching, so for a fixed seeding density ratio, the contribution from multiple scattering will increase. In that work, the intensity ratio was calibrated as a function of temperature in the flow and for seeding densities fulfilling the criterium above ($R_{sd} > 0.5 \times 10^{-10}$ m³/particles), which includes a contribution from multiple scattering. This approach incurs a slight reduction in the temperature sensitivity and the seeding densities must be kept in the same range for calibration and measurements [16].

An in-situ calibration approach was also used for the film cooling study described in Ref. [20], where it was noted that, since the measurements were performed at 6 kHz, it was possible to maintain a constant particle number density during the 3 s measurement sequences, and between different measurement sequences. Then, as in the Lee study, the in-situ calibration would have in effect compensated for a possible influence of the multiple scattering of luminescence emitted by particles at the main flow temperature on the intensity ratio measured in the jet core. A similar film cooling study using the same phosphor particles observed that the effects of multiple scattering caused the measured jet temperatures to depend on the seeding density, and that this is a particular problem when there is a large difference in the volume of two seeded streams [225]. Inhomogeneities in the seeding density may mean that locally the contribution from multiple scattering is higher. To prevent this, in Ref. [16], areas of the central jet which did not fulfill the criteria of sufficient seeding density (based on Mie scattering images) were removed from the measurement. In jet in coflow experiments where the seeding density in the central jet and coflow are different, due to mixing in the shear layer the seeding density decreases with distance from the jet centreline, and the seeding density ratio criteria is no longer fulfilled. This applies to all experiments with two or more seeded streams. However, the effect of mixing on the seeding density, and therefore on the relative signal contribution, will be convoluted with the temperature dependence of the luminescence intensity per particle. This should be considered when addressing the impact of multiple scattering.

The potential of structured laser illumination (see description of the principle in Section 5.4) to eliminate multiply scattered light in the seeded gas phase was explored in some detail by Zentgraf et al. [18]. The same jet in coflow configuration as described above in the Lee study was used. In this study a direct comparison between conventional imaging and the two-phase SLIPI technique was conducted. There, the same two subsets of data shifted by half a spatial period were exploited, i.e. addition was performed to reproduce conventional imaging, and a subtraction was used for the SLIPI approach. In this case a single pulse laser was used to excite the particles and therefore the sub-image datasets were separately recorded in time by shifting the grating used to impart the structure to the light sheet. However, since the magnitude of the multiple scattering depends on the number of particles, some conditioning had to be applied to extract time-average sub-images for a roughly constant seeding density. This conditioning used a simple filtering applied to the luminescence images to provide an “apparent” particle number density.

The temperature of the central jet was varied, and calibration curves obtained by both approaches were compared for various levels of seeding. As expected, the sensitivity of the technique in the conventional approach is degraded as the coflow seeding density increases because the jet signal is increasingly corrupted by multiply scattered light. On the other hand, calibration curves from the SLIPI subtraction were almost independent of the seeding density i.e. the seeding density ratio criteria described previously for the Lee et al. study [16] may be relaxed. Because of the sinusoidally-modulated

light sheets used in SLIPI, two conditions must be met in order to completely remove multiply scattered light. First is that the signal intensity scales linearly with the excitation intensity, and second that there is no cross-dependency of the intensity ratio on the laser fluence. In view of the findings of Section 4.4.4. regarding the phosphors ZnO and BAM:Eu²⁺, the validity of those two assumptions has to be carefully considered or additional uncertainty in the application of structured illumination may arise.

The investigation using structured illumination also allowed quantification of the contribution of multiple scattering in the seeded coflow itself by comparing the detected signal of the conventional and SLIPI approaches. Images of mean luminescence intensity for the two processing routes are shown in Fig. 33. The contribution of multiple scattering is assessed in two areas denoted 4 and 5 in Fig. 33. In area 5, the contribution of multiple scattering amounts to about 70% of the signal for the seeding conditions of the experiment, while in area 4, which should be free from contribution from surface luminescence, the contribution is still 40%. In this case the source of this light and therefore its spectral content is unclear, which complicates the uncertainty analysis. In both regions, the contributions were found to increase with the seeding level. Note that the magnitude of the “apparent” seeding density evaluated here from luminescence images may differ significantly with respect to that measured using a high-resolution counting method such as that of Ref. [44] (see also Section 4.3.2).

To retain the advantages of single-shot thermometry, clearly a single shot SLIPI approach [224] with two or three laser pulses is preferred. However the Zentgraf study rightly emphasises that even to recover average temperature fields, due to both the fact that the seeding density surely varies in time, and the particle deposition is by nature transient (discussed in the previous section), any realistic integration of SLIPI with planar phosphor thermometry really demands an instantaneous approach. In the Zentgraf study preliminary measurements using a second laser to achieve single-shot two-phase SLIPI are also shown.

Multiple scattering could also decrease the spatial resolution of the measurement, by broadening the light sheet or blurring the images of particles in the measurement plane. To quantify this effect we imaged a USAF 1951 resolution test chart through a 5 cm thick rectangular jet seeded with ZnO particles. For a very high seeding density of 8×10^{12} particles/m³ it was found that although the light was attenuated by ~ 50%, the modulation of line pairs at a frequency of 3.17 pairs/mm was maintained at a satisfactory level of 50%, compared to 60% without particles in the flow. A loss of spatial resolution from imaging through clouds of particles or from broadening of the light sheet therefore appears unlikely. Instead, as discussed above, it would appear that the potential effects of multiple scattering are manifested as a “background” contribution.

Finally, if the excitation and emission spectra of the phosphor particles overlap, re-absorption of luminescence can occur, and the detected spectrum may be dependent on the number density and the optical path through the seeded flow of interest since part of the spectrum will be more absorbed. In addition, the Mie scattering cross section is, albeit weakly, wavelength-dependent, and for particles with a broad emission spectrum, elastic scattering can potentially alter the spectrum of the collected light. For both BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO, there is an overlap in excitation and emission spectrum as shown in Fig. 4. To investigate possible effects, an isothermal jet of air 40 mm in diameter was seeded with BAM:Eu²⁺ particles, and the intensity ratio of particles in the mid-plane was measured while changing the seeding density. Over the range tested (from 0.5 – 2.5×10^{11} particles/m³) no changes were observed [13]. A similar experiment was repeated for ZnO in a 20 mm diameter jet, and over the range tested (up to 6×10^{11} particles/m³), no changes were observed either. The same ZnO particles were investigated in water (again in the midplane of a volume 20 mm deep) with mass

loads corresponding to 2.5×10^{12} particles/m³, with the same result [15]. The Lee study tested this effect in a 16 mm central jet seeded with BAM:Eu²⁺ particles and a 140 mm coflow which was seeded either with BAM:Eu²⁺ or non-luminescent MgO particles [16]. The study was interesting because the jet was heated to 610 K. Because the emission spectrum shifts toward the UV with increasing temperature, there is more overlap between the 610 K emission spectrum and the room temperature excitation spectrum. A difference of 5–10% in the jet intensity ratio for coflow BAM:Eu²⁺ particle number densities up to 10^{11} particles/m³ was observed. However, the authors acknowledge multiple scattering could also be responsible for this, and, despite the thresholding on R_{sd} that was applied, it is not possible to be conclusive about self-absorption at this higher temperature. YAG:Dy³⁺,Er³⁺ particles were tested in the same manner at room temperature, in the midplane of a 37 mm volume, and no changes were observed between 1 and 2×10^{11} particles/m³ [186].

To summarise, for all experiments careful assessment and management of multiple scattering effects are absolutely necessary, which are acute in particular geometries. The temperature range, seeding densities and temperature dependence of the signal per particle all play a role. Our view is that agreement in the counting methods used must be established to ensure the results of the experiments described here are transferable. As it stands, structured laser illumination on a single-shot basis appears a viable means to remove the multiple scattering contribution. The impact very likely depends on the phosphor, therefore, the same experiments must also be repeated for other phosphors, noting too that the relative importance of absorption and scattering depends on the particle size and shape. ZnO must therefore be tested as SEM images show a very different morphology compared to BAM:Eu²⁺ (see Section 2.3).

5.6. Laser fluence effects

In this section, potential errors which may arise from the non-linear dependence of the luminescence intensity on the excitation fluence (saturation) and from the undesirable dependence of the measured luminescence property (intensity ratio, lifetime, phase-shift) on the excitation fluence are analysed. These errors are evaluated in the context of phosphors known to exhibit these phenomena, and the examples are drawn from measurements using the ratio-imaging approach. However the general concepts are broadly applicable, and may prompt studies of other phosphor particles used in other thermometry configurations as required.

As discussed in Section 4, it was observed for two phosphors (ZnO and BAM:Eu²⁺) tested in the gas phase, that the luminescence intensity is not proportional to the laser fluence. A sublinear dependence, characteristic of saturation effects, starts at fluences as low as 10 mJ/cm². In an imaging experiment, due to the limited signal level, it is desirable to operate in the non-linear regime. The consequence is that for a light sheet with a Gaussian spatial intensity distribution, the contribution of low fluence regions at the side of the light sheet to the total luminescence signal increases relative to a linear regime case. This effectively decreases the spatial resolution of the measurement in the out of plane direction. To quantify this effect, a profile of luminescence signal in the out-of-plane direction can be simulated based on laser sheet measurements and the saturation data of the phosphor. In Ref. [20], for a Gaussian light sheet with a mean fluence of 17 mJ/cm², only just inside the saturation regime of the phosphor BAM:Eu²⁺ used, it was found that because of this effect the effective FWHM of the light sheet increased from 900 μm to 1 mm. Operating further into the saturation regime effectively broadens the light sheet. As pointed out in Ref. [16], a beam homogeniser can be used to transform the Gaussian beam profile into a top-hat in the out-of-plane direction, permitting operation at higher fluence without spatial broadening of the probe volume.

Section 4 has also identified that at low fluences there is a dependence of the intensity ratio on the laser fluence for the same two phosphors. Above a certain fluence threshold (~ 50 and ~ 120 mJ/cm² for ZnO and BAM respectively), the intensity ratio was no longer sensitive to the laser fluence and it may seem attractive to operate in that regime. However, the probe volume would be significantly larger than expected for a Gaussian beam, as described above. Also, it is often not possible to reach such high fluences, e.g. if the field of view is large, or for measurements at kHz rates, where normally only a few mJ can be delivered by high-speed lasers.

Therefore in normal cases, one can anticipate that the laser fluence may not be uniform over the entire measurement volume. For reference, when unaccounted for, a 10% change in the fluence corresponds to a 2 K error at 20 mJ/cm² for BAM:Eu²⁺ [13], and a 6 K error at 5 mJ/cm² for ZnO [14] around room temperature. There are various origins for the variation in the laser fluence:

- Steady spatial variations induced by the laser profile and optics used to define the probe volume e.g. a light sheet,
- Fluctuations in the excitation energy e.g. pulse to pulse variation in the overall laser pulse energy,
- Temporal variation in the excitation spatial profile,
- Variations of the excitation fluence of particles located at different positions in the probe volume where there is no measure of particle position e.g. in the out of plane direction within the laser sheet in an imaging experiment.

The first type of variation can in principle be included in the white field correction (as described in Section 3.3.4), by dividing the intensity ratio (or decay time) image by an average intensity ratio (or decay time) image obtained at room temperature where the temperature is uniform. This correction is expressed by Eq. 9 which assumes that the relative change of the intensity ratio with excitation laser fluence is independent of temperature. The validity of this assumption was explored for intensity ratio imaging with ZnO [14,185]. As shown in Fig. 38, the maximum deviation between normalised calibration curves obtained at 5 mJ/cm² and 20 mJ/cm² is 7.2 K at 470 K. In the two-colour ratio imaging experiments of Ref. [14], the light sheet optics formed a sheet that was diverging across the field of view corresponding to fluence variations of 50 and 5% in the horizontal (beam focusing towards its waist) and vertical (diverging) directions. This led to errors of 2.2 and 0.2 K respectively. Since a much larger span of laser fluences (20–213 mJ/cm²) was used in the study of Fan et al., instead a cuvette of fluorescent dye was used to determine the fluence distribution in only one direction, and thereby establish a final calibration function that depended on the laser fluence and temperature [185]. It must be noted that a separate white field correction should still be applied. For BAM:Eu²⁺,

Fig. 39. Dependence of the normalised intensity ratio²⁺ on the laser fluence for BAM:Eu²⁺ particles at temperatures 295 K and 615 K. Reproduced from Ref. [16] with permission from Springer.

as shown in Fig. 39, the normalised change in the ratio from 9 to 40 mJ/cm² is slightly different between 295 K and 615 K, translating into a deviation of 12.5 K in the normalised calibration curves. At a flow temperature of 615 K, a 50% change in fluence around 15 mJ/cm² would lead to an error of 3.2 K. This shows that in practical situations fixed spatial variations in excitation fluence can generally be corrected for, and that the residual error is rather small.

Temporal variations in excitation fluence can be corrected by measuring e.g. the laser pulse energy on a shot to shot basis, using an energy meter, or a photodiode, as applied in Ref. [14].

Correcting for temporal variation in the excitation spatial profile would require recording this e.g. by simultaneously imaging a cuvette filled with a dye solution. Also when a vertical strip of the image is at known temperature, e.g. a turbulent jet and a coflow, frame referencing can be used, a procedure sometimes employed for Rayleigh imaging, see e.g. Refs. [226,227]. Temporal variations in the excitation fluence distribution can also be caused by refractive index inhomogeneities in the fluid itself, or strong lensing effects by droplets, menisci and so forth. Laser sheet “striping” effects are well known difficulties in liquids with strongly non-uniform temperature fields. Phosphors as temperature-sensitive as ZnO, but without any dependence of the emission spectrum on the laser fluence are needed.

If the laser beam is Gaussian, a particle will be illuminated by a different fluence depending on its position within the probe volume e.g. the depth position (z) within a laser light sheet in an imaging experiment. While the particle position in the image plane

Fig. 38. Intensity ratio as a function of temperature for ZnO at fluences of 5, 10, 15 and 20 mJ/cm², through which curves have been fitted to guide the eye. Left: absolute intensity ratio. Right: data normalised at 295 K. Reproduced from Ref. [14] with permission from the Optical Society of America.

(x, y) is known, the z position is not. While dividing by an average ratio image (or decay time image) acquired at room temperature (see above) corrects for the systematic error, it does not correct for the unknown particle z position. However, at relevant seeding densities (e.g. 10^{11} particles/m³) and depending on the spatial resolution and laser sheet thickness (e.g. 600 μm for both), statistically there are many particles (~ 50) in each independent probe volume and so this potential contribution to the single-shot is considered negligible.

5.7. Calibration accuracy

The temperature dependence of the measured quantity (intensity ratio or lifetime) must be established. For the reasons discussed in Section 3.4, this is preferably determined from dispersed particles at various reference temperatures, for example, in-situ. It is necessary to add phosphor to the fluid and control the fluid temperature, which is relatively easy in liquids. A standard approach in gases is to seed phosphor in a stream which is electrically heated and issues from a tube into the ambient. The potential core of the jet in this case offers in principle an extended region at uniform and steady temperature. This prevents temporal and spatial averaging error of the intensity ratio or lifetime, which may not have a linear relationship with temperature.

The reference temperature must be determined from independent physical probes e.g. thermocouples, or another optical method, e.g. CARS thermometer (although there has not been any report of another optical technique being used to determine the reference temperature for phosphor thermometry in fluids). One obvious source of error is the uncertainty in this independent reference temperature measurement. Intrusive probes such as thermocouple or micro-thermistors have high accuracy (a few K or less) in the determination of the temperature of the sensing element (junction or micro-thermistor), which is well documented in the literature. However two types of error can be much more significant when measuring fluid temperatures with such probes, especially gases at high temperatures. First, the probe may be at a different temperature than the fluid, due to heat transfer to or from the sensing element to the probe and surroundings. Second, the presence of the probe may change the temperature of the fluid, either via heat transfer, or through catalytic reactions.

Heat transfer related errors of intrusive thermometers are a well known limitation of this type of sensor [228]. The deviation from the fluid temperature may strongly depend on the probe geometry (exposed junction, insulated, wire/bead diameter and length, nature of support), the probe material (thermal conductivity, emissivity), and the probe surroundings (flow parameters, immersion length into the isothermal region of the flow). For accurate measurements, it is essential to quantify possible errors due to heat transfer. Fortunately often these factors upon which the temperature error depends are simplified, e.g. for very thin probes fully immersed in the fluid. The heat transfer consists of radiation from the wire/sheath (noting that calculating the radiation error considering the junction alone is not appropriate); convection to and from the wire and sheath (noting that if the jet is surrounded by a coflow, additional convection losses between the sheath/wires and the coflow must also be accounted for) and conduction along the length of the probe.

For example, larger probes e.g. the 500 μm diameter thermocouples used in Refs. [16,44] are attractive options since they are rather rigid, and for the intermediate temperatures (up to ~ 700 K) of those studies an error of just a few K is estimated. In comparison, the study in Ref. [13] was performed at significantly higher temperatures (~ 900 K) and a smaller 3 mm immersion depth in the jet. The error with a 500 μm diameter probe would be much higher in this case, due to increased radiation and conduction away from the junction. A

50 μm probe was used instead, which was supported with a ceramic tube.

Catalytic reactions on the thermocouple surface have also been observed in reducing environments, especially in pre-flame regions of premixed flames [229,230], which results in a probe temperature higher than that of the fluid without the probe due to exothermic recombination reactions. In our laboratory we observed such effects in lean premixed hydrogen-air flames, which could potentially be a test case for calibration at intermediate temperatures. Long after the flame blew off and no heat release was observed, the measured thermocouple temperature would still indicate above 700 K. In addition, the indicated temperature would increase with the equivalence ratio. Non-catalytic coatings are available (see studies mentioned above), but they also increase the size of the bead and/or wire, which leads to higher heat transfer errors.

Of course, careful consideration of the reference temperature measurement error also applies to calibrations performed on aggregated powder or phosphor coatings in a furnace, oven, heated plate etc. On the one hand it should be a relatively simpler task to obtain an accurate reference temperature. On the other hand however, it should be noted that since this calibration method may be inherently inaccurate (see Section 3.4), some validation data in the flow is required. The discussion above also applies when independent thermocouple measurements of flow temperatures are used to validate the data.

As with other techniques which require calibration, the quality of the fit, the number of datapoints, and the uncertainty of those points determine the statistical uncertainty of the calibration function. Calibration points beyond the temperature range measured in the actual experiment are also preferred, to avoid bias caused by noisy data around the minimum and maximum calibrated temperatures in the experiment. In general, maximum or mean deviation from the fit are reported, but this does not take into account the number of datapoints.

Finally, another source of calibration error may stem from the white field correction. For the intensity ratio approach, as discussed in Section 3.3.4, a white field correction is necessary, which is generally performed using a ratio image obtained either in an isothermal flow or using a phosphor pellet behind a diffusive screen. It was observed that performing the correction with a light source with a different emission spectrum, e.g. a LED light source does not necessarily correct an isothermal intensity ratio image, because the spatial variation in the spectral transmission function may have a different effect on the intensity ratio between the two channels for each light source [44]. For BAM:Eu²⁺, an LED light source would overestimate the angular dependency due to its sharper spectral features. In principle then, as the emission spectrum of the phosphor changes with temperature, the terms α and β of Eq. (9) may not be independent, and a white field correction must be recorded at various temperatures. In other words, a different temperature calibration must be applied to each pixel. However, for BAM:Eu²⁺, the gradients in the emission spectrum (shown in Fig. 7) are small and do not vary significantly with temperature, so a white field correction performed at room temperature satisfactorily corrected the actual non-isothermal measurements [44]. This effect may require quantification for some combinations of phosphor and imaging configuration, especially where the collection angles are steep.

5.8. Intrusive character of the technique

Although laser diagnostics are by their nature non-intrusive in comparison with bulky physical probes, they may under certain conditions modify the system of interest. For example, the need for optical access may require altering the system boundaries, and the laser may deposit energy on the walls, dissociate reactive molecules, or deposit energy in the fluid via absorbing species or particles etc.

Besides these very general considerations, for this technique solid particles are required, as often used for LDV or PIV. The particles may change the physical properties of the fluid, deposit on walls thereby affecting boundary conditions e.g. heat transfer or the dimensions of confined environments, or damage components especially moving parts, such as piston rings or valves. For example a loss of cylinder sealing caused by a few hours of seeding YAG:Dy³⁺ particles was observed in an IC engine study [32]. For the sake of completeness, in specific reactive environments catalytic effects may be a consideration (but are unlikely because, like normal PIV tracers, thermographic phosphor particles are relatively inert materials), or particles may locally quench the flame by chain termination reaction at the surface. Here, various effects of the particles on the fluid are considered.

The heat capacity is the most straightforward to address. Adding particles adds mass to the system, so for the same heat release, e.g. by chemical reaction, the final fluid temperature may decrease. The presence of the particles acts to increase the volumetric heat capacity of the fluid. Hasegawa et al., for example, reported that the temperature of the in-cylinder gas was decreased by 2% when seeding YAG:Dy³⁺ particles into an IC engine [31], presumably at a very high particle concentration.

The relative change in the volumetric heat capacity of the fluid can be described by:

$$\frac{(\rho c)_{f+p} - (\rho c)_f}{(\rho c)_f} = \frac{\pi N_p c_p \rho_p d_p^3}{6 \rho_f c_f} \quad (21)$$

with ρ being the density, c the specific heat capacity, N_p the number density of particles (particles/m³), d_p the volume-equivalent diameter of the particle. The subscripts f and p designate the gas and particle properties respectively. This calculation requires the specific heat capacity (i.e. heat capacity per unit mass) of the phosphor particles. Using differential scanning calorimetry, we measured the specific heat capacity of BAM:Eu²⁺ powder (KEMK63/UP-P2, Phosphor Technology UK) as 720 J/kg · K at 293 K. Note that since the specific heat capacity per unit mass of the gas and particles are similar, the specific heat capacity as calculated in Ref. [37] does not change, and is not the right measure for this effect. For 2 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles, the increase in the volumetric heat capacity for a seeding density of 2×10^{11} particles/m³ is 0.2% in air at 300 K, and 0.5% at 1100 K [13,51]. While this shows that for moderate seeding densities, the particles have negligible effects on the volumetric heat capacity, there is an obvious limit to seeding many orders of magnitude more particles to compensate for using an inefficient phosphor for example, or to offset the loss of signal with increasing temperature.

The transport properties of the fluid (thermal conductivity, viscosity, and diffusion coefficients) can also be potentially influenced by the presence of particles at high seeding levels. However, as an example, based on particle-fluid thermal conductivity calculations proposed by Maxwell [231] at a seeding density of 2×10^{11} particles/m³, the particles have no effect on the thermal conductivity of the gas due to the very little volume fraction ($\sim 10^{-6}$) they occupy in the fluid [51].

Another possible effect may be radiation losses from particles, which could contribute to a decrease in the fluid temperature. While radiation from the particles were shown to cause only a very small difference between the particle and the fluid, even at 2000 K and considering a pure black body emitter ($\epsilon=1$) (see Section 5.2 and Ref. [44]), the particles can potentially remove energy from the fluid. To quantify this effect, a particle in an insulated volume of fluid the size of the inverse of the seeding density was considered. At 1900 K, and for 10^{11} particles/m³, the rate of cooling is 4 K per ms. This effect should be considered in burners with slow hot recirculation zones. The combined impact of radiative heat loss and gas-particle heat conduction on the extinction limits of more heavily-seeded pre-mixed flames are analytically examined in Ref. [232].

6. Applications

6.1. Measurements in liquids

Temperature measurements at the liquid-gas interface in a vertical falling film absorber

This test-case studied the absorption process in an absorption chiller, often used for cooling where electricity is expensive or if there is a source of waste heat. In such device, the refrigerant is absorbed in a solvent, pumped and later boiled as an alternative to the vapor compression of the basic refrigeration cycle.

In a falling film absorber a lithium bromide brine solvent forms a film falling down a tube into which water vapour (the refrigerant) is absorbed. The absorption process releases heat at the liquid-vapour interface, but if the temperature of the film increases, so does the saturation pressure, with a negative impact on the rate of absorption of the vapour in the film. A flow of coolant on the inside of the tube is used to cool the film, as shown for example in the vertical configuration of Fig. 40, with the aim of maintaining the brine in a subcooled state and maximising the mass of absorbed refrigerant. Advancing the understanding of this complex heat and mass transfer problem is key to improving the capacity of the chiller. Phosphors were first used to measure the temperature at the water-liquid interface along the length of a vertical tube [24,234]. The device consisted of a 1.5 m stainless-steel tube over which the solvent, aqueous lithium bromide, fell as a film, with a coolant flowing in the opposite direction on the inside. The tube was mounted in a glass tube, which was filled with water vapour from the boiler and maintained at a pressure of 1.3 kPa. La₂O₂S:Eu³⁺ particles (5–10 μm in diameter) were added to the solvent, which was circulated in a loop formed of the absorber column, the boiler and a pump.

The hydrodynamics of the falling film were such that rolling waves were formed, and that on average the film was 100 μm thick. The sweeping action of the rolling waves was supposed to keep the phosphor particles at the interface. The particles were illuminated by a nitrogen laser (337 nm, 20 ns pulse) over a 6 mm diameter region, and the luminescence of the ⁵D₂ line at 514 nm was detected with a photomultiplier tube. The lifetime of this line is short (~ 4 μs) and has a high temperature sensitivity ($> 3\%/K$) over the temperature range of this study (40–50 °C). The lifetime is much shorter than the transit time of the particles in the excitation region

Fig. 40. Schematic of a falling film absorber. Reproduced from Ref. [233] with permission from Elsevier.

Fig. 41. Temperature profiles along the running length of the liquid-vapour interface, the wall temperature, and the temperature of the coolant running inside the tube, measured with thermographic phosphors, RTDs and thermocouples respectively. Reproduced from [24] with permission of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers.

(~ 20 ms) due to the film motion ($U = 0.5$ m/s) so particle displacement during the luminescence decay was not a problem.

Preliminary measurements were performed on a heated Petri dish filled with the aqueous LiBr solution with the same concentration (2.5 mg/L) of phosphor. No reaction between the phosphor and the LiBr was observed and the measurements agreed with those performed on powder. Those measurements were used for calibration. An accuracy of 0.5°C was measured by comparing the temperature measured by optical thermometry in the Petri dish to that of a calibrated thermocouple.

The measurement of the falling film in the test stand are presented in Fig. 41. Near the top of the tube, the measured film temperature is 51°C , and as a result of the competing effects of the heat of absorption, and heat transfer to the coolant along the height of the tube, the second being stronger, the temperature at the interface is shown to decrease exponentially to $\sim 43^\circ\text{C}$ 1.4 m below. An agreement within $\pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ between repeated measurements at a given location was observed. In addition, the temperature of the film shortly after entering the absorber as measured with the phosphor (51°C) agreed well with the saturation temperature at the absorber pressure (1.3 kPa) of 50.4°C .

The main difficulties reported in this study was interference from the LiBr solution broadband luminescence, with a persistence of ~ 1 ms, combined with a drop in the concentration of thermographic phosphor particles over time due to particles settling within the absorber loop. This resulted in a degradation of the measurement accuracy in the absorber in comparison to measurements in the Petri dish. Regardless, though this was the earliest study using thermographic phosphors for temperature measurements in fluid flows, it was remarkably successful. Together with a variety of other measurements, the film temperature data were used to derive heat and mass transfer correlations.

Temperature measurement of single droplets and sprays

Spray diagnostics are much needed to improve the modelling of the atomisation and vaporisation processes, which are key to several industries ranging from drug delivery to the lungs to the automotive industry. In internal combustion engines in particular, emission levels are closely related to the optimisation of the fuel spray. Droplet size, velocity and temperature are important parameters in models. While phase Doppler anemometry is widely used to measure the two former quantities, the few diagnostics for droplet temperature, e.g. using dyes, exciplex fluorescence, and rainbow interferometry are less mature. The development of an alternative approach based on phosphor particles is therefore also desirable.

In Ref. [26], the temperature of individual free-falling mm-size water and isoctane droplets were measured using the $^5\text{D}_2$ emission of the phosphor $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ as in the abovementioned falling film study. Phosphor particles (of unspecified diameter) were added to water (1% by weight, three orders of magnitude larger than in the previous study) in a heated tank, from which 4 mm diameter droplets fell into temperature-regulated surrounding air, so in some cases heat transfer between the droplet and the gas during the fall could be minimised. When a droplet crossed the beam of a helium-neon laser, a trigger signal was sent to a pulsed frequency tripled Nd:YAG laser (355 nm, 38 mJ/pulse) with a beam diameter of 10 mm for excitation of the phosphor particles in the whole droplet, as shown in Fig. 42. The decay of the luminescence emission following the laser pulse was detected by a PMT. The decay time was converted to temperature using calibration data obtained from a heated metallic plate coated with the phosphor. To examine the accuracy and precision of the technique, the measured droplet temperature was compared to the temperature of the liquid in the tank measured by a thermocouple.

The droplet-to-droplet precision and deviation from the thermocouple were found to be better than 1 K over the range 295–365 K. Using the same system, measurements were also performed in isoctane droplets. Since the $^5\text{D}_2$ luminescence has a lifetime of several μs , interference from the fast fuel fluorescence can be avoided with a delay in the lifetime evaluation window. At 289 K a precision of 0.34 K and an accuracy of 0.6 K were reported. $5\ \mu\text{m}$ $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ particles and a similar system were also used to measure the temperature decrease in time of acoustically-levitated evaporating droplets [27].

In the same study [26], the feasibility of using the temperature dependent emission spectrum of $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}^{4+}$ for the temperature evaluation was also examined. The same mass fraction of phosphor particles was used, but with 266 nm excitation and the luminescence spectrum was recorded using a spectrometer and an intensified CCD camera. The ratio of the 631 nm and 657 nm lines was measured to infer the droplet temperature using calibration data obtained in a heated cell filled with water/phosphor mixture. Results obtained using both this spectral ratio and the temporal approach using $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ agreed well with modelled droplet temperatures, accounting for heat losses as the droplets fell between the tank and measurement location.

Fig. 42. Experimental setup for the temperature measurement of individual falling droplets. Reproduced from [26] with permission of the Optical Society of America.

The same authors applied the same lifetime thermometry principle to imaging inside 3 mm free falling water droplets using the same phosphor $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$, using a fast framing camera (maximum repetition rate 100 Mhz) [28]. Here a laser sheet (355 nm) was formed and directed towards the middle of the droplet. The gate delay and duration of the 7 independent ICCD cameras were adjusted to cover (in total) approximately 1.5 times the $1/e$ luminescence decay time, with an overlap of 50% between exposures. Following each laser pulse, for each pixel a decay time was fitted to this 7-point time series and converted to temperature, presumably using the calibration data obtained with a coated heated plate and a PMT as described in the previous study [26]. The temperature fields measured in 3 mm droplets falling from a heated liquid reservoir into room temperature air indicated temperature inhomogeneities which according to the authors may be attributed to heat transfer. To assess the accuracy and precision of this approach, measurements were also performed in an isothermally heated liquid container. From comparison with thermocouple measurements, a precision of 0.66 K is reported. The accuracy at 343 K was found to vary from 0.6 to 5 K depending on the choice of timing for the individual ICCD gates.

In sprays found in automotive applications, the diameter of the droplets of interest is often much smaller (10's of μm) than those studied above and the droplet velocity is very high (100's m/s). The same lifetime imaging approach based on $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ was applied to image the temperature distribution in an air-assisted water spray [28]. Here, the water-phosphor mixture was also mixed (0.25% by mass) with a surfactant (Triton X-100) to improve the particle dispersion. Lower temperatures were observed in the inner core of the spray which was attributed to evaporative cooling since neither liquid nor surrounding gas were heated. It is not clear whether it is only the liquid phase temperature or also the gaseous phase which was being measured, but the study described above on a levitated evaporating droplet found that the particles stayed in the droplet during the evaporation process [27], which would support the assumption that mostly the liquid phase temperature is measured. With this approach, displacement over the total 30 μs lifetime evaluation windows led to errors which would be even more significant in high velocity sprays found in internal combustion engines.

To alleviate this issue the authors suggested using the two colour intensity ratio approach, which in principle, for a very fast phosphor, can be made as short as the laser pulse. Brübach et al. presented two-dimensional temperature measurements in n-dodecane sprays using this method [29]. 8 μm $\text{Mg}_4\text{FGeO}_6:\text{Mn}$ phosphor particles was added to n-dodecane at a load of 1–2% by weight. 266 nm excitation was used with an ICCD + image doubler for two colour imaging. The camera exposure was 1 ms with a delay of 1 μs with respect to the laser pulse, to avoid fluorescence from the fuel. Calibration measurements were performed in an optically-accessible liquid tank for which a 0.5 K shot to shot standard deviation was reported. Average temperature images of the spray were presented for different liquid tank temperatures, as expected reflecting an increased spray temperature with increasing liquid tank temperature. One of these average images is shown in Fig. 43. There are some systematic errors

Fig. 43. Temperature map of an n-dodecane spray averaged over 150 single shots for an initial liquid phase temperature of $T=343$ K measured by the thermocouple at the nozzle. The point of origin corresponds to the outlet of the nozzle, false colour is degrees K. Reproduced from Ref. [29] with permission from Springer.

Fig. 44. (a) Falling burning methanol droplet photographed with an ICCD camera. (b) Temperature imaging of a falling burning methanol droplet taken in the middle of the Bunsen burner. The ICCD camera exposure time is 10 ns. Reproduced from [42] with permission of the Optical Society of America.

left-right and top-bottom in the temperature distribution. Also, during the long exposure time required to obtain sufficient signal (1 ms), it was noted that the particles moved much further than the spatial resolution (1.3 mm) so the signal was a temporal average of the luminescence of several phosphor particles passing the respective probe volume.

A phosphor with a much shorter lifetime such as ZnO would be far more suitable. The luminescence lifetime of the 387 nm edge luminescence of ZnO is below a nanosecond, and the emission spectrum is highly sensitive to temperature, permitting application of the intensity ratio method with high temperature sensitivity and short measurement duration. In Ref. [42], 2D temperature measurements were performed in free falling burning mm-size methanol droplets using ZnO:Ga and a similar two colour imaging system (ICCD + image doubler) as described above. A mass load of 0.1% phosphor particles in methanol was used, and as they fell, the droplets were ignited using a bunsen burner. The ICCD gate time was set to 10 ns, overlapping the laser pulse (355 nm, 5 ns, 18 mJ/pulse). Here due to the short lifetime of the luminescence (< 1 ns), a delay cannot be used to avoid fast fluorescence signals induced by the laser e.g. from the fuel. The unfiltered image of the burning droplet without laser illumination and the temperature field measured in the droplet are shown in Fig. 44. In the photograph of the droplet, the strongest flame luminosity can be observed a short distance above the falling droplet. This luminosity was suppressed using a 10 ns ICCD gate time. A uniform temperature distribution can be observed inside the droplet with a standard deviation of 0.8 K. Colder regions may be observed at the top and around the droplet periphery which are indicative of systematic errors, since in principle heat should be transferred from the flame toward the centre of the droplet. The average measured temperature is 2.7 K lower than the boiling temperature of methanol, demonstrating a good level of overall measurement accuracy. According to the authors, it was likely that internal reflection in the droplet caused a loss of spatial resolution. It does seem that a fan-shaped stripe structure originating at the point where the laser sheet intersects the droplet surface is visible, perhaps due to the laser fluence dependence of the intensity ratio for ZnO based phosphors (see below).

Convective flows

Turbulent natural convection occurs in systems of geophysical and astrophysical importance like the atmosphere, oceans, the Earth's mantle and in stars [235], as well as in, for example, the ventilation of buildings and the solidification of metals. These systems are therefore of fundamental interest and are often studied numerically and experimentally. In the laboratory, such flows are frequently investigated in scaled, simpler experiments with well-defined boundary conditions, for example the Rayleigh–Bénard

configuration, i.e. a horizontal layer of fluid bounded by a heated bottom surface and a cooled top surface. In such thermally driven flows the two parameters of primary interest are temperature and velocity. With this aim, as a demonstration the liquid temperature of a buoyant plume was measured using ZnO particles and the two colour imaging approach [15]. 1–2 μm ZnO particles were mixed with water (mass load of 1 mg/L, much lower than in the droplet and spray studies, but similar to that used by Miller et al. [24]). The mixture was placed in a 28 ml (40 x 20 x 35 mm) fused silica cuvette, with a small resistance heating block at the bottom. ZnO can be excited with laser light at 355 nm, but it was found that at this wavelength, the Raman scattering of water interfered with one of the luminescence channels used for thermometry. As in the study above, since the duration of the luminescence signal and laser pulse almost exactly match, the Raman scattering cannot be avoided by delaying the camera exposure. The frequency quadrupled Nd:YAG output at 266 nm was used instead, thereby shifting the Raman signal to a spectral region well-separated from the ZnO emission. An 800 μm thick laser sheet intersected the cuvette and luminescence from the particles was collected and spectrally separated using two non-intensified cameras in a beamsplitter arrangement (see Fig. 2) for an in-plane spatial resolution of 400 μm . The intensity ratio images were converted to temperature using calibration data obtained in a preliminary experiment which consisted of the cuvette without heating block placed on a heated magnetic stirrer plate. This offered a temperature uniformity of 1 K over the 25 to 75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ range. These preliminary measurements were also used to determine the 1- σ precision, which was better than 3 K, and the shot to shot standard deviation of average temperature 1.4 K. The maximum deviation from the fit was 0.6 K.

A time sequence of the temperature field in the cuvette shortly after the resistance heating block is turned on is shown in Fig 45. A plume forms above the heating block and rises upward due to buoyancy. While this approach provides temperature measurements with high spatio-temporal resolution in liquids, as noted above, the well-known issue of laser striping in liquids caused by refractive index gradients can compromise the accuracy of the measurement if the emission spectrum of the phosphor used is laser fluence-dependent, as it is the case for ZnO. Phosphors with a reduced spectral dependence on the laser fluence are therefore required for studies where extensive beam steering may occur.

6.2. Heated air jets

Heated round jets of air were used as reference test cases in most studies aiming to demonstrate different temperature imaging approaches using thermographic phosphor tracer in gaseous flows [14,16,19,21,31,35,39,44–46,53,178].

This configuration was chosen for many reasons, chiefly because it is an open laboratory-scale flow that is simple to build. Secondly

Fig. 45. Evolving temperature field in a water-filled cuvette above a 10 × 10 mm resistance heating block. Only every fifth image of the 10 Hz recording is displayed. A little bubble can be seen rising with the buoyant plume. Reproduced from [15].

the radial and centreline velocity and temperature profiles can be verified at a basic level for respective symmetry, and an initially uniform region followed by a continuous decrease in temperature. Thus systematic errors from the measurement technique can easily be detected. Also, with a few exceptions [21,31,53], in most of these studies the jet velocity and diameter were set to be far in the turbulent jet regime ($Re > 2000$) for which mean and fluctuating components of both velocity and temperature have been measured in specific heated jet configurations over a wide range of spatial locations [236,237]. This allows for qualitative comparisons. In addition, the jet potential core can be used for in situ calibration and assessment of the measurement precision (see Section 3).

Hasegawa et al. seeded a laminar heated jet of air (10 mm diameter, $U \sim 0.8$ m/s, $T = 500$ K) with 4 μm YAG:Dy³⁺ particles [31]. Following excitation with a 355 nm laser sheet, the luminescence from the phosphor particles was detected by a stereoscope and an ICCD camera for two colour imaging, as well as by a photomultiplier tube for point lifetime measurements. Both intensity ratios, and decay times were converted to temperature using data previously obtained from a phosphor paint placed in a temperature controlled cell using a spectrometer and a PMT respectively.

The lifetime of YAG:Dy is ~ 1 ms around 500 K and so the exposure time of the camera was set to 100 μs to provide the necessary signal level; likewise for the decay time measurement the evaluation window has to be on the same order as the lifetime. This would lead to unacceptable level of particle displacement in turbulent flows, but in this study owing to low jet exit velocity this should not be expected to influence the results.

The temperature field measured in the heated jet is shown in Fig. 46, as are the centerline profiles measured by the 0-D lifetime and intensity ratio methods and a thermocouple. Both thermocouple and lifetime method indicate a subtle temperature decay of the jet which is not resolved by the intensity ratio measurement, due to a combination of measurement noise and systematic error that are visible in the temperature image. Both optical methods indicated a higher temperature than the thermocouple, which the authors attributed to heat transfer caused by the thermocouple presence. The authors supply a value of 5% temperature error, which seems to correspond to the mean deviation between the temperature profiles measured from the intensity ratio method and the thermocouple. The agreement between the lifetime method and the thermocouple is good despite the fact that the lifetime of YAG:Dy hardly changes up to 1200 K, i.e. it is barely sensitive to temperature around 500 K [238].

Omrane et al. combined the same detection systems (ICCD and image doubler) and excitation (355 nm) with the phosphor Mg₄FeGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ for measurements in a turbulent heated jet of air (20 mm, $U \sim 10$ m/s) at an exit temperature of 670 K [39]. Adding a PIV laser at 532 nm to illuminate the same particles, while recording the Mie scattering on an additional PIV camera, they performed the first simultaneous flow temperature and velocity measurements using thermographic phosphors. The calibration method and the particle size were not reported. The exposure time is on the order of the luminescence lifetime of 1 ms, leading to a presumed displacement of 10 mm during the integration time.

The average temperature and velocity fields obtained from 50 single shots is shown on Fig. 47. The velocity field is as expected. The temperature field, however, shows high fluctuations (> 150 K) on the left side of the jet which the authors attributed to non-uniform particle seeding. Point measurements were also performed at various locations on the jet centerline using the lifetime approach with a PMT. These indicated a continuous temperature decay from 470 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 430 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ from 10 mm to 55 mm above the tube exit. While this trend seemed qualitatively correct, the accuracy could not be determined because the jet heating system was not regulated, nor was a thermocouple used to measure jet exit temperature. Here, one potential

Fig. 46. Average temperature field in a heated air jet downstream of tube exit measured using YAG:Dy³⁺ tracer particles, $D = 10$ mm is the jet diameter (left), Centreline temperature profile measured using a thermocouple, the 0-D lifetime method and the 2-D intensity ratio method. Reproduced from [31] with permission from Springer.

issue is the large displacement (~ 10 mm) of the particles during the lifetime evaluation window, meaning particles enter or leave the probe volume during that time. It may produce the effect that the signal will decay faster than expected, because of particles which have been excited but which leave the probe volume (so their emission is no longer collected) and particles that enter the probe volume (which do not emit light since they have not been excited by the laser). Here and in general the long integration time needed to match the decay time of Mg₄FeGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ using either lifetime or intensity ratio methods, causes such significant particle displacement for this jet, compromising the measurement accuracy and resolution.

Jordan and Rothamer also measured single shot temperature fields in a turbulent heated jet (8.5 mm, $U \sim 20$ m/s) [45] using $8 \mu\text{m}$ Y₂O₂S:Yb³⁺,Er³⁺ phosphor particles, an upconversion phosphor, which was excited at 980 nm (500 mJ/cm²) using an OPO/OPA system. Unlike the two previous studies which used an image doubler, here the luminescence filtered in the 500–600 nm spectral region was imaged on two ICCD cameras positioned either side of the measurement plane. The exposure time was set to 2 μs to freeze the

flow motion. However it is shorter than the luminescence lifetime of either line ($\sim 50 \mu\text{s}$), meaning only a fraction of the signal was collected. The intensity ratio was converted into temperature using calibration data measured in the jet itself (in situ), which indicated that the temperature sensitivity around room temperature is high, at 1.4%/K, but decreases to 0.7%/K at 423 K.

Single-shot and average measurements were presented at three exit jet temperatures 323 K, 373 K and 423 K. Average measurements only were presented at 473 K due to a lack of signal caused by the strong thermal quenching of the observed luminescence transition. $8 \mu\text{m}$ particles were used, which are too large for measurements in turbulent flows (see tracing analysis in Section 5.2), but it is anticipated that using smaller Y₂O₂S:Yb³⁺,Er³⁺ particles would further reduce the maximum temperature for single shot measurements. Fig 48 shows two single shot measurements together with an average field at a jet exit temperature of 373 K. From the single shot images, a higher temperature in the jet core is observed and the average field is symmetric about the jet centreline, with a visible broadening of the radial temperature profile and a temperature decrease in the streamwise direction. The authors estimated a precision of 5 K at 373 K in a region of the jet where the temperature was presumed nearly uniform, for an in-plane spatial resolution of about 600 μm (estimated from the reported binning and filtering that were used). This study showed considerable promise, as the first to be free of the systematic errors found in the previous heated jet studies.

Simultaneous temperature, velocity and mixture fraction measurements were performed using $2 \mu\text{m}$ BAM:Eu²⁺ particles seeded into heated round jet (8 mm, $U \sim 30$ m/s), surrounded by an 80 mm coflow [44]. The phosphor particles were excited by a UV laser (355 nm, 100 mJ/cm²) and a double-pulse laser (at 532 nm) was

Fig. 47. Average temperature and velocity fields in a heated jet flow compiled from 50 single shots. Reproduced from [39] with permission from Springer.

Fig. 48. Two single shots (left and centre) and the average (right) temperature fields for a jet exit temperature of 373 K. Black pixels indicate a insufficient signal level, e.g. when no particles are present. Compiled from images taken from Ref. [45] with permission from Springer.

Fig. 49. Three instantaneous shots and the time-average temperature and velocity fields for a jet exit temperature of 530 K. Only a fourth of the velocity vectors are plotted for visualisation. Data from the authors.

used for PIV. The luminescence of the particles was detected by two cameras positioned viewing from the same direction using a beamsplitter arrangement (see Fig. 2) for two colour imaging. Unlike the previous imaging studies using phosphors, here non-intensified cameras were used. The phosphor has a $1/e$ lifetime of about $1 \mu\text{s}$ so that a short exposure time of $5 \mu\text{s}$ could be used while still collecting the whole signal. After processing, the in-plane resolution of the measurements were $400 \mu\text{m}$ as determined using an equally smoothed image of a resolution target, matching the laser sheet thicknesses. The intensity ratio was converted to temperature using calibration data performed in the same jet, at various exit temperatures.

Examples of instantaneous superimposed temperature and velocity fields are shown on Fig. 49 at a jet exit temperature of 530 K. White regions corresponds to regions with insufficient signal. Here the co-flow was seeded with non-luminescent Al_2O_3 particles, in order to obtain the velocity field in the whole flow while being able to distinguish between the two streams, so as to visualise the mixture fraction (as described below). In the three instantaneous images, one can clearly distinguish a contorted high temperature and velocity core region, surrounded by colder slower regions where the jet mixes. From one shot to the other, the same region is alternately occupied by hot gas and by slower-moving cold co-flowing gas. The average field clearly indicates the mixing layers which are the result of these individual turbulent flow realisations, as well as the uniform-temperature jet potential core.

To assess the accuracy of the technique, jet temperature profiles were measured by translating a $500 \mu\text{m}$ grounded type-K thermocouple through the flow 15 mm above the tube exit during steady operation. These data were compared to time-averaged temperature profiles extracted at the same vertical position from a single line of independent measurements obtained using the two-colour

Fig. 50. Comparison of horizontal temperature profiles measured with thermographic phosphors and with a type K thermocouple for a jet exit temperature of 530 K. From Ref. [44].

luminescence technique, as shown in Fig. 50. The profiles are evidently symmetrical, and the mean deviation from the thermocouple measurements is 8.5 K (1.6%). The largest deviations are observed in the shear layer away from the jet exit, and are likely to be caused to statistical bias due to the absence of seeding in the co-flow, as discussed in the article. Statistics to determine the single-pixel temperature precision were also gathered from 600 measurements at each steady jet temperature, indicating a precision of 16 K and 33 K at 483 K and 683 K respectively.

By seeding only phosphor into the central jet, and non-luminescent Al_2O_3 particles in the coflow, the concept of utilising the luminescence from the particles themselves to visualise the mixing between the two streams was explored in the same study [44]. The mixture fraction, which is defined at a given spatial position as the mass fraction of gas originating from the central jet, was calculated from the luminescence intensity, normalised to a reference region (in the jet core), and corrected for thermal quenching of the luminescence and for the temperature dependence of the gas density, both using the simultaneously acquired temperature. The simultaneously acquired temperature and mixture fraction field showed good correlation since both quantities are transported by the turbulent flow field, and cooler regions corresponds to region where the two streams mix. However, unlike the intensity ratio approach used for thermometry, this mixture fraction method was dependent on local spatial inhomogeneities in the particle number density, so overall the single pixel precision was 20%.

Several other studies have performed temperature measurements (with or without simultaneous velocimetry) in turbulent heated jets as a validation of the measurement concept, also using BAM:Eu^{2+} but with an ICCD and stereoscope [35], with a double pulse 355 nm laser and a two camera system for simultaneous thermometry and velocimetry [185], or using other phosphors: YAG:Pr^{3+} [46], YAG:Dy^{3+} [35,178], $\text{YAG:Dy}^{3+},\text{Er}^{3+}$ [178], ZnO [14], and $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ [53]. A heated jet was also used to estimate the precision of the thermographic laser Doppler velocimetry concept discussed in Section 3 for simultaneous point measurement of flow temperature and velocity [21,22].

In the following, three particular imaging studies in heated jets are highlighted, one that demonstrated an improved level of temperature measurement precision ($< 1\%$) using the sensitive phosphor ZnO [14]; one that uses a single camera for temperature and velocity measurements [53]; and lastly a study in which the turbulent heat fluxes were extracted from simultaneous temperature and velocity measurements [16].

While high precision in any temperature measurement is almost always desirable, this is particularly important for applications involving subtle temperature differences. Examples include natural convection, heating and cooling of buildings, flows in compression machines, and the cooling of electronic components. As discussed in Section 4.4.1, ZnO particles are inherently more sensitive so the achievable temperature precision at room temperature is improved

Fig. 51. Temperature field in the shear layer of a turbulent jet ($T=363$ K). Left: single shot. Right: average field compiled from 100 single shot images. The x -coordinates are in reference to the jet centerline. From Ref. [14] permission from the Optical Society of America.

by a factor 3 compared to that using BAM:Eu²⁺ particles for the same experimental conditions (seeding density, fluence, spatial resolution). The potential of ZnO phosphor particles was demonstrated in the shear layer of a turbulent heated jet with a temperature difference of 70 K between the jet exit temperature and the coflowing stream [14]. ZnO particles (size 1–2 μm) were seeded into both jet and co-flow streams and a standard measurement system, calibrated in the flow, was used to derive the temperature (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 51 shows a single shot and an average temperature field in the shear layer between the hot jet and the cold coflow. The single-shot shows large vortical structures generated by the shear between the jet and surrounding coflow. The resolution of the measurement is enough to resolve cooler regions within these eddies, caused by the mixing of hot gas and cooler coflowing air. The average temperature field shows the effect of turbulent fluctuations, leading to some broadening of the shear layer. The pixel-to-pixel precision was 4.0 K at 363 K (1.1%), based on a region in the jet core. In terms of accuracy, the deviation with the thermocouple measurement at a reference location is 3.0 K. The deviation of the centerline temperature profile from a constant value was 4.6 K, mainly due to laser fluence inhomogeneities as discussed in Section 4.4.4.

Using a single-camera single-laser approach, Yokomori et al. performed simultaneous temperature and velocity measurements in a laminar heated air jet (8.5 mm, $U \sim 0.5$ m/s) with the phosphor Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ [53]. As in the other studies, the luminescence was spectrally filtered for thermometry using a two-colour approach, but here with a custom-made two colour single camera imaging system (see Fig. 14). Using a fast-phosphor screen intensifier, the camera was exposed twice during the long luminescence decay (~ 1 ms) following the laser pulse, so that the velocity field could be derived from a cross-correlation between the two consecutive particle images recorded on the same half of the chip. The ratio of the luminescence intensity recorded during the first exposure on each half of

the chip was converted to temperature using calibration data obtained from a heated plate coated with the phosphor. The underlying principle is illustrated in Fig. 16 in Section 3. Time-averaged temperature and velocity measurements were presented at five jet exit temperatures from room temperature to 673 K. A subtle centerline temperature and velocity decay were observed from the jet exit to 20 mm downstream due to the laminar nature of the jet. Radial and axial temperature profiles were compared to thermocouple measurements, showing a good agreement. A radial velocity profile for the isothermal case was compared to an analytical solution for the developing jet from a fully developed laminar tube flow which too displayed reasonable agreement. Due to the low seeding density used in this approach, single shot measurements could not be performed.

Experimental data for the turbulent heat flux in well-defined test cases, such as the turbulent round jet are much needed for the refinement of numerical models of turbulent flows based on Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations or large eddy simulations (LES). In the work of Lee et al. [16], simultaneous measurements of temperature and velocity were performed in a heated jet ($d = 16$ mm, $U \sim 20$ – 40 m/s) surrounded by a coflow also using the phosphor BAM:Eu²⁺, in order to evaluate radial and axial turbulent heat fluxes. Non-intensified cameras in a beamsplitter arrangement were used for the detection of luminescence. In order to evaluate the turbulent fluxes without statistical bias, both coflow and central jet were seeded with phosphor particles. In this case, particular attention was paid to minimise interferences from multiple scattering as discussed in Section 5.5. The accuracy of the calibration fit was 4 K. One diameter downstream of the nozzle exit, the average radial temperature profile was compared to thermocouple measurements (500 μm type K), which showed a maximum deviation of 25 K in the shear layer. A single-shot single pixel standard deviation in the jet core at 620 K of 2.9% was reported.

The radial and turbulent fluxes were evaluated from the time-average of the product of the fluctuating components of the radial and axial velocity components and the temperature. The gradient diffusion model, often used in numerical flow simulations, can be expressed for e.g. the radial component:

$$\overline{u'T'} = -\alpha_t \frac{\partial \overline{T}}{\partial r} \quad (22)$$

where u' and T' designate the fluctuating components of the radial velocity and temperature respectively, and the overline designates the temporal average. α_t is the turbulent heat diffusivity. To explore the validity of this model, at various spatial locations, the measured radial turbulent flux was compared to the mean radial temperature gradient. The results, shown in Fig. 52 (left) indicate that in the near field ($x/d = 1$; 4) the relation between both quantities deviates

Fig. 52. Measured radial turbulent flux plotted against mean radial temperature gradient (left) for different axial locations x , and turbulent heat diffusivities α_t , calculated by differentiating second-order polynomial fit through the data for Eq. (22). Open symbols denote $\text{Re} = 6400$ and closed symbols denote $\text{Re} = 12,800$. Reproduced from [16] with permission from Springer.

significantly from linear. The magnitude of the temperature gradient also decreases with distance from the jet exit, as the jet spreads. Polynomials were then fitted to the turbulent heat flux with the mean temperature gradient as the independent variable, to evaluate the turbulent heat diffusivities at various location downstream of the tube exit. The results are shown in Fig. 52 (right). In the near field ($x/d = 1; 4$), the extracted thermal diffusivity varies significantly with radial location, but seems independent of the Reynolds number. Further downstream, the dependence on the radial location is weak, but the turbulent heat diffusivity now scales almost linearly with the Reynolds number. Turbulent heat fluxes were also measured by Schreivogel and co-workers in the film cooling flows described in section 6.4.4. [20]. Both studies demonstrate the wealth of information that can be extracted from simultaneous single shot temperature and velocity imaging for the advancement of turbulent flow models.

6.3. Measurements in internal combustion engines

Some of the earliest examples of gas temperature measurements using phosphor particles were inside optically-accessible IC engines. This is not surprising since IC engines feature a rich variety of in-cylinder processes (spray dynamics, turbulent mixing, near-wall heat and mass transfer, chemistry), that require investigation, towards improving efficiency (fuel economy and CO₂ output) and reducing pollutant emissions (NO_x, unburned hydrocarbons, CO, particulates e.g. soot). These processes are often by nature transient, stochastic and coupled, and are especially critical for advanced combustion technologies such as partially premixed and homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI), direct-injection stratified charge and so forth; and when using alternative fuels e.g. biodiesel, ethanol etc. With this in mind, application of phosphor thermometry to the gas phase as well as on surfaces in IC engines is a key area of development.

Using phosphor particles as a tracer, the first engine studies were of HCCI combustion. Basically, very early injection or port-fuelling generates a lean, homogeneous fuel-air mixture which is compressed to autoignition. It is an attractive combustion concept because of the near negligible NO_x and smoke emissions and high efficiency. However one of several drawbacks is the steep rate of heat release. Actually, it is thermal stratification in the bulk charge caused by wall heat transfer and turbulent mixing that staggers ignition, moderates the heat release rate, and reduces the rate of pressure rise. Therefore, investigations of the temperature (and velocity) field are needed.

The early studies of Hasegawa et al. used the YAG:Dy³⁺ phosphor (4 μm particles) for thermometry only. The particles were seeded into the intake manifold of a 4-valve modified Diesel engine (82.2 × 94 mm bore × stroke) run at 1200 rpm in HCCI mode [31–33]. The engine was port-fuelled (fuel-air equivalence ratio $\phi = 0.27$) with either isooctane [32] or 50/50 isooctane/n-heptane blends [31,33], for which the compression ratio (CR) and intake temperatures were 15.6 and 393 K or 12.2 and 363 K respectively. The laser sheet (355 nm, 80 mJ/pulse) propagated horizontally into the cylinder through a full silica ring and images of the vertical plane were captured using an ICCD and stereoscope for intensity ratio imaging. The laser repetition rate was 10 Hz and measurements were phase-locked to different timings during the cycle.

The temperature calibration was executed in a heated test cell, on a solid metal rod coated with phosphor using ceramic cement. Initial validation in an electrically-heated jet found good agreement between measurements using a type-S thermocouple, the luminescence lifetime, and the intensity ratio methods of 5% error at ~500 K see Section 6.2. The lifetime measurements were used to optimise the gate time in the engine experiments to 100 μs. Also, to

avoid fluorescence and laser Mie scattering a 100 ns laser-camera delay was used.

In the engine experiments, a 2% drop in the temperature was noted when seeding the particles. It was also mentioned that damage to sealing in the engine occurred after a few hours of seeding [32]. Between approximately 10 and 15 crank angle degrees before top dead centre (CAD BTDC), depending on the fuel and operating conditions and 20 CAD after top dead centre (ATDC) reliable results could not be obtained due to background signals caused by chemiluminescence. This was characterised in a separate experiment with no particle seeding, which showed that at 5 CAD BTDC, flame luminosity could be as high as 30% of the luminescence intensity, rendering accurate measurements impossible. Outside these crank angles, good agreement within 5% between the spatial average of the phase averaged temperature field extracted from the imaging results and a mass-averaged thermodynamic calculation based on the cylinder pressure was achieved, as shown in Fig. 53.

Single shot measurements from measurement sequences phase-locked to different crank angles are shown in Fig. 54, for the n-heptane isooctane blend, and CR = 12.2 [31]. Histograms of measured temperatures indicate that at 35 CAD BTDC the mean temperature is 621 K with a deviation of 32.9 K. The authors attribute the spatial variations visible in Fig. 54, not to measurement noise but instead to turbulent transport of low temperature gas from the boundary layers [31]. For the engine running on isooctane with a CR of 15.6 [32], the single shot results were used to correlate the dimensionless temperature deviation against Reynolds number at different engine speeds, finding a linear relationship at crank angles before the onset of combustion. For these operating conditions, measurement could be performed up to 10 CAD BTDC, for which “flame kernels” with a size 1–3 mm were identified with peak temperatures of 1100 K and local temperature gradients up to 300 K/mm. Unburned zones at this crank angle were again attributed to turbulent transport of gases at a lower temperature from the boundary layers. Unfortunately, in these studies velocity measurements were not conducted simultaneously. Though in principle a wealth of information could be extracted from studies like these, two key parameters are missing: 1) there is no indication of the single-shot pixel-to-pixel precision at high temperatures, and so the nature of the temperature inhomogeneities (e.g. as those shown in Fig. 54) cannot be reliably ascertained; and 2) though a geometric spatial resolution of 180 μm is mentioned, it is not clear whether it is based on the projected size of a camera pixel, or from recording images of a resolution target. Note that the engine study of Neal et al. described below reported, using very similar ICCDs and images of a resolution target, a degraded spatial resolution equivalent to 8–12 camera pixels [47]. The reliable identification of fine structures/gradients and

Fig. 53. Calculated temperature and average temperature results evaluated from planar measurements in the HCCI engine, for 50/50 isooctane/n-heptane fuel CR = 12, intake temperature 363 K. Reproduced from Ref. [31] with permission from Springer.

Fig. 54. Single shot temperature images from the studies of Hasegawa et al. operating conditions as in Fig. 53. From Ref [31] with permission from Springer.

temperature inhomogenities calls for thorough validation of the precision and spatial resolution in well-defined test cases.

A detailed understanding of Diesel combustion processes has enabled the reduction of the emissions of these engines, and laser diagnostic techniques have played an important role in investigating the spray, the subsequent vapourisation and mixing of the fuel with ambient air, and ignition and combustion [239]. Phosphor thermometry was used by Takada et al. to investigate Diesel combustion in the same engine as above [43]. The engine was run at 1200 rpm with $CR = 13.2$, the intake temperature was 368 K, and n-heptane or isoctane were used as fuel and injected at 3 CAD BTDC. $4 \mu\text{m}$ BAM:Eu²⁺ or YAG:Dy³⁺ particles were used as a tracer to measure the temperature in the vertical plane through a glass piston bowl geometry as shown in Fig. 55. 355 nm excitation was used for both phosphors, and again an ICCD and stereoscope with appropriate filters for each phosphor was used to detect the luminescence emission for intensity ratio imaging. Note that no results were presented for BAM:Eu²⁺. The same calibration procedure as described above (solid object in test cell) was used.

It was stated that measurements were only possible only up to TDC (3 CAD after the start of injection), again due to intense chemiluminescence from combustion. It was also noted that the phosphor particles stick to walls, causing severe background interference. An SiO₂ nanoparticle coating applied to the particles (see Section 3.2.1) was used to combat this. The evolution of the background signal after stopping seeding YAG:Dy³⁺ particles both with and without this coating was tested, indicating an improvement of the signal to background ratio from 4 to around 6–7. However, it is not clear how repeatable the measurements are, and whether deposition changes for different operating conditions or measurement runs.

Temperature images were obtained using the YAG:Dy³⁺ phosphor for a motored case, where cooler regions were observed, which

Fig. 55. Top: Setup used in the Diesel engine study of Takada et al. [43], showing side view, indicating the expected fuel spray trajectory, piston bowl geometry and laser sheet orientation, and top view. The laser sheet directly passes through the fuel spray. Bottom: Phase-averaged temperature image recorded in a fired Diesel engine using isoctane fuel. The liquid fuel spray location is shown by the dotted line. Reproduced from [43] with permission of Society of Automotive Engineers.

the authors attributed to heat transfer to the piston. Fired results using both fuels were also presented. A six hole injector was used and the laser sheet directly crosses the axis of the fuel jet in the field of view, as shown in Fig. 55. Mie scattering images at 1 CAD BTDC (2 CAD after the start of injection) clearly indicated the presence of liquid fuel, yet at these times temperature data through the whole field could still be determined, as shown in Fig. 55. Presumably, particle seeded air was entrained by the high-velocity fuel jet. Cooler temperatures could be identified in these regions since the fuel temperature is lower. Higher temperatures could be observed in the surrounding gas when using n-heptane, supposedly because the fuel vapour started reacting.

Studying the gas temperature and velocity inside a motored engine is useful to understand the turbulent flow and heat transfer to the cylinder walls. The study of Neal et al. used $1.8 \mu\text{m}$ YAG:Pr³⁺ phosphor particles to measure temperature and velocity fields in a motored optically-accessible small-bore Diesel engine [47]. The engine had a bore \times stroke of 82×76.2 mm and CR 12.3. It was run at 1200 rpm for two different intake temperatures of 383 and 303 K. In this study temperature and velocity in the horizontal plane were measured. The laser sheets (266 nm light for excitation and 532 nm light for PIV) propagated through windows in the cylinder liner. Luminescence and scattering signals were collected through a flat sapphire piston crown and directed towards the detection system

(two ICCD cameras and beamsplitter and PIV camera) using a mirror at 45°. The calibration was performed using the same detection system observing aggregated powder in a furnace, looking through the same sapphire piston cap. During calibration the temperature sensitivity was optimised via the laser-camera delay and exposure times to maximise the intensity ratio sensitivity between 625 and 775 K, as discussed in Section 3.2.3, since this is the temperature range of key interest for this motored engine study.

The bulk gas temperature was calculated using the ideal gas law with input cylinder pressure data and a two-zone method that separately accounts for the bulk gas volume and crevice volume, which is assumed to be at the wall temperature. This estimation was compared to average temperatures using phosphor thermometry data obtained at 10 Hz and phase-locked to different crank angles between 80 and 30 CAD BTDC. A good agreement of 5% was obtained, as shown in Fig. 56. The intensity ratio sensitivity increases with temperature and the particle number density also increases with the cylinder pressure, so the single-shot precision improves to 30 K at a mean bulk temperature of 560 K at 30 CAD BTDC. As stated above, using ICCDs the measured spatial resolution was between 8–12 pixels, corresponding to 0.5 to 1 mm in the object plane. This analysis of single shot temperature precision was performed for a small region of the images where the temperature is expected to be homogeneous. This step is essential to characterise the performance of the measurement technique before it is applied to cases where the fields inside the cylinder will be non-uniform, e.g. as in the above Hasegawa studies [31–33], or for conditions of increased turbulent and wall heat transfer.

Another reason why among the other examples this engine study was especially noteworthy is its wealth of practical considerations. The cylinder head was painted with a low reflectivity silicon-based paint to reduce reflections, as well as being coated with a thin layer of soot from a rich diffusion flame before each measurement run. This is particularly important since in this case the clearance near TDC was very small and the surfaces (piston and cylinder head) were very close to the horizontal plane. The study mentions that the seeding should be sufficient for measurements, but not too much so as to generate high background signals caused by particle deposition, or clog the piston rings. Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were mixed with the YAG:Pr³⁺ particles, yet still, bursts of particles caused by the seeding system reportedly compounded the deposition issue. Deposition led to systematic errors e.g. the valve seats visible in the average temperature images, which masked genuine nonuniformities arising from heat transfer to and from the exhaust and intake valves; and limited the number of images (typically 10–20) that could be

Fig. 56. Calculated temperature and average temperature results evaluated from planar measurements in a motored engine (intake temperature 303 K). Errorbars correspond to $\pm 5\%$ accuracy in the temperature. Reproduced from [47] with permission of Society of Automotive Engineers.

recorded before the background was too strong. Beyond 30 CAD BTDC the results were unreliable, with measured temperatures actually decreasing toward TDC. As discussed in Section 5.4, this was attributed to a long-lived (10's μ s) fluorescence signal from the piston window induced by scattered laser light. Solutions such as excimer laser grade fused silica and narrower interference filter bands were suggested. It should be emphasised that phosphors that can be excited nearer the visible spectral region, at 355 nm for example, are very much preferred to reduce such interference.

4–6 μ m Mg₄FGeO₆:Mn⁴⁺ phosphor particles (also with SiO₂ nanoparticle coating) were used by Someya et al. to study the temperature and velocity distributions in a motored engine [52]. The engine featured a pentroof cylinder head with cylinder dimensions 86 × 86 mm (bore × stroke). Measurements were carried out at 700 and 1500 rpm, intake pressure of 0.38 bar and intake temperature of 326 K. The laser sheet (355 nm) was coupled into the cylinder vertically using a 45° mirror and a glass piston, and the plane was imaged through a sapphire window installed in the liner. The method was the single laser (12.5 Hz repetition rate) and high-speed camera approach for lifetime imaging as described in Section 3.1.2.

Phosphor particles sticking to the wall were mentioned to affect the gas temperatures measured adjacent to the wall, which may be significant here because the laser sheet is dumped onto the cylinder head, causing a lot of scattering. The low repetition rate measurements were phase-locked to crank angles from 60 CAD BTDC to TDC, and average data derived from temperature images were extracted for both engine speeds. Unfortunately there is no comparison with expected in-cylinder gas temperatures. Good precision was obtained at TDC, where temperatures are around 800 K, but as discussed in Section 3.1.2, the precision at all other (lower) temperatures should degrade considerably as the lifetime is longer.

All studies discussed here reported the issue of particle deposition in the confined environments of engine cylinders. Particle deposition occurred over time, and this considerably limited the number of datapoints recorded before the influence of background signals was deemed unacceptable. However, if measurements were recorded at a much faster rate, e.g. at several kHz, then many more datapoints can be recorded during the same time period for a much improved convergence of the data. kHz-rate measurements also permits the tracking of fast transient events, e.g. in the mixture preparation, that can then be correlated to the outcome of each cycle (pressure peak, occurrence of misfire) in an effort to investigate the cause of cycle-to-cycle variations. It is also clear that reference temperature data are of paramount importance, in particular of homogeneous temperature fields, in order to validate the measurements in terms of precision and systematic errors, before applying them for measuring the temperature distributions in the operating mode of interest.

Measurements inside a high pressure gas spray chamber

In the work of van Lipzig et al., temperature measurements were performed inside a high pressure, high temperature fixed volume chamber using the phosphor BAM:Eu²⁺ [37]. The purpose of this work is related to the Premixed Charge Compression Ignition (PCCI) concept, which relies on earlier injection during the compression stroke, which aims at improved mixing of fuel and air than in traditional compression ignition engines for lower NO_x and soot levels, but also maintaining a degree of control over load and combustion phasing. The said spray chamber is used to investigate fuel sprays under engine-like PCCI conditions, thus diagnostics are required to characterise local temperature distributions, which has a strong influence on ignition.

The test case consisted of a cubic optically-accessible combustion chamber, initially filled with a mixture of ethylene, oxygen, nitrogen and argon at a pressure above 10 bar, which was then burned so as to produce, upon cooling of the chamber, the desired temperature,

pressure and density conditions prior to spray injection. 4 μm phosphor particles were seeded into the nitrogen stream early in the filling procedure using a commercial powder injector consisting of a fluidised bed and a venturi tube. Due to the lengthy filling procedure (~ 100 s), settling of the particles caused the number density in the center of the chamber to drop significantly before the post-combustion events of interest, leading to a decrease in the luminescence intensity of approximately 80%. The mixing fan could not be used because it reportedly increased the particle deposition. Suspended particles were excited by a laser light sheet at 355 nm in the vessel mid-plane, and the luminescence was detected by two ICCDs located on opposite sides of the measurement plane. The luminescence images were filtered to a resolution of about 2 mm. After division, the ratio images were converted to temperature data also obtained during the post-combustion cooling phase. During this phase, the mass-averaged temperature in the vessel can be accurately estimated from the vessel pressure using the ideal gas law. A spatially averaged intensity ratio was computed for different times in the cooling phase, and compared to the mass-averaged temperature to form a calibration curve. This post-combustion calibration curve was compared to another spatially averaged datapoint obtained before combustion. Interestingly, the agreement showed that the intensity ratio of the particles was not affected by the combustion event as discussed in Section 4.4.3.

Fig. 57 shows the main results of these measurements. The temperature was evaluated at three vertical locations, one at the center, and two others 30 mm below and above this midpoint. The curves plotted in Fig. 57 are the average over 3 measurement runs. In the cooling phase, measurements were only possible after the local temperature fell below 650 K, due to the thermal quenching of the luminescence emission. Measurements at the top location were only possible even later, presumably due to low seeding density at this location caused by particle settling, which is also confirmed by the higher noise level at this location. At time $t=4$ s, there is a 150 K difference between temperatures evaluated at the top and bottom, which the authors explain by the buoyancy of hot gases. This difference gradually decays and is, within the measurement uncertainty, uniform at $t = 15$ s. The precision is determined from the standard deviation of spatially average measured temperature over repeated experiments, which increases from 30 K at 393 K to 60 K at 650 K. While measurements were successfully performed in this challenging configuration, unfortunately the targeted engine-like conditions for spray injection at higher density and temperature could not be reached. For higher densities, the filling time is longer, and the drop in signal higher, so the seeding density limits the maximum measurable temperature. Improvement in the seeding apparatus allowing seeding at later time would be necessary.

Fig. 57. Temperature measurements at three different location in a high-pressure cell in the cooling phase, and bulk temperature derived from ideal gas law calculations. Reproduced from [37] with permission from Springer.

6.4. Further applications

Von Kármán vortex street

Imaging measurements performed at a sampling rate of several kHz or more are immensely valuable to track unstable flow behaviour in time. However, as discussed in Sections 1.4 and 3.2.2, many temperature imaging techniques, e.g. Rayleigh thermometry, require high laser energy which cannot be delivered with off-the-shelf high-repetition rate DPSS lasers. The first application of phosphor particles to kHz-rate temperature and velocity imaging used a frequency-tripled DPSS laser (355 nm, 1.3 mJ/pulse at 3 kHz) to excite seeded BAM:Eu²⁺ particles [19]. As mentioned in Section 4.4.4, when using BAM:Eu²⁺, a fluence of around 5–10 mJ/cm² is sufficient for precise single-shot measurements. Two high-speed CMOS cameras (12 bit, 1024 × 1024 pixels) in a beamsplitter configuration were used to detect the luminescence emission for intensity ratio imaging. Simultaneously a dual-cavity frequency-doubled DPSS laser (532 nm) and a high-speed CMOS camera positioned on the opposite side of the measurement plane were used for PIV. 2800 temperature-velocity images for each 0.9 s recording were stored.

The temperature calibration and evaluation of the single-pixel temperature precision were performed in the potential core of an electrically-heated jet of air. Based on statistics in the jet core, a precision of 4.9 K at 293 K (close to the noise limit of 3.8 K predicted by signal statistics) and 21.9 K at 500 K was achieved. The point here is that, since the luminescence of BAM:Eu²⁺ saturates, the low pulse energy of the DPSS laser does not significantly compromise the precision in comparison with the use of flashlamp-pumped Nd:YAG lasers. At least when the measurement domain is a few centimetres in size, the same signal per particle can be achieved. The CMOS camera performance was evaluated, see Section 3.2.3, with the finding that non-linearities were not significant either, while the higher readout noise is partly compensated with larger pixel size. This study also noted that since the laser pulse energy was constant up to 10 kHz the thermometry could actually be performed at this rate with no compromise in temperature precision. The limitation is imposed by the PIV camera, which must operate at full frame readout to maximise the resolution, and twice the repetition rate. With some DPSS lasers and CMOS cameras now on the market in 2017, temperature imaging at 40 kHz with 1,024 × 512 pixels is feasible.

In the same work the high-speed diagnostics were applied at a sampling rate of 3 kHz to the Von Kármán vortex street [19]. This is a well-known flow instability, which consists of a pattern of wake vortices that are repeatedly shed when there is a flow around a bluff body. The test case consisted of an air flow seeded with 2.4 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ phosphor particles, emanating from an 80 mm diameter pipe at a temperature of 293 K and velocity of 1.6 m/s. A 6.25 mm diameter pipe electrically-heated to 530 K was positioned horizontally in the flow. The same setup described above was used. The horizontally-orientated laser sheets intersected the flow perpendicular to and just above the heated pipe, and luminescence and scattering signals were recorded at 90° to the light sheet using 3 high-speed CMOS cameras.

Fig. 58 shows a sequence of four temperature and velocity fields measured in the wake of the heated cylinder. The mean velocity field was subtracted from the instantaneous fields to visualise the eddies. Here only every fifteenth image from the original 3 kHz recording is displayed. Counter-rotating pockets of hot gas are alternately shed from either side of the pipe due to the unsteady flow separation at the rear stagnation point. A video of these measurements is available as a supplementary material to Ref. [19]. The vortex shedding frequency was approximately 40 Hz, in good agreement with an estimated shedding frequency calculated from the Strouhal number in this regime of Reynolds number (here $Re = 700$). The diagnostics are able to resolve the transient behaviour with a high level of precision, which is essential to study infrequent or oscillatory heat and mass

Fig. 58. Temporal evolution of the temperature and velocity fields in the wake of a heated cylinder. Every fifteenth image of the 3 kHz recording is displayed. The mean velocity field has been subtracted from the instantaneous fields for visualisation of the eddies. Data from Ref[19].

transfer phenomena encountered in many flows of practical engineering importance.

Liquid fuel jets in hot air crossflow

Spray investigations using phosphors has so far been discussed in the context of liquid fuel injection in IC engines. Fuel injection is also very important in gas turbine combustors, where the breakup, atomisation and vapourisation of the fuel jet in the presence of a hot, high-velocity crossflowing gas must be properly understood. Two studies by Tan et al. reported on a joint temperature/fuel concentration/droplet detection technique using $\text{YVO}_4:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ phosphor particles [38,172].

Initially spectroscopic investigations of 50 nm and micron-size $\text{YVO}_4:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ and $\text{YAG}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$ particles dry-coated onto ceramic bars and dispersed in Jet-A fuel were conducted. Nanoparticles were washed for, to minimise the effect of particles on the spray and reduce abrasion damage to the fuel injector, but signal levels were too low. Much brighter $\text{YVO}_4:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ luminescence in the red spectral region allowed the suppression of the broadband blue-green Jet-A fluorescence signal compared with the weak blue-green emission of $\text{YAG}:\text{Dy}^{3+}$. Regardless, presumably this was not an issue since the camera exposure was delayed with respect to the laser pulse (see below). Measurements of the overall luminescence signal at temperatures between 300 and 773 K were used to derive the concentration field (also see below). The intensity ratio-temperature response of 1.8 μm $\text{YVO}_4:\text{Eu}^{3+}$ particles was investigated for various laser-camera delays. For short delay (0–10 μs), a non-monotonic behaviour and a low sensitivity were observed, while a useful response could be obtained for a delay of 100 μs . In the following a delay of 100 μs and a gate time of 30 μs was used.

In the test rig, temperature-controlled Jet-A fuel was seeded with phosphor particles and injected vertically upwards through a 0.67 mm diameter orifice in the lower wall of a rectangular channel (25.4 \times 31.75 mm), into heated crossflowing air. The laser sheet propagated downwards into the channel through a window and luminescence and Mie scattering signals were collected through another window along a single optical axis at 90° using three cameras and beamsplitters (see Section 3.2.5). The intensity ratio method was used to derive the temperature field and then applied to condition for the temperature dependence of the luminescence signal, thereby obtaining the concentration field from either luminescence image. A similar approach was discussed in the previous Section 6.2, and in Ref. [44]. Based on the assumption of equal mass transfer from liquid-phase to gas-phase between particles and fuel, a comparison between the concentration field derived from the luminescence signal, and the Mie scattering field may in principle allow the qualitative identification of regions where fuel is in the gas-phase.

Average and instantaneous temperature fields as well as average concentration and fuel Mie scattering images were presented, for a 75 m/s crossflow at a temperature of 713 K and fuel temperature of 323 K, at a momentum flux ratio of 10. The temperature increased downstream, indicating heating of the fuel by thermal mixing. The concentration profile also shows qualitatively a similar behaviour. However many artefacts are observed which can be explained from experimental considerations. One of the main issues was the long laser-camera delay (100 μs) and exposure (60 μs) used. Considering the high flow velocities used here (75 m/s), as in some of the studies described above e.g.[28,39], particles emitting luminescence were significantly displaced by up to several mm during the exposure leading to blurring of the measured fields. Also particles were transported away from the region where they were excited, so at the time of observation near the nozzle only particles which have not been illuminated are present, leading to low signals near the nozzle and displaced peak fuel concentrations. Also the Mie scattering from liquid fuel was collected at the instant of the 355 nm laser pulse. Therefore the liquid+vapour (luminescence) and liquid fuel only (Mie) concentration images were presumably displaced relative to one another. Background signals caused by luminescence of particles deposited on the wall that was multiply-scattered by the spray also resulted in artificially high concentration regions near the wall.

For such a study, clearly a phosphor with a shorter lifetime is desirable. Regarding the fuel concentrations, it was also recognised that (1) the particles do not evaporate with the fuel, but will rather concentrate to some degree in the droplets, and also (2) that the Mie signals depend on the unknown number density and size of the fuel droplets. These factors must be considered to extract quantitative fuel concentration profiles.

Air/vitiated gas mixing layer

Rothamer and coworkers measured temperature and velocity fields in a large-scale facility where two streams met behind a splitter plate to investigate turbulent mixing in high temperature flows. This has applications in e.g. afterburners. One stream was a vitiated high-temperature gas into which Jet-A fuel is normally injected, the other a clean air stream. 1.8 μm $\text{YAG}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ phosphor particles (with an Al_2O_3 coating) were used as a tracer for two-colour ratio imaging and PIV. The laser sheets (266 nm excitation for $\text{YAG}:\text{Pr}^{3+}$ and 532 nm for PIV) propagated downwards into the optically-accessible test section, to measure at two cross-stream locations in the mixing region. In one test case a bluff body was placed behind the splitter plate. Various conditions were run with the clean stream temperature \sim 500 K and 25 m/s, and vitiated stream temperatures up to 873 K and just over 100 m/s. The intensity ratio-temperature calibration was performed in a furnace to 1700 K. Although the intensity ratio peaked at 1300 K and then decreased with temperature, the maximum flow temperature (873 K) ensured there was no ambiguity.

Average and single shot temperature and velocity images of the mixing region were presented. Both streams were seeded but it was reportedly difficult to get a sufficient number of particles in the vorticated stream so only 10 to 15% of the recorded images could be used. Depending on the seeding density, it was observed that the SNR varied spatially, where it became worse in the higher-temperature vorticated flow. Still, for exemplary single shots, the precision (1σ standard deviation) in a uniform temperature region was found to be as high as 20 K at 873 K, an extraordinary 2.3%. Average temperatures compared to those measured with a thermocouple were within ~ 15 K. In this flow the buoyancy effects were small relative to the kinetic energy of the flow, and analytic solutions for a turbulent plane mixing layer could be used for additional comparison. Good agreement between these solutions and the temperature and velocity measurements were found for the cross-stream and stream-wise mixing profiles. This study is a good example of simultaneous measurements in a challenging environment: a large, enclosed facility at intermediate temperatures and high flowrates.

Film cooling

Film cooling is a key technology in modern gas turbine engines, consisting of a flow of air ('coolant') taken from the compressor stage that is directed through holes drilled at an angle in the combustor liner which then (ideally) spreads out to form a protective film. Reduction of NO_x emissions in gas turbine combustors is achieved using lean combustion, but increases the demand for fresh air in the combustor and reduces the amount of air available for film cooling. Thus, different configurations, e.g. trenched cooling holes, where the holes are placed in a transverse slot can be used to reduce mixing between coolant and combustion gases and encourage lateral spread of the coolant, reducing the cooling air requirement [240]. Most experimental studies of these flows is based on cooling effectiveness measurements at the surface e.g. [241]. However to design more efficient film cooling geometries, non-intrusive measurements of the flow temperature, velocity and derived quantities like the turbulent heat flux are needed in well-defined, generic flow configurations.

To this end, BAM:Eu^{2+} particles were used for temperature and velocity imaging of film cooling flows in an optically-accessible closed-loop wind tunnel facility. The electrically-heated main flow ($u_m = 10$ m/s and $T_m = 373$ K) was driven by a radial blower through a settling chamber into the 400 (w) \times 150 (h) mm test section. Two hole configurations were studied: a row of three cylindrical holes (diameter = 6 mm) and trenched cooling holes (test plate shown in Fig. 59). Liquid-nitrogen-cooled cooling air was supplied through these holes via a plenum and the flow temperature adjusted using an ambient air bypass. Thus critical non-dimensional parameters (velocity, density, momentum ratios) that govern the mixing and cooling jet penetration could be altered. Both the main and cooling flows were seeded with $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ BAM:Eu^{2+} particles.

The two-colour ratio imaging and PIV were performed at a repetition rate of 6 kHz using the setup shown in Fig. 59. The 532 nm laser sheets for PIV entered through a window in the top of the test section and perpendicular to the test surface, forming a vertical measurement plane down the centreline of the middle cooling hole. Initially the 355 nm laser sheet used to excite the phosphor co-propagated with the green light but, as shown in Fig. 32 (Section 5.4), this generated a very large background signal caused by the excitation of particles deposited on the test plate immediately downstream of the cooling holes. Therefore a periscope was positioned well downstream to direct the UV laser sheet horizontally as shown in Fig. 59. The periscope was continuously purged with pressurised air to prevent contamination of the turning mirror with phosphor particles. A RANS simulation indicated there was a negligible effect of the periscope and purging flow on the upstream film cooling flow. Particle luminescence and Mie scattering signals were collected through a side window using three high-speed CMOS cameras. The

Fig. 59. Diagram of the laser diagnostics used in Ref[20].

temperature calibration was performed using a simple two-point method in the main and cooling jet core, since intensity ratios derived from spectroscopy between 217 and 373 K indicated that a linear fit was reasonable over this temperature range. It was noted in another film cooling study using the same phosphor particles that the effects of multiple scattering caused the measured jet temperatures to depend on the seeding density [225]. Here it was supposed that the in-situ calibration procedure coupled with the short measurement times alleviated the issue. The camera memories permitted fully 18,000 images for each 3 s measurement run to be recorded. The 6 kHz repetition rate was chosen to resolve the shear layer fluctuations predicted at 2.6 kHz. A single shot temperature precision of 18.4 K at 373 K, at a spatial resolution of $800 \mu\text{m}$ was evaluated from the data.

Results were presented for the ordinary cylindrical and trenched holes at density $DR = \rho_c/\rho_m$ and momentum flux $I = u_c^2 \rho_c/u_m^2 \rho_m$ ratios respectively fixed at 1.6 and 8 (subscripts c and m refer to cooling and main flow). For these conditions the average temperature field (see Fig. 60) showed that for ordinary angled holes the jet was completely detached from the surface. In contrast, the trenched geometry led to a stable cooling film that appeared to be attached to the surface. However, time-resolved image sequences indicated instances where hot air broke through the cooling film and almost reached the surface. This is visible at $x/D \sim 6$ in videos of the measurements available online as supplementary material to Ref. [20]. The measured temperature and velocity fluctuations were also used to calculate the streamwise $u'_x T'$ and wall-normal $u'_z T'$ turbulent heat fluxes as shown in Fig. 61 for the cylindrical hole. Comparing the average field of Fig. 60 and the turbulent flux field of Fig. 61, it can be seen that the negative streamwise heat flux in the upper shear layer actually contradicts the aforementioned gradient diffusion hypothesis (Eq. (22)) usually adopted in RANS simulations to model the scalar flux. The instantaneous images for the cylindrical hole (see supplementary material to Ref. [20]) indicated that the jet became unstable and ejected pockets of cold air moving with a higher-than-average velocity. It was proposed that this might be responsible for the direction of the turbulent heat flux in the upper shear layer deviating from normal to the constant-temperature contours.

Fig. 60. Average temperature field for the cylindrical cooling holes. Temperature is normalised $\theta_{fi} = (T_m - T_{fi}) / (T_m - T_c)$. Jet trajectory and jet core as defined by the average and RMS velocity fields respectively are marked. From Ref. [20].

Fig. 61. Streamwise and wall-normal turbulent heat fluxes for the angled cylindrical holes. The dash-dotted line indicated the mean jet trajectory. From Ref. [20].

This study brought together a lot of advantages of the method to investigate flows of technical importance. The instantaneous measurements can be used to calculate average fields and the heat flux, but also time-resolved measurements provide interpretation of mean flow behaviour. kHz sampling rates also permit calculation of spectra to determine dominant frequencies of e.g. shear layer fluctuations. These data can be compared with numerical simulations and thereby used to develop models, e.g., large eddy simulations (LES) which aids the design of film cooling geometries in future gas turbines. Furthermore, in an actual combustor the main flow fluctuations are much higher, and these diagnostics are very suitable to track the disturbance of the cooling film by large-scale main flow eddies.

Flames

Spatially resolved temperature and velocity data is much sought after in combustion research, and as discussed in the introduction the task remains a significant challenge despite advancements in other laser-based thermometries. In principle, in flames thermographic

phosphors possess some clear advantages: 1) they are inert, 2) they have in general a high melting point (> 2000 K), and 3) they are often insensitive to the fluid environment (Sect. 4.4.3). On the other hand, the temperature range of the technique is limited by the thermal quenching of the luminescence. In a recent study [17], BAM:Eu²⁺ particles were seeded into laminar non-premixed flames with the aim of determining a) the maximum temperature the technique can measure, and how accurate the measurement are in reactive flows; and b) whether phosphor particles can survive the hot flame front and therefore whether they can be used in enclosed environments where recirculation between burned and unburned gas usually occurs.

In this study, a fuel mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen was fed to the inner tube of a coflow burner to produce a laminar non-premixed flame with tunable temperature range and gradients. In addition, the relatively simple hydrogen chemistry allowed accurate simulation. 2 μm BAM:Eu²⁺ particles were seeded in the fuel stream. The luminescence from the particles was detected using the typical two camera and beamsplitter setup (see Fig. 2), while the Mie scattered light from the particle was detected by a camera on the other side for the 2D mapping of the seeding density. Intensity ratios were converted to temperature based on a calibration curve derived from spectral measurements of BAM:Eu²⁺ powder, normalised to the room temperature ratio. To allow a spatially resolved evaluation of the measurement accuracy, an axisymmetrical numerical simulation of the flame was also performed.

The results are shown in Fig. 62. The measurements capture the gradients predicted by the simulations. As the temperature increases, the single-shot single-pixel standard deviation represented by the errorbars increases, as a result of a drop in signal. This

Fig. 62. Comparison between measured single shot, average and simulated radial temperature profiles at various heights in a laminar non-premixed N₂-diluted hydrogen-air flame (fuel stream composition by volume 66% N₂, 33% H₂, 1% CH₄). Errorbars represent the standard deviation of 25 shots. Reproduced from [17] with permission from Elsevier.

drop is predominantly caused by the thermal quenching of the luminescence, since at 1000 K the local seeding density is still a relatively high 3×10^{11} particles/m³. Higher seeding densities may slightly increase the temperature limit, but the non-intrusiveness of the technique will then be questionable.

As discussed in Section 4.4.3, the same burner running on pure hydrogen was used to probe particles post-flame to demonstrate their survivability.

7. Conclusions and future work

The use of thermographic phosphors as tracer particles in fluid flows is a promising addition to the portfolio of flow temperature diagnostics discussed in the introduction. The general method affords the advantage that the velocity can be measured at the same time, for which the same particles serve as a tracer. This is an important capability in furthering our understanding of turbulent flows, especially those involving heat transfer and/or chemical reactions. Furthermore, there is a very wide range of phosphor materials involving a variety of luminescence mechanisms which can be used to measure the temperature. Those phosphors that have been used for fluid thermometry currently cover the range from 200 to 900 K. While the higher temperature limit is imposed by phosphor-specific thermal quenching, in-principle there is no lower temperature limit. The advantages cited for the use of phosphors as remote surface temperature sensors apply in many respects to flow diagnostics too, with the features that they have a high melting point, are not consumed by chemical reactions, and there is as yet no evidence that the luminescence emissions which are actually used to derive the temperature are sensitive to the fluid composition or pressure over the short time scales encountered in turbulent flows.

Commensurate with the different luminescence responses (lifetime, spectral), this review has made clear that there are various approaches to derive temperature information, currently either at a point or in 2D. The most common approach consists of exploiting the temperature-dependence of the emission spectrum, preferably using two cameras with interference filters and a beamsplitter, which allows measurements with a short duration ($\sim 1 \mu\text{s}$), a usual requirement for measurements in turbulent flows. By virtue of the general properties of thermographic phosphors (visible emission, broad excitation spectra, insensitivity to surrounding fluid environment) the instrumentation required is comparatively simple (non-intensified cameras, Nd:YAG lasers), as is the signal processing (image division, white field correction and calibration). Planar measurements can also be performed at sustained kHz-rates, a unique capability for the time-resolved study of flow instabilities. There have been several demonstrations using various realisations of lifetime approaches, but, due to the phosphors chosen, these tended to have longer integration times. It does not seem likely that the extraordinary sensitivity of the lifetime can be exploited over a wide temperature range (100's K) in turbulent flows. Another approach involves probing individual particles, for correlated point measurements of temperature and velocity with a spatial resolution as high as 200 μm . Using a phase shift method for the temperature evaluation, high precision measurements (8 K at 850 K) were reported with this approach. Two general conclusions are apparent: that the principle of using phosphor particles as tracers is a flexible one; and also that, considering the information extracted i.e. simultaneous temperature and multi-component velocity in up to two dimensions, with high spatial and temporal resolution, the diagnostics are fairly straightforward. The method can easily be taken up, adapted and developed by other research groups with different laboratory capabilities, to suit various applications.

The review has shown that certainly not all phosphors that have been used for thermometry so far are equal in terms of thermometric performance. To meet the conditions on accurate flow tracing,

particles on the μm -scale must be dispersed in the fluid. Therefore one should be mindful of the statements in Section 2 regarding desirable phosphor properties: the phosphor must be carefully chosen to yield high signal level while allowing a short measurement duration. The luminescence properties are best characterised when particles are dispersed in a fluid, but the mass load or seeding density must be measured to provide some reference. With such methods, the emission intensity can be evaluated on a mass or per particle basis, allowing for a direct comparison of different phosphor particles, as has so far been undertaken for BAM:Eu²⁺ and ZnO. The particles can also be tested in various environment to determine potential cross-sensitivity of the measured temperature to parameters such as the gas-composition. For the phosphors and fluids tested, the insensitivity to the fluid phase and composition was in most cases confirmed, and any dependence only detected for extended exposure durations. The luminescence of BAM:Eu²⁺ particles was also shown to be unaffected by their passage through a high temperature flame.

Sources of measurement uncertainty were presented, e.g. particle temperature and velocity response times, detector response, fluence-dependence, surface luminescence, and multiple scattering. The effects of the last two phenomena are in some cases severe. A dependence of the intensity ratio on the laser fluence was observed in different phosphors to various degrees, prompting in some cases additional corrections. On the other hand, some sources of errors normally present no obstacle and the uncertainty analysis is straightforward.

The technique has been applied to a variety of test cases, in gases, liquids, and in two-phase flows. These studies range from basic proof-of-concept in heated jets, to the derivation of turbulent statistics in wind tunnels, comparison to numerical simulations, and to in-cylinder internal combustion engine measurements.

Key areas of future development

The choice of phosphor particles is clearly one of the decisive experimental parameters. Different characterisation methods have been used for bulk powders, and in gases and liquids. Phosphor particles normally possess a distribution of sizes and are irregularly-shaped. The required data are the signal of dispersed particles (with unambiguous measure of the mass or number of particles), size and morphology, the temperature quenching behaviour, and the temperature sensitivity. Unified characterisation methods and a basis for comparison of results between research groups would accelerate progress.

Without question, multiple scattering is a source of error that needs to be thoroughly studied, and as it stands, carefully and routinely considered for experiments. It may only be an issue in particular configurations involving large seeded volumes, and problematic only for certain phosphor particles. Particle deposition and the ensuing surface luminescence also present difficulties in enclosed environments. Both of these issues may be tackled with structured laser illumination. A more effective approach that targets the root of the problem would be phosphor particles that emit more luminescence relative to the amount of scattered light. The thermographic laser Doppler velocimetry approach is well-suited to enclosed environments, and recent results show that the method can efficiently reject both surface and multiple scattering signals, allowing measurements as close as 200 μm to the surface.

These developments are illustrative of the flexibility afforded by particle-based scalar measurements, for example, the extension of the technique to three-dimensional "tomographic" temperature and velocity measurements is an exciting prospect. Considering so few phosphors have been investigated in the context of fluid temperature measurements, such developments will be closely related to the identification and/or production of alternative phosphor

particles. Producing near-spherical particles with narrow size distribution would simplify the theoretical analysis and understanding of the interaction between the excitation laser and particles. The particle shape could also be engineered, to improve the absorption characteristics, reduce multiple scattering, or improve tracing abilities, for example hollow spheres. Lastly we emphasise that there is a vast variety of potential compounds which can be explored to increase the temperature range toward high temperature reacting flows, reduce cross-sensitivities to improve the measurement accuracy, and further enhance the measurement precision.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank former and current colleagues and collaborators for their valuable contributions over the last 7 years. We also gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council. Christopher Abram is funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 programme under project # 708068.

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